

**UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA
INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TÉCNICO**

**Microfluidic biochip platform for detection of stress
biomarkers in vineyards**

Cristiana Maria Filipe Domingues

Supervisor: Doctor João Pedro Estrela Rodrigues Conde

**Thesis approved in public session to obtain the PhD Degree in
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Jury final classification: Pass with Distinction

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“We’re all stories, in the end. Just make it a good one, eh?”

The Doctor

Resumo

A crise climática representa desafios significativos para a agricultura, particularmente para a viticultura, que é vital para as economias locais e o património cultural. O aumento das temperaturas, os padrões climáticos imprevisíveis e a intensificação dos stresses bióticos e abióticos ameaçam a saúde da videira, reduzindo os rendimentos e alterando a qualidade do vinho. Esses problemas são ainda mais exacerbados pelas limitações dos métodos de diagnóstico convencionais, que consomem muito tempo, exigem muitos recursos e dependem de conhecimento especializado. Enfrentar esses desafios urgentes requer ferramentas inovadoras e sustentáveis, permitindo a deteção de stress em tempo real e uma intervenção precisa para garantir a resiliência e a sustentabilidade da viticultura. As tecnologias microfluídicas apresentam uma solução inovadora para enfrentar esses desafios. Essas plataformas miniaturizadas e portáteis permitem a deteção rápida e económica de biomarcadores vitais, como o ácido abscísico (ABA), um indicador crítico do amadurecimento da fruta e do stress causado pela seca, e o ácido salicílico (SA), um marcador importante de infeções nas plantas. Ao empregar biossensores avançados e alavancar mecanismos microfluídicos (dispositivo bombeado externamente e plataforma capilar), somos capazes de desenvolver um imunoensaio competitivo microfluídico para deteção de ABA, bem como um protocolo de tratamento de amostra pronto para o campo. Também foi possível integrar o ensaio desenvolvido com um sensor ótico, tornando o dispositivo mais portátil para testes de campo. Os sistemas microfluídicos desenvolvidos combinam a facilidade de uso com a alta sensibilidade, atingindo um limite de deteção (LOD) de 10^{-6} a 10^{-3} mg/mL e 10^{-6} a 10^{-4} mg/mL para o dispositivo bombeado externamente e plataforma capilar, respetivamente. Adicionalmente, foi desenvolvida uma plataforma de deteção de SA utilizando um ensaio baseado em aptameros usando o tratamento de amostra previamente estabelecido, conseguindo um LOD de 10^{-9} a 10^{-6} mg/mL. A sua integração na viticultura e na agricultura de precisão suporta a deteção precoce do stress em plantas, permitindo aos agricultores mitigar riscos e aumentar a sustentabilidade. Além da agricultura, a versatilidade da microfluídica estende-se a aplicações biomédicas, incluindo para a descoberta de medicamentos. A plataforma para deteção de adenilato quinase (AK) *in vitro* foi desenvolvida permitindo estudar o efeito de drogas. Este dispositivo foi capaz de detetar o efeito deste medicamento em 10-100 células lisadas. Esta pesquisa destaca o papel transformador das tecnologias microfluídicas na viabilização de práticas agrícolas sustentáveis, ao mesmo tempo que contribui para a segurança alimentar global e a preservação do ecossistema. Ao abordar necessidades críticas na viticultura e agricultura como um todo, a microfluídica oferece um caminho para sistemas resilientes capazes de se adaptar aos desafios de um mundo em constante mudança.

Palavras chave: Microfluídica, Ensaios baseados em microesferas, Biossensores, Portabilidade, Ponto de atendimento

Abstract

The climate crisis poses significant challenges to agriculture, particularly viticulture, which is vital to local economies and cultural heritage. Rising temperatures, unpredictable weather patterns, and the intensification of biotic and abiotic stresses threaten grapevine health, reduce yields, and alter wine quality. These issues are further exacerbated by the limitations of conventional diagnostic methods, which are time-consuming, resource-intensive, and rely on specialized personnel. Addressing these pressing challenges requires innovative, sustainable tools capable of enabling real-time stress detection and precise intervention to ensure the resilience and sustainability of viticulture. Microfluidic technologies present a groundbreaking solution to address these challenges. These miniaturized, portable platforms enable the rapid and cost-effective detection of key biomarkers, such as abscisic acid (ABA), a critical indicator of fruit ripening and drought stress, and salicylic acid (SA), a key marker of plant infections. By employing advanced biosensors and leveraging microfluidic mechanisms (externally pumped device and capillary platform), we can develop a microfluidic competitive immunoassay for ABA detection, as well as, a field-ready sample treatment protocol. It was also possible to integrate the developed assay with an optical sensor, making the device more portable for field testing. The developed microfluidic systems combine ease of use with high sensitivity achieving a limit of detection (LOD) of 10^{-6} to 10^{-3} mg/mL and 10^{-6} to 10^{-4} mg/mL for the externally pumped device and capillary platform, respectively. Additionally, a SA detection platform was developed using an aptamer-based assay combined with a previously established sample treatment, achieving a LOD ranging from 10^{-9} to 10^{-6} mg/mL. Their integration into viticulture and precision agriculture supports early detection of plant stresses, empowering farmers to mitigate risks and enhance sustainability. Beyond agriculture, the versatility of microfluidics extends to biomedical applications, including drug discovery. The platform for adenylate kinase (AK) detection *in vitro* was developed allowing to study the effect of drugs. This device was capable of detecting the effect of this drug in as little as 10-100 lysed cells. This research highlights the transformative role of microfluidic technologies in enabling sustainable agricultural practices while contributing to global food security and ecosystem preservation. By addressing critical needs in viticulture and agriculture as a whole, microfluidics offers a pathway to resilient systems capable of adapting to the challenges of a rapidly changing world.

Keywords: Microfluidics, Bead-based assays, Biosensors, Portability, Point-of-care

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

2D	Two-dimensional
3D	Three-dimensional
5-FU	Chemotherapeutic agent 5-fluorouracil
ABA	Absciscic acid
ADC	Analog-to-digital converter
AK	Adenylate kinase
APTES	Aminopropyltriethoxysilane
a-Si: H	Hydrogenated amorphous silicon
AzA	Azelaic acid
AZI	AZELAIC ACID INDUCED gene
BR	Brassinosteroids
BSA	Bovine serum albumin
CAD	Computer-assisted design
CCD	Charge-coupled device
CK	Cytokinin
CL	Chemiluminescence
DBR	Distributed Bragg reflectors
DI	Deionised water
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
DWL	Direct write laser
ELISA	Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay
EQE	External quantum efficiency
ET	Ethylene
Fab	Fragment antigen binding
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FBS	Fetal bovine serum
Fc	Fragment crystalline
GA	Gibberellins
GFLV	Grapevine Fanleaf Virus
GLRV	Grapevine Leafroll Virus
GRBV	Grapevine Red Blotch Virus
HLX	Tungsten-halogen lamp
HPLC	High-performance liquid chromatography

HRP	Horseradish peroxidase
IAA	Indole-3-acetic acid
IPA	Isopropyl alcohol
ITO	Indium tin oxide
JA	Jasmonic acid
LAMP	Loop-mediated isothermal amplification
LDO	Linear dropout
LEDs	Light-emitting diodes
LFAs	Lateral flow assays
LOC	Lab-on-a-chip
LOD	Limit of detection
MCU	Microcontroller unit
MEMS	Microelectromechanical systems
MeOH	Methanol
MgCl₂	Magnesium chloride
mRNA	Messenger RNA
NaCl	Sodium chloride
NC	Normally closed
OSR	Oversampling ratio
OVI	International Organization of Vine and Wine
PBS	Phosphate buffer solution
PCBs	Printed circuit boards
PDMS	Polydimethylsiloxane
Pe	Péclet number
PEG	Polyethylene glycol
PGIP	PolyGalacturonase-inhibiting protein
PGMEA	Propylene glycol methyl ether acetate
PLA	Polylactic acid
PMMA	PolyMethylmethacrylate
PoC	Point-of-care
PoCT	Point-of-care testing
PR	Pathogenesis-related
qPCR	Quantitative PCR
RCA	Rolling circle amplification
Re	Reynolds number

RF	Feedback resistor
Rf-PECVD	Plasma-enhanced chemical vapour deposition
RNAseq	RNA sequencing
ROI	Region of interest
RP-HPLC	Reverse-phase HPLC
SA	Salicylic acid
SAR	Systemic acquired resistance
SELEX	Systematic evolution of ligands by exponential enrichment
SPS	Samples per second
ssDNA	Single-strand DNA
STS	Stilbene Synthase
TIA	Trans-impedance amplifier
TIR	Total internal reflection
TMB	Tetramethylbenzidine
Tris	Tris(hydroxymethyl) aminomethane
UV	Ultraviolet
UVO	Ultraviolet ozone

PART I

Chapter 1

Introduction

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1.1. Importance of fast and simple diagnostic tools in the field

The climate crisis has far-reaching implications for agriculture, particularly for viticulture, where grapevines play a crucial role in supporting local economies and cultural traditions. As climate change accelerates, the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events such as heatwaves, droughts, and heavy rainfall are increasing [1]. These phenomena disrupt the delicate balance required for grapevine growth, leading to reduced yields and alterations in grape quality, particularly in sugar content and acidity, which are vital for winemaking. Beyond climatic factors, grapevines are also vulnerable to biotic stresses, such as fungal diseases (e.g., gray mould - *Botrytis cinerea*, downy mildew - *Plasmopara viticola*, oidium/powdery mildew - *Erysiphe necator*), viral infections (Grapevine Leafroll Virus (GLRV), Grapevine Fanleaf Virus (GFLV), Grapevine Red Blotch Virus (GRBV)), and pest infestations (e.g., insects, mites, nematodes) [2][3][4]. These challenges are exacerbated by the warming climate, which creates more favourable conditions for pest proliferation and disease spread. The economic stakes of climate impacts on viticulture are significant [5][6]. Changes in grape quality and availability not only threaten local livelihoods but also disrupt global markets for wine and table grapes. Additionally, regions traditionally known for wine production may find themselves unsuitable for grape cultivation, requiring a geographical shift in vineyards, which poses logistical and economic challenges. That said, there is a need for tools that align with the need for sustainable viticulture practices, enabling farmers and vineyard managers to adapt to changing climate conditions while optimizing resources [7].

1.1.1. Phytohormones and Their Role in Plant Growth, Development, and Stress Response

Phytohormones, or plant hormones, are crucial signalling molecules that regulate plant growth, development, and responses to environmental stresses [8]. Typically, active in minute concentrations ranging from nanomolar to micromolar levels, these hormones play essential roles in various physiological processes. Auxins promote cell elongation, root initiation, and tropic responses, influencing plant architecture and vascular differentiation [9]. Cytokinins interact with auxins to promote cell division, delay leaf senescence, and coordinate organ growth by balancing auxin distribution [10]. Gibberellins stimulate processes like stem elongation, seed germination, and flowering, playing a significant role in overcoming dormancy and ensuring reproductive success [11]. Ethylene, a gaseous hormone, regulates fruit ripening, leaf abscission, and plant responses to biotic and abiotic stresses [12][13], while brassinosteroids enhance cell expansion, vascular development, and stress resilience [14].

In addition to their role in growth, phytohormones are pivotal in enabling plants to adapt to environmental stresses, such as drought and pathogen infections [8]. Several hormones are particularly important in this context (Figure 1.1. [15]): jasmonic acid (JA) [16], salicylic acid (SA) [17], and azelaic acid (AZA) are key players in the plant's defence against infections – Biotic stresses, such as those caused by *Botrytis cinerea* [4][18], while abscisic acid (ABA) and indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) are central to hydric stress responses – Abiotic stresses [19][20]. Hydric stress, the primary abiotic stress caused by drought, is becoming increasingly critical due to climate change [21]. These hormones form complex, interconnected signalling networks that allow plants to balance growth and survival under challenging conditions [22][23][24]. According to Feng *et al.* [25], the typical concentrations of ABA range from 2.64×10^{-5} mg/mL to 2.1×10^{-1} mg/mL, while SA, along with related hormones like AZA, IAA, and JA, vary from 1.38×10^{-5} mg/mL to 5.47 mg/mL. These concentration ranges provide a useful baseline for understanding their roles in stress regulation.

Figure 1.1. Chemical formula of the different biomarkers important for plant regulation [15].

1.1.2. Dynamic Interplay Among Phytohormones

The dynamic interplay among phytohormones adds complexity to plant stress responses and developmental processes. For example, ABA and SA often exhibit antagonistic roles: ABA promotes drought tolerance, while SA enhances biotic resistance. ABA primarily modifies responses to abiotic stress like drought and salinity by inducing stomatal closure and increasing callose deposition, which also plays important roles in limiting pathogen invasion. However, while ABA helps protect against abiotic stress, it can suppress SA-mediated immune responses. In contrast, SA activates defences against pathogens, but its role in promoting biotic resistance

can interfere with ABA's drought tolerance mechanisms. Consequently, plants must carefully balance these signals to optimize responses to both abiotic and biotic stresses [24][26]. Meanwhile, JA and SA can either cooperate or oppose each other depending on the type of pathogen encountered [22]. Research by Ana Margarida Fortes has highlighted the multifaceted roles of phytohormones, particularly in grapevine physiology, where hormones like auxins, ABA, ethylene, and brassinosteroids interact dynamically to regulate processes such as sugar accumulation, fruit softening, and resilience under both water stress and infections (Figure 1.2) [8][13][23][27][28].

Figure 1.2. Pathways and interactions between the different phytohormones. The signalling pathways of cytokinin (CK), SA, auxin, ABA, gibberellins (GA), brassinosteroids (BR), ethylene (ET), and JA are depicted with their respective signalling molecules, transcription factors, and target genes. Arrows indicate activation relationships, while lines ending with a bar represent inhibition. Synergistic and antagonistic interactions among these pathways regulate processes such as growth, defence responses (including expression of PR and PDF1.2 genes), stomatal closure, and callose deposition. The DELLA protein functions as a central integrator, coordinating crosstalk between different hormones and contributing to the balance between development and defence [28].

1.1.3. Cultivar-Specific Variability in Phytohormone Concentrations

According to the International Code of Nomenclature, a cultivar is "an assemblage of plants that has been selected for a particular attribute or combination of attributes and that is distinct, uniform, and stable in these characteristics" [29]. Since phytohormone concentrations can vary

significantly between cultivars, different grapevine cultivars exhibit distinct hormonal profiles throughout their growth, development, and stress responses [13][30]. This variability highlights the importance of understanding the hormonal crosstalk that drives plant adaptation to environmental conditions. Continuous monitoring of grape cultivars across successive seasons can offer valuable insights into the dynamic changes in phytohormone concentrations. Such studies would deepen our understanding of the relationship between phytohormone levels, developmental stages, and stress responses, paving the way for more targeted strategies to enhance plant resilience in the face of climate change and pathogen pressure.

1.1.4. Individual Phytohormones in Stress and Development

1.1.4.1. ABA

ABA is a key phytohormone involved in several biological processes, including water regulation, osmotic stress tolerance, and seed germination [31][32]. Its role in osmotic stress tolerance is particularly significant, as ABA induces the production of dehydration tolerance proteins in most plant cells [33][34]. The chemical formula is represented in Figure 1.1. Moreover, ABA inhibits cell division and helps plants adjust to cold temperatures. Synthesized in response to stress, ABA is primarily produced in the roots and transported to the leaves [35]. Under drought conditions, the roots produce ABA, which is then transported to the leaves, where it alters the osmotic potential of stomatal cells. This results in stomatal closure, reducing transpiration, and conserving water during stress [34][36]. Therefore, ABA production increases as stress intensifies [37]. In grapevines, ABA plays a critical role in berry ripening during the *veraison* phase, which marks the colour change in grape berries, influencing processes such as sugar accumulation and berry softening, especially under conditions of water stress [8][34].

1.1.4.2. IAA

IAA is the primary auxin responsible for regulating cell elongation and growth in plants. It plays a crucial role in apical dominance, root initiation, and tropic responses like phototropism and gravitropism [20]. IAA promotes root growth, particularly lateral root formation, which enhances water uptake under drought conditions. It works synergistically with ABA, which triggers stomatal closure to conserve water, while IAA maintains a balance between growth and stress adaptation. Additionally, IAA interacts with other hormones, such as SA and JA, to activate defence mechanisms against pathogens. IAA also regulates fruit ripening, where it controls cell

expansion and development, impacting fruit quality and yield [8][20]. The chemical formula is shown in Figure 1.1.

1.1.4.3. JA

JA is essential for regulating plant defense and developmental processes. It is synthesized in response to pathogen attacks at the infection site and can move to other plant organs to initiate defense responses [16][38]. The chemical formula is shown in Figure 1.1. JA is not a volatile compound itself but produces a volatile derivative, methyl jasmonate, which can be transported to distant tissues, even from other plants. This volatile form, along with other jasmonates, triggers early defence mechanisms, such as the biosynthesis of pathogenesis-related (PR) proteins [39][40]. JA is also involved in various developmental processes, including seed germination, root growth, and flower development. Through its role in activating defence pathways and regulating growth, JA contributes to the plant's overall resilience to both biotic and abiotic stresses [16][40][39].

1.1.4.4. SA

SA plays a pivotal role in plant defence, particularly in the systemic acquired resistance (SAR) pathway [7][8][17]. During an infection, SA is produced as part of an immune response to protect healthy tissues from pathogen spread. The accumulation of SA at the infection site forms a protective barrier, limiting pathogen spread and activating defence mechanisms [41]. The chemical formula for SA is shown in Figure 1.1.

1.1.4.5. AzA

AzA, a regulatory molecule, plays a key role in plant defence, particularly through the SAR response [42]. The chemical formula is shown in Figure 1.1. AzA is produced when fatty acids are cleaved and converted, initiating a cascade of defence responses. AzA induces the AZELAIC ACID INDUCED (AZI) gene, which leads to the synthesis of SA [43][44][45]. The accumulation of SA at the infection site helps establish a protective barrier and limits pathogen spread. In addition to activating SA synthesis, AzA has antimicrobial properties, directly aiding in pathogen resistance. AzA is also being explored as a potential early biomarker for pathogen detection, as its production precedes SA synthesis during infection [46].

1.1.5. Interplay and crosstalk between phytohormones in stress adaptation and developmental processes

Although hormones have a primary function, they interact dynamically with one another, resulting in overlapping and multifaceted roles that extend beyond individual functions (Figure 1.2) [27][32][30]. Understanding the roles and dynamics of these hormones is crucial for enhancing plant resilience, particularly in grapevines [13][17]. Monitoring phytohormone concentrations across grapevine cultivars and seasons provides critical insights into the plant's stress response, enabling strategies to improve productivity and resilience amid climate change. Since phytohormones play distinct roles in various tissues, such as leaves, roots, and fruits (e.g., grape berries), analysing specific tissues like leaves and berries helps reveal how their concentrations vary with stress and developmental stages. This targeted approach offers a comprehensive understanding of hormonal dynamics and their impact on plant growth and stress tolerance.

1.1.6. Anatomy and Composition of the Grape Berry

The anatomy and composition of a grape berry, as depicted in Figure 1.3 [32], reveals its structural and chemical complexity. A significant component of the berry is the pericarp, which is divided into three distinct layers: the exocarp, mesocarp, and endocarp. The exocarp, or "skin," varies in thickness and properties depending on the grape cultivar [47]. Beneath the exocarp lies the mesocarp, or pulp, composed of thin-walled, highly vacuolated parenchyma cells of varying sizes. During berry development, these cells undergo division and expansion, with vacuole enlargement causing the cell walls to become thinner [48][49]. The endocarp forms the innermost layer of the pericarp, surrounding the seeds and contributing to the structural integrity of the berry.

The grape berry's physical and chemical characteristics are essential for the quality of its products, such as wine and grape juice. Its composition includes water; sugars like glucose and fructose; organic acids, such as tartaric and citric acids; nitrogenous compounds; minerals; phenolics like anthocyanins, which provide the red, purple, or blue pigmentation of dark-skinned grapes [50]; lipids; and volatile compounds responsible for the fruit's and wine's aromas [51]. This intricate composition makes the grape berry an ideal subject for this study.

Figure 1.3. Schematic of the grape berry. The constituents of the fruit are present in the scheme [32].

1.1.7. The Growing Need for Innovative Solutions in Agriculture

As the global population continues to rise, projected to reach 9.8 billion by 2050 and 11.2 billion by 2100, the demand for food and agricultural resources is set to increase significantly. Plants are central to meeting this demand, providing 80% of the food consumed globally and 98% of the atmospheric oxygen breathed [2][52]. However, environmental stresses—such as drought, salinity, and pathogen attacks—pose severe threats to agricultural productivity, with losses of up to 70% reported in some cases. These challenges are further compounded by climate change, which intensifies the frequency and severity of abiotic and biotic stresses on crops [2].

To address these challenges, the sustainable development of the agricultural sector is essential. Efforts must focus on improving plant resilience, enhancing productivity, and ensuring environmental sustainability. Traditional agricultural practices alone are insufficient to meet these demands [52]. Consequently, the integration of advanced technologies into farming practices is becoming increasingly vital [53]. Precision agriculture, driven by innovations such as remote sensing, big data analytics, and diagnostic tools, offers promising solutions. These approaches enable farmers to optimize resources and respond proactively to environmental challenges. Among the array of emerging technologies, microfluidics stands out as a transformative tool for advancing plant science and improving agricultural sustainability [54].

Microfluidics provides a fast, cheap, and easy-to-use solution for diagnosing biotic and abiotic stresses in plants. These devices are portable, operate with minimal reagent volumes, and

deliver precise control over reaction conditions, such as mass and heat transfer, allowing for faster reaction times and reduced costs [55][56]. By detecting key stress biomarkers, such as ABA, in real-time, microfluidic devices enable timely interventions to mitigate the effects of environmental and biological stresses on crops [57]. In addition to their diagnostic capabilities, microfluidic devices achieve rapid and accurate results, providing actionable data to farmers and vineyard managers. Their integration with sensors and automation facilitates seamless incorporation into precision agricultural systems, enabling continuous monitoring and adaptive management strategies [52]. The adoption of these technologies represents a critical step towards ensuring the resilience of agricultural systems. The integration of microfluidics into viticulture and broader agricultural practices offers a pathway to safeguard productivity and sustainability. By mitigating the risks posed by environmental stresses and supporting precision agriculture, these innovations will not only enhance crop resilience but also contribute to global efforts to meet the challenges of feeding a growing population and preserving vital ecosystems in the face of a rapidly changing climate.

1.2. The field of microfluidics and examples of microfluidic devices

The push for miniaturization across diverse technological domains catalysed the emergence of microelectromechanical systems (MEMS), a groundbreaking field that enabled the fabrication of devices ranging in size from 1 to 300 μm . Initially established in the 1980s, MEMS primarily focused on mechanical applications. However, by the 1990s, advancements in this field extended its utility to encompass biological, chemical, and multidisciplinary scientific applications, transforming its scope and potential impact. One of the most notable innovations arising from MEMS technology was the precise control and manipulation of fluid flow on a microscale. This capability led to the birth of a distinct discipline now known as microfluidics. Microfluidics is broadly defined as “the study of flows, whether simple or complex, mono- or multiphase, that circulate within artificial microsystems” [58]. This field has since evolved into a cornerstone of modern microscale engineering, enabling the exploration of phenomena and processes that were previously inaccessible due to scale limitations.

Microfluidic systems present numerous advantages that have propelled their adoption across diverse scientific and industrial domains. One of their most notable strengths is the reduced consumption of samples and reagents, making them highly cost-efficient. These systems also enable rapid analysis and high-throughput screening of catalysts, as well as the optimization of chemical processes. Furthermore, microfluidics excels in integrating multiple functionalities—such as sample preparation, separation, and purification—into a single compact device, streamlining workflows and enhancing operational efficiency [59][60].

Microfluidics also plays a pivotal role in the development of biosensors, which are analytical devices designed to detect and measure biological events by converting them into quantifiable signals proportional to the concentration of the target analyte. These biosensors have become critical tools in diagnostics due to their ability to conduct high-throughput screenings with minimal resource requirements. Widely recognized examples of microfluidic biosensors include pregnancy tests and blood glucose monitors, which have revolutionized point-of-care (PoC) diagnostics by making them more portable, accessible, and affordable [61][62][63]. Recent advancements in microfluidic-based biosensors have further enhanced their application in PoC diagnostics. These devices are capable of analysing small sample volumes (10^{-9} – 10^{-18} liters), minimizing costly reagent consumption, automating sample preparation, and reducing processing time [63]. Moreover, the development of integrated microfluidic devices for bioanalysis has been emphasized for their potential uses in PoC diagnostics [64].

In addition to these applications, the integration of MEMS and microfluidics has opened up significant opportunities for advancements in personalized medicine, environmental monitoring, and food safety. MEMS technology enables the miniaturization of microfluidic devices, allowing them to operate efficiently with low power consumption and minimal sample volumes while achieving high sensitivity and specificity. These capabilities make microfluidic systems indispensable for researchers and healthcare professionals, bridging the gap between engineering and biological sciences and fostering innovation in both fields [65][66][67].

Despite their advantages, microfluidic systems face unique challenges. One notable limitation arises from the use of small sample volumes [56]. While these are cost-effective and reduce waste, they may contain only a limited number of molecules or particles for analysis. This small quantity can constrain the system's ability to detect or measure substances, particularly when working with very low concentrations. As a result, sensitivity—the ability to accurately detect small amounts of a target substance—may be affected. Similarly, detection limits—the smallest quantity of a substance that the system can reliably measure—can become a concern if the device requires more molecules than the small sample volume contains [68][69][70].

Overall, the convergence of MEMS and microfluidics represents a transformative innovation, enabling precise control of microscale systems while addressing real-world problems in diagnostics, research, and industry. These technologies not only improve efficiency and reduce costs but also provide novel solutions that push the boundaries of science and engineering [65].

1.2.1. General microfluidic concepts

1.2.1.1. Surface-to-volume ratio

In microfluidics, understanding how certain geometrical properties change with scale reduction is crucial. As devices become smaller, their surface-to-volume ratio increases, which significantly impacts their performance. For example, in the case of a cylinder, the surface-to-volume ratio is given by the following equation:

$$\frac{\text{Surface}}{\text{Volume}} = \frac{2\pi(r \times h + r^2)}{\pi r^2 \times h} = 2 \left(\frac{1}{r} + \frac{1}{h} \right) \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

Where r represents the radius and h represents the height of the cylinder. As the scale is reduced, the surface-to-volume ratio increases rapidly. This results in a larger surface area relative to the volume of the system, enhancing processes that rely on surface interactions, such as molecular absorption, chemical reactions, and surface-driven phenomena like capillary flow. In

microfluidic systems, this increased ratio allows for more efficient analysis, boosting sensitivity and enabling faster, more accurate detection of low-concentration substances [71].

1.2.1.2. The Reynolds Number

Fluid flow in microfluidic systems is characterized by the Reynolds Number (Re), a dimensionless quantity that quantifies the relative significance of inertial and viscous forces in a fluid, defined as:

$$Re = \frac{\textit{inertial forces}}{\textit{viscous forces}} = \frac{\rho UL}{\mu} \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

In this context, ρ is the fluid density, U is the velocity of the fluid, L is the characteristic dimension of the system, and μ is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid. When the Reynolds Number is below 1000, the flow is classified as laminar, characterized by smooth and orderly motion primarily governed by viscous forces. This results in pronounced interactions between the fluid and the walls of the microchannel, as the flow profile is heavily influenced by the viscous drag exerted by the channel surfaces. Conversely, when the Reynolds Number surpasses 2000, the flow transitions to a turbulent state, marked by chaotic and irregular motion dominated by inertial forces. The intermediate range, between 1000 and 2000, is known as the transition region, where the flow gradually shifts from laminar to turbulent behaviour [56][71].

1.2.1.3. The Péclet Number

The Péclet number (Pe) is a dimensionless parameter that describes the relative importance of advective transport (fluid flow) compared to diffusive transport (molecular diffusion) in microscale fluid systems. It plays a critical role in understanding heat and mass transfer within microchannels, determining whether advection or diffusion dominates. Mathematically, the Péclet number is defined as:

$$Pe = \frac{v.L}{D} \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

where v is the characteristic velocity of the fluid, L is the characteristic length scale, and D is the diffusion coefficient. A high Péclet number indicates that advection, driven by fluid flow,

dominates the transport process, while a low Péclet number suggests diffusion is the primary mechanism [56].

1.2.2. Microfabrication

Microfluidic structures are typically designed at micrometer or submicron scales and consist of fluidic components such as channels, mixers, pumps, reservoirs, inlets, and outlets [72]. These devices are fabricated using well-established microfabrication techniques, including soft lithography, photolithography, etching, and deposition (Figure 1.4). This section focuses on various microfabrication methods, with a particular emphasis on photolithography and soft-lithography, which are employed in this work.

1.2.2.1. Photolithography

Photolithography is a precise technique for patterning substrates at microscopic scales, essential for fabricating microfluidic devices. Due to the susceptibility of microscale structures to contamination, the process is conducted in clean rooms, where particulate levels, temperature, and humidity are strictly controlled to ensure accuracy and integrity [73].

Photolithography using a Direct Write Laser (DWL) system and positive photoresist is a precise and versatile technique commonly used in the fabrication of microfluidic devices. The process begins with the preparation of a clean substrate, such as a glass substrate, to eliminate contaminants. A thin layer of aluminium (or a similar UV-opaque material) is then deposited on the substrate, followed by the application of a positive photoresist, such as PFR7790G. This light-sensitive material undergoes chemical changes when exposed to ultraviolet (UV) light, making exposed areas soluble in a developer solution. The photoresist is spin-coated to ensure a uniform layer and soft-baked to remove solvents and harden the coating. A key feature of the DWL system is its ability to directly use a Computer-Assisted Design (CAD) file to define the desired pattern. This eliminates the need for a physical photomask, as the UV laser directly transfers the CAD design onto the photoresist layer with exceptional precision. The focused laser beam scans the surface of the substrate, altering the chemical properties of the exposed regions of the photoresist. This direct patterning approach is highly versatile and enables the creation of intricate and finely detailed microstructures essential for microfluidic applications. After exposure, the substrate is immersed in a developer solution. The areas of the positive photoresist that were exposed to the laser dissolve in the solution, revealing the underlying aluminium layer, while the unexposed

photoresist remains intact, acting as a protective mask. The aluminium can then be selectively etched to transfer the desired pattern to the substrate. Once the patterning and etching are complete, the remaining photoresist is stripped away, leaving behind the final microstructure. These photolithographic masks may be reused many times to create reusable moulds that contain the same features [74].

The mould fabrication process begins with a silicon substrate, on which a layer of negative photoresist, such as SU-8, is spin-coated. The thickness of the photoresist typically varies depending on its intended role—either as a sacrificial layer or as a structural layer, such as when used for fabricating microfluidic moulds. Negative photoresists are light-sensitive materials in which the exposed regions become cross-linked and insoluble in the developer solution, while the unexposed areas remain soluble and are removed during the development step. After spin-coating, a soft bake is performed to eliminate any residual solvents that did not fully evaporate during the coating process. Next, the photomask is carefully aligned with the coated substrate, and the assembly is exposed to a uniform beam of UV light. This exposure induces chemical reactions in the photoresist, altering its solubility and transferring the photomask's pattern onto the photoresist layer. After exposure, the substrate is developed, and the unexposed areas of the negative photoresist are washed away, leaving behind the cross-linked pattern that mirrors the mask design. The result is a detailed mould, which is then used in the soft-lithography process to create the final microfluidic device or structure [74].

1.2.2.2. Soft-lithography

Soft-lithography is a microfabrication technique that involves the use of elastomeric materials to replicate microstructures with high precision. The most commonly used elastomer is polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), a silicon-based polymer known for its excellent rapid prototyping capabilities, ease of fabrication, and cost-effectiveness. PDMS is particularly favoured for microfluidic applications due to its biocompatibility, elasticity, optical transparency, gas permeability, low water permeability, chemical inertia, nontoxicity, and good thermal stability [75][76]. These properties make PDMS an ideal material for creating microstructures that require fine detail, such as microchannels, without the need for expensive equipment.

PDMS belongs to a family of polymers composed of repeating units of $-(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SiO}_2-$, and it forms an elastomer when polymerized in the presence of a reticulating agent at temperatures higher than 70°C. The ability to mould PDMS into submicrometer features enables the fabrication of highly detailed microfluidic devices, making it a go-to material for prototyping in research laboratories and industries. Additionally, PDMS is hydrophobic in its untreated state, but surface

treatment using oxygen plasma can make it temporarily hydrophilic. This surface treatment forms self-assembled siloxane monolayers, enabling it to bond irreversibly with surfaces like silicon, glass, or even PDMS itself, a process known as sealing [74].

Once the mould is ready, PDMS is poured over it, and the mixture is heated in an oven, where it polymerizes and solidifies. After the curing process, the PDMS structure is peeled off from the mould, resulting in a flexible elastomeric layer with well-defined microchannels or structures. To complete the microfluidic device, the PDMS microstructure is then sealed to another surface, typically a glass or PDMS substrate, to create closed channels. This sealing process is achieved by exposing the PDMS to oxygen plasma treatment, which activates its surface to form bonds with the other treated surface, ensuring a permanent and airtight seal [74]. The resulting microfluidic device is now capable of directing the flow of liquids through the microchannels for various applications, including lab-on-a-chip (LoC) devices and biosensors.

The full fabrication is highlighted in Figure 1.4.

Figure 1.4. Steps of fabrication of: 1) Aluminium hard masks; 2) SU-8 negative photoresist mould; and 3) PDMS structures used for trapping beads. The photoresists 1 and 2 should be selected to allow the spin-coating of a thinner and thicker SU-8 layer, respectively.

1.3. Detection methods for phytohormones

High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is a gold standard in biomarker detection due to its high precision, accuracy, and capacity to separate complex biomolecular mixtures [77][78]. HPLC is an analytical technique used to separate and quantify components in a mixture based on their interaction with two phases: the stationary phase (which remains fixed) and the mobile phase (which moves through the system) [77][78]. The separation is driven by the differing affinities of each component for these phases [79]. Components with a stronger attraction to the stationary phase are retained longer, while those more attracted to the mobile phase elute faster, creating a chromatogram with distinct peaks corresponding to each component's retention time. In reverse-phase HPLC (RP-HPLC), the stationary phase is non-polar and the mobile phase is more polar. Polar compounds in the sample interact more with the mobile phase and elute quickly, while non-polar compounds, like the biomarker ABA, are retained by the stationary phase, eluting later [77]. This allows the separation of polar impurities (eluting first) from the non-polar target biomarker. The system includes components like mobile phase tanks, pumps, injectors, columns, detectors, and waste containers to facilitate and record the separation process (Figure 1.5) [79]. This technique is particularly effective in controlled laboratory settings, such as in the analysis of plant hormones like ABA, making it indispensable in research and analytical chemistry [79].

Figure 1.5. Principal components of an HPLC [79].

However, the sophisticated equipment, operational expertise, and stationary setup required for HPLC make it unsuitable for PoC or field-based applications. To address these limitations, portable and adaptable methods are gaining prominence, with biosensor systems emerging as a leading alternative [80]. These systems, known for their specificity and ease of integration into

microfluidic platforms, offer practical solutions for on-site diagnostics and real-time monitoring, bridging the gap between laboratory precision and field applicability [81][82][83].

Biosensors, first pioneered in the 1960s by Leland C. Clark, are self-contained integrated systems designed to detect analytes of biological or chemical interest selectively and quantitatively [84]. These devices consist of two main modules: the microfluidic biological immobilization module (or biorecognition element) that interacts specifically with the target analyte, and the integrated detection module (or transduction element) that converts this interaction into a measurable signal [85][86]. Biosensors are highly versatile and capable of detecting a wide range of substances, including biological molecules like DNA, proteins, cells, and exosomes, as well as ions, dissolved gases, drugs, and toxins [83][87]. Biosensors can be classified according to the type of biorecognition element (bioreceptor) or the signal transduction mechanism employed [88][89]. The bioreceptors, which determine the sensor's specificity, include antibody-based sensors, aptamer-based sensors, enzyme-based sensors, nucleic acid-based sensors, and cell-based sensors.

1.3.1. Biosensors Classified by the Type of Biological Recognition Element

1.3.1.1. Antibody-based sensors

Antibodies are Y-shaped glycoproteins of the immunoglobulin supergene family, produced as part of the immune system's defence against pathogens [90]. Structurally, they are comprised of four polypeptide chains: two identical heavy chains and two identical light chains, linked by disulfide bonds at the hinge region – Figure 1.6 [91]. These chains are organized into distinct regions—the variable (V) region and the constant (C) region [92]. The V region, located at the amino-terminal ends of the heavy and light chains, forms the antigen-binding site and is highly variable, enabling specific recognition and binding of epitopes on antigens through non-covalent interactions such as hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic forces, and van der Waals forces. The specificity and affinity of these interactions are critical for the antibody's function [90]. The constant region, or Fragment Crystalline (Fc), remains largely conserved within antibodies of the same class and mediates immune system interactions. This region is responsible for binding to effector cells and activating immune responses such as phagocytosis and complement activation [90]. Based on their heavy chain structures, antibodies are categorized into five isotypes: IgG, IgA, IgM, IgD, and IgE, with IgG being the most abundant in human serum [92][93].

Antibodies can be polyclonal or monoclonal. Polyclonal antibodies, derived from multiple B-cell clones, recognize multiple epitopes on an antigen, whereas monoclonal antibodies,

produced from a single B-cell clone, are specific to one epitope [90]. For small molecules like ABA or JA, which cannot independently elicit an immune response, conjugation to larger carrier proteins such as Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) creates immunogenic haptens, enabling antibody production [90][94].

Antibodies' structural versatility allows the generation of functional fragments through limited proteolytic degradation. These fragments, such as the Fragment Antigen Binding (Fab), $F(ab')_2$, and Fc regions, retain their binding properties and expand the utility of antibodies in specialized applications [95]. Their high specificity and binding affinity, facilitated by a network of non-covalent interactions, ensure resilience during experimental procedures like washing steps, making antibodies indispensable in immunoassays [94].

Figure 1.6. Schematic representation of antibody molecular structure [91].

Antibody-based sensors rely on a standardized Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA). Immunoassays can be broadly categorized into competitive and non-competitive formats, each with distinct principles and applications. In a competitive immunoassay (Figure 1.7A) [94], the target analyte in the sample competes with a labelled version of the same analyte for a limited number of binding sites on the antibody. The signal generated is inversely proportional to the analyte concentration; higher analyte levels result in lower signal intensities [96]. This format is particularly useful for small molecules, such as hormones or drugs, where it may be difficult to produce two antibodies for a sandwich assay [94]. In contrast, non-competitive immunoassays (Figure 1.7B) [94], such as the sandwich immunoassay, involve two antibodies that bind to different epitopes on the target analyte. One antibody captures the analyte, while the second, labelled antibody provides the detectable signal. This approach is highly specific and

sensitive, as the signal is directly proportional to the analyte concentration [97]. Non-competitive assays are commonly used for larger biomolecules like proteins, where multiple binding sites are accessible [94]. Another example of non-competitive immunoassays is the "direct immunoassay," where a single antibody is directly labelled and binds to the target analyte, eliminating the need for a second antibody.

Figure 1.7. Diagram of (A) a competitive immunoassay, and (B) an immunometric assay (sandwich immunoassay), and their corresponding calibration curves [94].

Both competitive and non-competitive immunoassay formats can be tailored to suit various detection needs and are integral to the development of microfluidic diagnostic devices [98]. By adapting these immunoassay principles to microfluidic platforms, it is possible to achieve precise, high-throughput biomarker detection in compact, cost-effective, and portable systems, making them ideal for PoC diagnostics and field-based applications [63]. These platforms enable the rapid and reliable detection of biomarkers, paving the way for innovative healthcare solutions. The combination of antibodies' structural adaptability, precise targeting, and robust binding properties

underscores their crucial role in diagnostics, research, and technological advancements, including microfluidic systems for biosensing [63][64].

In order to optimize antibody performance in these microfluidic systems, Protein A from the cell wall of *Staphylococcus aureus* can be used as a ligand to bind the antibody. This molecule binds with high affinity to the Fc region of IgG, improving antibody orientation away from the immobilization surface. This enhances antibody-antigen binding and increases the sensitivity of the assay [90][94][99][100]. Therefore, antibody-antigen interactions make immunoassays a vital tool in the biotechnological field, particularly in the development of highly sensitive detection systems integrated into microfluidic platforms.

While antibody-based systems are widely used due to their high specificity, sensitivity, and adaptability, alternative detection techniques are gaining traction, particularly in the context of microfluidic platforms, due to their robustness and adaptability in various environments [61].

1.3.1.2. Aptamer-based sensors

Aptamers are short single-strand DNA molecules prepared *in vitro* that have a high affinity and specificity, binding to the target by folding into tertiary structures [101]. These molecules are comparable to monoclonal antibodies, despite belonging to a different class of biomolecules. Although antibodies have the advantage of low detection limits (even picomolar levels of analyte are accessible) and specificity, aptamers in addition to these advantages have several others, such as low cost, better thermal stability (due to their robust phosphodiester backbone) and can be generated against any desired target, such as non-immunogenic targets, like toxic small molecules or even single molecules. In addition, DNA has a longer shelf life than antibodies [102][103][104].

1.3.1.3. Enzymatic sensors

Enzyme-based sensors incorporate enzymes into the biorecognition layer to catalyse specific reactions with the target analyte or substrate. The detection process involves monitoring the resulting reaction products or byproducts, providing an accurate measure of the analyte [105]. These sensors are widely used in applications such as glucose monitoring, where enzyme-catalysed reactions play a crucial role in signal generation [106][107].

1.3.1.4. Nucleic acid-based sensors

Nucleic acid-based sensors employ DNA or RNA sequences as bioreceptors to detect complementary nucleic acid strands [108]. These sensors play a vital role in genetic testing, pathogen detection, and molecular diagnostics [109][110]. The underlying principle is the hybridization process, where a single-stranded nucleic acid probe immobilized on the sensor surface recognizes and binds to its complementary target sequence in a sample. This interaction occurs through the formation of stable hydrogen bonds between the two nucleic acid strands, enabling precise and reliable detection [111][112].

1.3.1.5. Cell-based sensors

Cell-based sensors utilize living cells as bioreceptors to detect environmental changes, toxins, or biologically active analytes [113][114][115]. These sensors monitor cellular activity or metabolic changes in response to various stimuli. They can measure functional information such as changes in intracellular or extracellular microenvironments and cellular responses to external factors like drugs, receptor ligands (chemical stimuli), or applied electrical potentials.

Biosensors can also be classified based on the signal transduction mechanism employed by the transducer, which converts the biological response into a measurable signal.

1.3.2. Biosensors Classified by Transducer Type

Various transduction techniques are used to convert the generated signal, including electrochemical [116], optical [117][118], piezoelectric [119], and magnetic methods [120]. The choice of transduction mechanism depends on the microfluidic application. Considering the different types of transduction techniques, this work focuses on optical sensors. The reason for this is the molecule labelling process with a fluorophore is straightforward, and the INESC-MN group (BioMEMS) has experience in the fabrication of this type of biosensor.

1.3.2.1. Optical biosensors

Optical biosensors, widely used in LoC devices, detect changes in light properties caused by biorecognition events. Known for their exceptional sensitivity, they often utilize fluorescent, chemiluminescent, or colorimetric tags in biomolecular recognition assays [121]. These optical transduction techniques are highly valued in biosensors and biotechnology due to their ability to amplify signals from single transducers, such as fluorophores or enzymes, significantly enhancing sensitivity and detection capabilities [122].

A variety of labelling techniques have been developed to tag biomolecules with fluorophores or enzymes, enabling multiple detection modes. Fluorophore labels can be organic, such as FITC, BODIPY FL[®], and Alexa Fluor[®] (A430), or inorganic, like quantum dots (e.g., Qdot 605). Enzymes such as horseradish peroxidase (HRP) can catalyse substrates like luminol for chemiluminescence or 3,3',5,5'-Tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) for colorimetry. Fluorescence transduction requires external light sources and filtering of excitation light to detect the emitted fluorescence accurately. In contrast, chemiluminescence transduction does not require external light sources and can use a constant substrate flow to sustain enzymatic reactions at maximum velocity. Colorimetry, which employs various enzyme substrates, enables signal transduction through absorption measurement or image analysis of the resulting coloured products.

For PoC devices, colorimetry is often preferred due to its simplicity and lack of dependence on additional equipment. However, microfluidic platforms designed to be paired with laboratory systems can benefit from fluorescence and chemiluminescence, leveraging their high sensitivity [121]. Standard optical detection systems, including microscopes and charge-coupled device (CCD) cameras, are commonly used to monitor and quantify signals in these setups [123][124]. However, their reliance on bulky equipment can limit the portability and practicality of the device for PoC applications. Advancements in miniaturization are now focusing on integrating such technologies into compact formats, enabling broader applicability and the development of portable and high-performance diagnostic devices. These advancements in optical biosensing underscore their crucial role in achieving high sensitivity and adaptability across both portable and integrated diagnostic systems [125][126].

The integration of biosensors into microfluidic platforms leverages their high sensitivity, specificity, and adaptability to create powerful diagnostic and analytical tools [63]. Microfluidic systems provide precise control over small fluid volumes, enabling rapid detection, efficient reagent usage, and enhanced signal-to-noise ratios. These features make miniaturized microfluidic-based biosensors particularly well-suited for PoC testing applications, where on-site or near-sample testing is essential. A key component of PoC devices is a microfluidic system with an integrated readout device, which ensures operational transparency, mobility, and stability while minimizing power consumption and human intervention [61][64]. This approach reduces human error, requires minimal invasiveness, and enhances the usability of the device. These combined advantages have positioned microfluidic biosensors as indispensable tools in healthcare, environmental monitoring, and biotechnology [61]. Below are notable examples that highlight the potential of these technologies in real-world scenarios.

1.4. Microfluidic-based biosensors

The host group at INESC-MN has developed advanced microfluidic platforms for the detection of single-strand DNA (ssDNA), antibodies, proteins [127], and small molecules such as toxins and metabolites (Figure 1.8A) [128][129]. These platforms have recently been enhanced by the incorporation of functionalized nanoporous microbeads into biochips [130], improving detection sensitivity and specificity. Additionally, miniaturized photodetectors for optical transduction [131] and innovative on-chip sample preparation methods [132] further strengthen the system's capabilities. A notable recent advancement is the use of hydrophilic PDMS to facilitate capillary-driven flow, which eliminates the need for external pumping systems [133]. These technologies collectively provide a robust technical foundation for this thesis project.

Although specific examples of PoC detection of phytohormones using microfluidic biosensors remain limited, the integration of microfluidics in biosensor development has shown significant potential across various applications [64][82]. For instance, Feng *et al.* [25] introduced an optical aptamer-based sensor integrated with a microfluidic capillary interface for detecting the plant hormone ABA. This system demonstrated a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.1 μM , showcasing its high sensitivity and suitability for precise hormone quantification (Figure 1.8B). Similarly, early microfluidic systems for hormone detection in grapes were pioneered by Brás *et al.*, who developed an enzymatic assay to quantify AzA indirectly. This method relied on the inhibitory effect of AzA on the tyrosinase enzyme activity, with the reduction in enzyme activity serving as a proxy for hormone concentration. The system demonstrated the capability to detect AzA with a LOD of 5 μM (Figure 1.8C) [134].

In addition to biosensors for detecting phytohormones, several platforms have been developed that specifically target plant pathogens. A review article highlights the latest advancements in microfluidic biosensors for nucleic acid and protein detection, underscoring their potential for PoC diagnostics [63]. For instance, Zhang *et al.* developed a portable microfluidic biosensor for the rapid detection of *Xanthomonas oryzae pathovars oryzae* and *oryzicola*, which cause bacterial blight in rice. This biosensor employs loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) technology to amplify pathogen-specific DNA sequences, enabling efficient, on-site detection [135]. Another example, developed by Kühnemund *et al.* consists of a digital droplet microfluidic device where the DNA is bound to magnetic particles and moved through different droplets, which correspond to different steps of Rolling Circle Amplification (RCA) to detect *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [136].

Figure 1.8. (A) Schematics of the bead-based multiplexed microfluidic device to detect mycotoxin with an internal reference for immunodetection of OTA, AFB1 and DON, accompanied with schematics of the competitive fluorescence immunoassay [129], (B) Schematics of the microfluidic device to detect ABA [25], (C) Schematics of the microfluidic device to monitor Aza, composed by a sample pre-treatment column, and coupled with integrated thin film silicon photosensors [134].

Although several biosensors have been developed for phytohormone detection, few of them tackle sample preparation. However, biological assays often require effective sample treatment to address the presence of complex matrices that can interfere with the quantitative analysis of the analytes of interest. The treatment process must balance thorough sample cleaning with the preservation of critical analytes necessary for detection. Isolation or “clean-up” steps—such as extraction, filtration, centrifugation, dilution, and target amplification—are tailored to the specific analyte and analytical technique employed. The choice of sample treatment method varies based on the application setting. In clinical environments, off-chip preparation is feasible due to the availability of specialized equipment. Conversely, in field applications where laboratory tools

are unavailable, on-chip or simple, equipment-free sample preparation becomes essential. Many sample treatment methods published in the literature rely on equipment, such as centrifuges or liquid nitrogen, which are impractical for farmers and unsuitable for field use [30][137]. Consequently, the development of simplified, field-friendly sample treatment protocols is vital to enhance the practical applicability of biological assays [138].

To increase the sensitivity of analyte detection methods, in samples where the analyte of interest is found in low concentrations, pre-concentration of the sample before analysis is a good hypothesis, thus indirectly producing higher limits of detection [138].

1.5. Objectives

The work that I am developing in my Ph.D. thesis focuses on the development of an innovative point-of-use miniaturized analytical device for stand-alone, fast, on-the-field control of strawberry infections and monitoring of grapevine hydric stress, based on an easy-to-use microfluidic biochip. A combination of microfluidics, antibodies, and aptamers, as well as, the development of a sample treatment protocol, will be used for the detection of stress analytes in grapevines and strawberries.

The main objective of this thesis can be outlined as follows:

1) **Individual assay development**

- 1.1) Microfluidic ABA detection. A microfluidic competitive immunoassay will be developed and optimized for the detection of ABA. Protein A microbeads will be used as a solid support to immobilize the anti-ABA antibody, with the assay taking place under continuous flow conditions. The system will be designed to ensure that the interaction between the target ABA, labelled ABA-BSA conjugate, and the antibody is competitive, allowing for accurate detection. The assay will be monitored using microscope-based fluorescence;
- 1.2) Microfluidic SA detection. An aptamer-based assay will be developed and optimized for the detection of SA. Streptavidin microbeads will be used as solid support to immobilize the biotinylated SA aptamer, with the assay taking place under continuous flow conditions. The interaction between the analyte and the aptamer induces a structural shift in the aptamer, enhancing labelled DNA binding. The assay will be monitored using microscope-based fluorescence;

- 2) **Individual sample treatment module** - To detect phytohormones in real samples, a sample treatment protocol will be developed, consisting of grape or strawberry sample preparation using a 5% MeOH-PBS solution for biomarker extraction, followed by centrifugation, filtration, and purification through microfluidic channels packed with Q-Sepharose beads. To address the limitations of centrifugation and filtration for field testing, the protocol will be optimized by eliminating these steps, resulting in a field-friendly process that does not require specialized equipment or personnel;
- 3) **Validation** - The developed microfluidic platforms will be used to analyse real samples from grapes at the *veraison* stage and strawberries infected with *Botrytis cinerea*;

- 4) **Individual microfabricated photosensor module** – A thin-film silicon photodiode previously manufactured in our group will be used for signal read-out generated by the fluorescence signal in the assays;
- 5) **Individual capillary chip module** – A capillary microfluidic device will be utilized together with the developed assay, offering an autonomous platform that operates without the need for an external pump;
- 6) **System integration** - The individual modules, optimized in 1) ABA/SA detection with microscope signal acquisition, will be integrated into an operational microfluidic platform, which will include sample preparation (2), signal transduction (4), and capillary technology (5).

1.6. Thesis Outline

This thesis is structured into three main sections, comprising a total of seven chapters. Part I, consisting of Chapter 1, provides a comprehensive theoretical background, including a discussion on phytohormones, and introduces the concepts of microfluidics. Part II, which includes Chapters 2 to 6, presents the experimental methods, results, and discussions of the research, and is strongly based on works published in international journals. Part III contains Chapter 7, which concludes the thesis by summarizing the findings and offering final remarks on the potential future applications of microfluidic biosensors in sustainable agriculture. This section highlights how these technologies can improve crop resilience, enhance productivity, and address the challenges posed by climate change. A brief description of each chapter is provided below. Each chapter within Part II includes an overall summary, reference(s) to the publication(s) where the presented results were published, and the personal contribution to that chapter.

The present chapter, Chapter 1, serves as a comprehensive foundation for the thesis, encompassing a wide range of topics. It begins with an overview of different phytohormones, detailing their functions and roles in plant physiology, particularly about growth, development, and stress responses. The chapter also delves into plant anatomy, highlighting the structural features relevant to phytohormone studies. Building on this, Chapter 1 introduces the foundational concepts of microfluidics and biosensors, emphasizing their importance in the real-time monitoring of phytohormones. It explains the principles of microfluidic systems, microfabrication techniques, and the various types of biosensors and transducers. To provide context and practical insights, the chapter concludes with examples from the literature, showcasing PoC applications of biosensors in microfluidic systems for plant monitoring and precision agriculture.

Chapter 2 introduces a microfluidic platform designed for the highly sensitive detection of AK, a biomarker indicative of cell damage. This system leverages microbeads and an optical sensor to detect AK released from as few as 10–100 human colorectal adenocarcinoma (HCT116) cells, highlighting its potential for real-time biomarker analysis in miniaturized settings. This work not only demonstrates the feasibility of bead-based assays in microfluidics but also contributes to the optimization strategies necessary for their effective deployment. Early in my thesis, I also developed a microfluidic chip for detecting cell death in the context of drug screening for cancer therapy. This initial project served as a valuable introduction to microfluidic handling and immunoassay development. Moreover, it enabled me to apply microfluidics across two distinct domains: creating a robust platform for laboratory analysis and designing a portable version for field use.

Chapter 3 discusses a microfluidic biochip developed for detecting ABA in grapes, a biomarker relevant to fruit ripening and drought stress in viticulture. The device uses a competitive immunoassay combined with an antibody-based biosensor and optical detection. A novel sample pre-treatment protocol was developed and validated with HPLC. It successfully detects ABA with a LOD from 10^{-6} to 10^{-3} mg/mL. This optimized test lays the groundwork for later applications, which will be explored in the next two chapters.

Chapter 4 presents a point-of-care testing (PoCT) platform based on microfluidic technology for detecting molecular biomarkers. It incorporates a miniaturized microfluidic component for immunoassays and an optical biosensor (fluorescence) system using a hydrogenated amorphous silicon (a-Si: H) p-i-n photodiode, which converts fluorescence into electrical signals. The platform achieved a detection limit of 0.36 nM for the Alexa430 fluorophore. It successfully replicated lab-based immunoassay results and was used to detect ABA in grapes, showing a clear distinction between green grapes (low ABA) and mature grapes (high ABA). This demonstrates its potential for real-time agricultural monitoring.

Chapter 5 introduces a reusable capillary-driven microfluidic platform designed for the PoC detection of ABA. The system utilizes PDMS-PEG copolymer to address hydrophobicity issues of traditional PDMS, enabling passive, capillary-driven fluid transport without external pumps. This portable and cost-effective platform simplifies field analysis with a streamlined sample preparation method for grapes, detecting ABA at concentrations with a LOD ranging from 10^{-6} to 10^{-4} mg/mL.

Chapter 6 presents a portable microfluidic assay for rapid SA detection, a key plant defence hormone. The assay employs an aptamer-based fluorescence sensor with optical detection, enabling real-time, highly sensitive analysis directly in plant samples. A sample pre-treatment protocol was developed and validated with HPLC. The assay successfully detects SA at relevant concentrations for early infection identification, offering a cost-effective, field-deployable tool for improved crop management and food security, with a LOD from 10^{-9} to 10^{-6} mg/mL.

Finally, the conclusions in Chapter 7 summarize the achievements of the thesis alongside suggestions for future developments.

PART II

Chapter 2

Microfluidic Detection of Adenylate Kinase as a Cell Damage Biomarker

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Highlights

In vitro cell cultures are used as models for drug discovery. The detection of cell damage biomarkers such as adenylate kinase (AK) is often used in drug screening and cell biology experiments. A microfluidic platform for AK detection was developed with the capability of detecting the AK resulting from the lysis of 10–100 human colorectal adenocarcinoma HCT116 cells. For this assay, AK was captured on the surface of microbeads integrated into a microfluidic device and optically detected using a fluorescently labelled anti-AK antibody. Microfluidic technologies have in addition been used to develop two- and three-dimensional cell culture models that have the potential to accelerate drug discovery. The microfluidic platform was used to detect the AK resulting from the lysis of HCT116 cells cultivated in a microfluidic biochip, demonstrating the potential for the integration of the miniaturised biosensor with the cell chip.

Publication

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Personal contributions

Designed, and microfabricated the microfluidic structures. Development of the direct immunoassay. Co-performed the cell culture in the microfluidic cell culture chamber and the study of the drug effect on the cells. Analysed all the data acquired. Main writer of the publication.

2.1. Introduction

Cancer is the second leading cause of death in the world, and therapy resistance is one of the main factors limiting patient outcomes [140]. In cancer, as well as in other diseases, the discovery of new drug candidates is of vital importance to improve treatment outcomes and reduce mortality rates [141][142]. Two-dimensional (2D) or three-dimensional (3D) cell cultures are used as experimental models for drug discovery [143][144][145][146]. The detection of AK, a protein present in all cells that is responsible for the high-energy phosphoryl transfer reaction, is often used as a cell damage reporter in drug screening [147][148]. AK is released into the extracellular medium when the cell membrane is damaged, which is taken as an indication of the efficiency of the therapy. The activity of the AK released by damaged cells is usually performed in a two-step assay. In the first reaction, AK converts ADP to ATP. In a second reaction, luciferase catalyses the formation of light from ATP and luciferin; the light is then measured using a luminometer. This assay can be time-consuming and requires significant cell volumes (25 μ L) and laboratory equipment [149]. In this work, we present a microfluidic biosensing module for the detection of AK based on a direct immunoassay, which was used to detect AK in the supernatant after the lysis of human colorectal adenocarcinoma HCT116 cells.

A recent tendency has been to miniaturise the platforms for cell culture using microfluidic technologies to create cell chips [150]. Cell chips are miniaturised devices in which cells grow in an environment that can be easily manipulated and treated in a controlled and reproducible way at length scales comparable to the cell dimensions [141][151][152][153]. Cell chips have been used to clarify disease mechanisms, in pharmaceutical screening, and in the monitoring of different aspects of cell biology, such as dispersion, migration, and signalling mechanisms [154]. One of the most important potential advantages of cell chips is the possibility of integrating miniaturised sensors for the real-time and space-resolved monitoring of the cell culture in the chip [151]. This can be accomplished through microfluidic chip instrumentation, including, for example, impedance sensors for cell attachment and biomass monitoring, pH sensors to track pH changes caused by cellular metabolism, oxygen optical sensors, or by including a bio-sensor module [155]. In this chapter, the detection of AK was demonstrated for monitoring the effect of cell damage exposure to the chemotherapeutic agent 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) in a cell chip.

2.2. Materials and Methods

2.2.1. Reagents

PPA HyperCel, HEA HyperCel, and MEP HyperCel were obtained from Pall Corporation (Port Washington, NY, USA). CM Sepharose, Capto MMC, NHS Sepharose, Heparin Sepharose, Capto MMC Imp Res, and SP Sepharose were obtained from Cytiva (Uppsala, Sweden). Phosphate buffer solution (PBS) 10 \times , adenylate kinase antibody (1 mg/mL), Accutase, RIPA buffer, aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES), Dye BODIPY FL[®], and Alexa Fluor[®] (A430) NHS ester (succinimidyl ester) were obtained from Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA). AK (42.2 μ M), BSA, and polyethylene glycol (PEG) 8000 were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). The complete cell culture growth medium for HCT116 cells comprised DMEM (modified) medium supplemented with 100 U/mL penicillin and 100 μ g/mL streptomycin obtained from Gibco[™] (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA), and 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) obtained from the Biowest (Riverside, MO, USA). Clinical-grade 5-FU (50 mg/mL) was kindly provided by Hospital São Francisco Xavier (Lisbon, Portugal).

2.2.2. Fabrication of the Biomarker Detection Chamber

The microfluidic devices for AK detection were fabricated with two different heights: (1) 100 μ m used for bead packing and (2) 20 μ m for the sample and reactant injection and bead trapping (devices in Figure 2.1A, B). In Figure 2.1A, the solutions flowed through the same inlet used for bead packing. The microfabrication process used two masks, each for a different height.

Figure 2.1. The microfluidic structures, packed with beads, for screening studies (A) and detection of AK in assays (B).

The fabrication of the photomasks and master mould for the structures in Figure 2.1A and Figure 2.1B can be found in Pinto *et al.* [74] and Brás *et al.* [156], respectively. The PDMS was

prepared at a ratio of 1:10 with its curing agent (Sylgard 184 silicon elastomer kit, Dow-Corning) poured on top of the mould, and baked for 90 min. The PDMS was then peeled from the mould, and the inlets and outlets were punched with an 18-gauge syringe; then, the PDMS structure was sealed against a 500 μm PDMS membrane prepared under the same curing conditions. Both PDMS surfaces were subjected to an oxygen plasma (Harrick Plasma, Ithaca, NY, USA) to seal the device. The sealed structures were stored for at least 24 h before being used to stabilise their hydrophobicity.

2.2.3. Fabrication of the Microfluidic Cell Culture Chamber

The microfluidic cell culture chamber used in Section 2.3 has a height of 20 μm and an area of 1 cm^2 , with structural posts to avoid the collapse of the channel (Figure 2.2). The procedure for fabrication is described in Condalipes *et al* [157]. For the microfabrication process, one mask level was used for a 20 μm high structure. The aluminium photomask was designed using CAD software (Auto-CAD 2022) and was fabricated in-house using direct-write photolithography (Heidelberg DWLII, Heidelberg Instruments Mikrotechnik, Mittelgewannweg, Heidelberg, Germany). A 200 nm Al layer was deposited on a clean glass (Corning Eagle) substrate via magnetron sputtering (Nordiko 7000). A 1.5 μm thick layer of positive photoresist (PFR 7790G) was spin-coated on the deposited Al layer, and the pattern was transferred to the photoresist with a direct-write laser photolithography system (Heidelberg Instruments, DWLii). After exposure, the substrate was developed (TMA 238 WA, JSA Micro), and the Al was wet-etched using a commercial Al etchant (TechniEtch Al80 aluminium etchant, Microchemicals, Ulm, DE, Germany). The mask was used to fabricate a mould by exposing a SU-8 negative photoresist. The mould was fabricated by first spin-coating a 20 μm thick layer of SU-8 2015 (Microchem) onto a silicon substrate, which was previously cleaned. The SU-8 was then exposed to UV light through the Al mask, followed by post-exposure baking and development in propylene glycol methyl ether acetate (PGMEA, Sigma-Aldrich). Then, the mould underwent a final hard-baking step at 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 min. The finished SU-8 mould was then used for the fabrication of the PDMS microfluidic cell culture chamber.

Figure 2.2. Microfluidic chamber for cell culture.

The PDMS microfluidic cell culture chamber was sealed against a polystyrene Petri dish. To promote sealing, the Petri dish was subjected to an oxygen plasma treatment for 5 min at 30 W. The surface of the Petri dish was functionalised with silane using APTES solution according to a process described in Condalpes *et al* [157]. After this incubation time, the Petri dish was washed with DI water and dried with compressed air. The PDMS microfluidic structure received an oxygen plasma treatment for 5 min at 30 W. Finally, both the silanised Petri dish and PDMS oxidised surfaces were pressed against each other for a few seconds, generating a covalently bonded device.

2.2.4. Packing of the Biomarker Detection Chamber

Commercially available microbeads were prepared in an ethanol solution 20% (v/v) comprising PPA HyperCel, HEA HyperCel, MEP HyperCel, CM Sepharose, Capto MMC, NHS Sepharose, Heparin Sepharose, Capto MMC Imp Res, and SP Sepharose. In all cases, the bead suspension was homogenised and transferred into a PEG 8000 20% (w/w) solution in a proportion of 1:10. PEG was used to avoid clogging the channel with bead aggregates and to achieve uniform packing. To pack the microfluidic structure, a negative pressure was applied at the outlet using a syringe pump (NE-4000, New Era Pumps, Farmingdale, NY, USA). A pipette tip containing the bead suspension was previously inserted into the inlet. The negative pressure produced a flow rate of approximately 7 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ into the channel, resulting in the packing of the beads inside the detection chamber. Subsequently, the microfluidic structures were washed at 17 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ using PBS 1 \times .

2.2.5. AK Labelling

To prepare fluorescently labelled AK, 50 μL of the commercial protein was diluted in 400 μL of 0.1 M sodium bicarbonate buffer and then conjugated with 10 μL of the amine-reactive dye BODIPY FL[®] NHS ester (succinimidyl ester) previously dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) at 10 mg/mL. This mixture was incubated in the dark for 1 h at room temperature. The excess dye was washed using a 10 kDa Amicon tube (Merck, Alameda Fernão Lopes, Algés, Portugal). This

was carried out by using 500 μL of PBS at a time and centrifuging at $14,000 \times g$ for 10 min until the permeate was not fluorescent [158][159].

To prepare the fluorescently labelled anti-AK antibody, the process was the same as the one described above, but with the dye Alexa Fluor[®] (A430) NHS ester (succinimidyl ester).

The excitation and emission wavelengths for BODIPY FL[®] NHS ester (succinimidyl ester) and Alexa Fluor[®] (A430) NHS ester (succinimidyl ester) are 502/ 510 nm and 430/545 nm, respectively.

2.2.6. Preparation of Lysed HCT116 Cell Supernatant

For the AK detection in cell lysate solutions, described in Section 2.3.2, the HCT116 (ECACC 91091005) cells were cultivated in a T-flask in a complete cell culture growth medium at 37 °C, with 5% CO₂ in a saturated atmosphere [160]. The medium and cells (at 1.6×10^6 cells/mL) were collected, and RIPA lysis buffer was added according to the manufacturer's specifications [161]. The resultant mixture was left to incubate on ice for 30 min. Afterwards, the mixture was centrifuged at $14,600 \times g$ for 30 min at 4 °C, and 7 mL of supernatant was recovered. Successive dilutions were made from the supernatant obtained after lysis. HCT116 was the cell line used in this study because it is susceptible to 5-FU.

2.2.7. Image Acquisition and Processing

Fluorescence measurements were performed using a fluorescence microscope (Leica DMLM) equipped with a digital camera (DFC300FX) and a 100 W short arc mercury lamp as an excitation light source, coupled to an I3 filter cube with a band-pass for the excitation of 450–490 nm (blue) and a long-pass for emission at 515 nm (green). For the quantification of AK, the fluorescence signal from the beads inside the microcolumns was acquired with an exposure time of 2 s, and $1 \times$ gain. The obtained micrographs were analysed using ImageJ software from the National Institutes of Health, USA [162]. The images were split into red, green, and blue channels, and only the green channel was analysed by creating a region of interest inside the microfluidic channel (signal) and an equal region outside of the microfluidic channel (background) that was subtracted from the signal value.

2.2.8. Direct Immunoassay for AK Detection

2.2.8.1. Microbead Screening Study

The microbead screening study for AK capture was performed in the microfluidic column in Figure 2.1A [74]. The microcolumn was packed with the microbeads as described in Section

2.2.4. Then, a solution of AK labelled with 1 mg/mL BODIPY FL[®] was injected at a flow rate of 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 10 min. The microfluidic structure was washed with PBS 1x using 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, and fluorescence was measured.

2.2.8.2. Optimisation

The structure in Figure 2.1B was used to perform the optimisation of AK detection. The microcolumn was packed with NHS Sepharose beads ($\sim 90\ \mu\text{m}$), as described in Section 2.2.4. Then, a solution of commercial AK was injected, followed by the addition of a blocking agent (BSA 1%, BSA 4%, or complete cell culture growth medium), both using a flow rate of 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 10 min. Finally, an anti-AK antibody labelled with Alexa Fluor[®] (A430) was injected with a flow rate of 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 5 min. The microfluidic structure was washed with PBS 1x using a 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ flow rate for 10 min, and fluorescence was measured.

2.2.8.2.1. Anti-AK Antibody Concentration

As described in Section 2.2.8.2, different concentrations of labelled anti-AK antibodies (5×10^{-2} , 1×10^{-1} , 5×10^{-1} , 1, and 5 mg/mL) were tested against a fixed concentration of 42.2 μM commercial AK. BSA 4% was used as a blocking agent.

2.2.8.2.2. Blocking Agent

As described in Section 2.2.8.2, different blocking agents, BSA 1%, BSA 4%, and complete cell culture growth medium were tested in the absence of commercial AK and with 1 mg/mL anti-AK antibody labelled with Alexa Fluor[®] (A430).

2.2.8.3. AK Detection Calibration Curve Using the Optimised Anti-AK Antibody Concentration and Blocking Agent

A calibration curve was plotted with AK concentrations ranging from 1×10^{-1} to 42.2 μM . The microfluidic structure in Figure 2.1B was used to detect and quantify the AK concentration. After the NHS Sepharose bead packing step, described in Section 2.2.4, a flow of AK solution at a given concentration and a flow rate of 0.2 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ was maintained for 10 min. The complete cell culture growth medium was used as a blocking agent and flowed at 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 10 min. FBS is very rich in proteins, such as BSA, which is an excellent blocking agent in immunoassays. Subsequently, 1 mg/mL anti-AK antibody labelled with Alexa Fluor[®] (A430) was injected at a flow rate of 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 5 min. The microfluidic structure was washed with PBS 1x using 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 10 min. All these solutions were pumped using a negative pressure at the outlet. The fluorescence was measured.

The fluorescence signals obtained were plotted as a function of the different measured AK concentrations. Then, a linear regression was measured, using five concentration points: 2.5, 4.2, 12.7, 25.3, and 42.2 μM , as shown in Section 2.3.2.

2.2.8.4. Measurement of AK in the Cell Culture Supernatant

The microcolumn in Figure 2.1B was packed with NHS Sepharose beads, as described in Section 2.2.4, followed by the insertion of lysed supernatant (as described in Section 2.2.6) for 10 min at a flow rate of 0.2 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. Different dilutions of 1.6×10^6 cells/mL were tested. A volume of 5 μL of 1 mg/mL anti-AK antibody labelled with Alexa Fluor[®] (A430) was then flowed for 5 min at a flow rate of 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, followed by a wash step with PBS 1x for 10 min with a flow rate of 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. All these assay steps were pumped using negative pressure at the outlet. These assays were performed without a blocking step, as described before in other sections, because the samples collected were surrounded in the complete cell culture growth medium.

2.2.9. Cell Culture in the Microfluidic Cell Culture Chamber

The microfluidic cell culture chamber (Figure 2.2) was sterilised (for 20 min in UV light), coated with collagen type I, and washed with the complete cell culture growth medium, and HCT116 cells were injected into the chip following the processes described in Condelpes *et al* [157]. The chip was placed into an incubator (37 °C, 5% CO₂) for 5 h to allow cell attachment to the collagen-coated chip surface. After seeding, the medium was set to flow at 0.2 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, and the chips were placed inside an incubator during the full cell culture period of the experiments.

2.2.9.1. Cell Growth + RIPA Lysis in the Microfluidic Cell Culture Chamber

After 61 h of cell growth as described in Section 2.2.9, cell lysis was induced. Two different lysis procedures were performed: (1) RIPA lysis buffer was set to flow inside the chip where cells were cultured, and (2) the cells were first removed from the chip and then lysed off-chip using the RIPA buffer. Additionally, a control assay was performed in which no RIPA buffer lysis was used.

When cell lysis was performed inside the microfluidic channel, the RIPA buffer solution was set to flow for 15 min at 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. The solution collected at the outlet was centrifuged at $14,600 \times g$ for 30 min at 4 °C (according to the manufacturer's instructions) to remove cells and cell debris from the solution, which could interfere with the AK detection process [163]. When cell lysis was performed off-chip, cells were first detached using an accutase solution, which flowed in the chip for 20 min at 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ at 37 °C, with 5% CO₂. The cells were collected periodically

at the chip outlet. According to the approximate number of cells inside the chip, the appropriate quantity of RIPA buffer was added, and the lysis protocol described in Section 2.2.6 was carried out (Figure S2.1A).

2.2.9.2. Cell Growth + 5-FU + RIPA Lysis in the Microfluidic Cell Chamber

For the study of the drug effect, cells were grown in the chip for 24 h, as described in Section 2.2.9. After that time, 5-FU was injected for 72 h at 0.2 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. Different drug concentrations were tested: 0 μM , 50 μM , and 1000 μM in a complete cell culture growth medium. During the treatment time, samples were collected periodically at the chip outlet. Whenever a sample was collected at a given time point, a new microcentrifuge tube was used for the collection at the outlet.

After 72 h of cell growth, the RIPA buffer solution was injected for 15 min at 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. The solution collected at the outlet was subjected to centrifugation at $14,600 \times g$ for 30 min at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ - according to the manufacturer's instructions (Figure S2.1B).

In both cases, RIPA lysis and 5-FU exposure in the microfluidic cell chamber, measurements of AK were performed as described in Section 2.2.8.4.

2.3. Results and Discussion

2.3.1. Screening of Microbeads for AK Capture: Optimisation of Anti-AK Antibody Concentration and Blocking Agent

The main goal of this work was to develop a microfluidic direct immunoassay capable of detecting a cell damage biomarker. This detection can be performed off-chip after cell treatments or coupled with a cell chip in which cells were exposed to a lysis agent or a drug. Here, AK was used as the biomarker of cell damage since it is commonly used in compound screening. The AK direct immunoassay detection is based on capturing the biomarker in microbeads mechanically trapped in a microfluidic channel, followed by the optical detection of AK using a labelled anti-AK antibody. This strategy is schematically summarised in Figure 2.3. The specific signal is directly proportional to the concentration of AK in the sample and can be used to determine the number of AK molecules that are released upon cell damage.

Figure 2.3. Schematic of the immunoassay for AK detection using microbeads. AK primary amines form covalent bonds with the NHS groups.

To achieve this goal, a novel microfluidic-compatible strategy for AK detection was developed based on microbeads typically used in chromatographic processes. The use of microbeads trapped in the microfluidic structure increases the surface area, hence the sensitivity of detection, and decreases the diffusion length, and therefore the duration of the assay. Thus, the first step in assay development was to determine which beads were optimal to capture the AK target. The microcolumn used for these screening assays is schematically shown in Figure 2.1A. A screening study with different microbeads was performed to select the microbeads that were the most efficient in the capture of the target AK molecule.

PPA HyperCel and HEA HyperCel bind target molecules mainly via hydrophobic interactions, while MEP HyperCel and Heparin Sepharose has a binding mechanism that includes a mild hydrophobic effect, together with electrostatic, and NHS Sepharose bind via covalent interactions. CM Sepharose, Cpto MMC, and Cpto MMC ImpRes beads are weak cation exchangers, whereas SP Sepharose is a strong cation exchanger. Only cation exchanger beads were tested because the AK protein at pH 7 is positively charged (the isoelectric point is approximately 9 [164]). From this screening assay, in which fluorescently labelled AK first flowed, followed by a PBS 1x wash, as shown in Figure 2.4A, B, it was concluded that the NHS Sepharose beads exhibited higher fluorescence after a longer washing step, and thus these beads were selected for further assay development. NHS Sepharose beads form covalent, chemically stable amide bonds with the primary amines present in AK, and the spacer arm between the NHS group and the agarose beads allowed highly efficient binding by minimising steric hindrance (Figure 2.3).

Figure 2.4. Microbead screening study: (A) test of different microbeads to determine the optimal microbead to capture AK. A solution of $[AK_{BODIPY FL}] = 1 \text{ mg/mL}$ was set to flow through the beads for 10 min and a washing step with PBS 1 \times was performed for 5 min ($n=1$); (B) capture and longer washing curves obtained by continuously measuring the fluorescence intensity of the packed NHS Sepharose, HEA Hypercel, and PPA Hypercel beads ($n=1$). The images refer to NHS Sepharose. The excitation wavelength was 450–490 nm (blue).

Having selected the NHS Sepharose beads to capture the AK, the next step in assay development was to determine the concentration of anti-AK antibody necessary to reach a saturation signal at the relatively large AK concentration of 42.2 μM . This saturation means that essentially all AK target molecules were involved in the detection of the anti-AK antibody. As it is possible to observe in Figure 2.5A, increasing the antibody concentration beyond 1 mg/mL did not change the signal, so this anti-AK antibody concentration was selected for further assays.

The complete cell culture growth medium was selected as the blocking agent, because it presented lower fluorescence intensity values in negative control assays, indicating the absence of non-specific interactions (Figure S2.2). The negative control experiment consisted of the assay described in Section 2.2.8.2 but without flowing the AK target in the microfluidic channel. Here, we tested three different blocking agents (BSA 1%, BSA 4%, and the complete cell culture growth medium) to see which one would be the best. The assay without blocking would lead to the binding of the labelled anti-AK antibody to the microfluidic channel walls or microbeads. In this way, with the presence of the blocking agent in the assay, the labelled anti-AK antibody would only covalently bind to the AK target. Thus, the verified fluorescence signal would always be due to the presence of the AK target and not for any other reason. In addition, we also ruled out the possibility of binding the labelled anti-AK antibody to the components of the complete cell culture growth medium, due to the low fluorescence values obtained in the negative control.

Figure 2.5. Immunoassay for AK detection: (A) optimisation of the labelled anti-AK antibody concentration for a fixed AK concentration (42.2 μM). Capture and wash steps were performed at 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ and 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, respectively; (B) fluorescence response curve for different target synthetic AK concentrations, ranging from 1×10^{-1} to 42.2 μM , using the optimised assay conditions, and linear regression ($y = 1135.69 \ln(x) + 546.70$). The control corresponds to the assay without target AK, establishing the baseline for non-specific interactions and residual capture of detection antibodies ($n = 3$). The excitation wavelength was 450–490 nm (blue).

2.3.2. AK Detection Sensitivity in Buffer and Lysed Cell Solution

After determining the optimal anti-AK antibody concentration (Figure 2.5A), a curve was plotted for the fluorescence signal as a function of AK concentrations in PBS 1x (with the anti-AK antibody fixed as the optimised concentration), which is shown in Figure 2.5B. The results show that it is possible to detect molecules of AK down to a concentration of approximately 1×10^{-6} M.

This response curve was obtained using the microfluidic structure schematically shown in Figure 2.1B. This structure was less susceptible than that shown in Figure 2.1A to the development of air bubbles and disturbance to the microbead packaging integrity, which may lead to irregular flow rates, increased noise in the measurements, and decreased assay reproducibility.

Having established the sensitivity of the AK detection assay in model conditions (AK in PBS 1x), the next step was to demonstrate that the AK resulting from cell lysis could be detected. For this purpose, the successive dilutions of a solution with 1.6×10^6 lysed HCT116 cells were used to determine the lower concentration limit of lysed cells detectable using the microfluidic AK

detection immunoassay. The original cell solution was subjected to chemical lysis using the RIPA buffer, a reagent used for mammalian cell lysis and protein solubilisation. Figure 2.6 shows that it is possible to detect the AK resulting from the lysis of approximately 10–100 HCT116 cells with reaction volumes of 2 μL . The Toxilight™ Bioassay reagent method used on a macroscale is faster in terms of detection because the readable signal is detectable 5 min after the addition of the Toxilight™ Bioassay reagent. However, for this measurement, 25 μL of cell volume is required, and to reach this volume, it takes about 2 h (using a flow rate of 0.2 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$). Using the method developed in this article, the detection time was approximately 20 min; however, the cell volume required was much smaller (2 μL), so the sample collection time was only 10 min. In this way, it can be inferred that the method using microfluidics surpasses the macroscale method, in addition to the fact that the sensitivity is greater since at the macroscale, it is only possible to detect 10 HCT116 lysed cells per well (25 μL), while at the microscale, it is possible to detect 10–100 HCT116 lysed cells in 2 μL [149]. It is important to note that for cell lysis to occur, it was necessary to add the RIPA buffer solution since centrifugation alone did not cause significant cell damage (results shown in blue in Figure 2.6).

Figure 2.6. Cell lysis is monitored through AK detection in a microfluidic chip. AK detection immunoassay was performed in solutions obtained by sequentially diluting a stock lysate solution with a concentration of 1.6×10^6 cells/mL (pink squares) and in a solution of cells subjected only to centrifugation (blue) ($n = 1$). The control results from non-specific interactions and the residual capture of free detection antibodies when only the complete cell culture growth medium flowed through the channel (in the absence of cells) ($n = 3$). The excitation wavelength was 450–490 nm (blue).

Using Figures 2.5B and 2.6, it is possible to estimate the number of AK molecules detected per lysed cell. Although the matrices are different (the calibration curve of Figure 2.5B was

plotted for the experiment using PBS 1x), it was found in separate experiments that the presence of RIPA buffer does not interfere with the AK detection assay. An estimate of approximately 3.1×10^5 AK molecules per cell was obtained, assuming a cell volume of approximately 3×10^{-6} μL [165].

2.3.3. Monitoring Cell Damage in a Microfluidic Cell Chip

The AK detection assay was used to monitor cell lysis in a cell chip. HCT116 cells were inserted, incubated, and grown in a cell chip. In one experiment, after 61 h of cell growth, chemical lysis with RIPA buffer was performed following two different approaches: (1) in the chip and (2) off-chip lysis. The increase in the fluorescence signal after RIPA buffer treatment demonstrates that cell damage monitoring in the cell bio-chip is possible using the AK microfluidic detection assay (Figure 2.7A). From the fluorescence value obtained and using the established calibration curve, it was possible to estimate that the number of cells present on the chip and subsequently lysed was approximately 2×10^4 . It was also possible to observe a slight increase in fluorescence at 61 h of cell growth before chemical lysis (Figure 2.7A), which could be due to the occurrence of natural cell damage in the chip.

A second AK detection experiment was performed by inserting different 5-FU concentrations into the biochip during cell growth. Notably, 5-FU is one of the most commonly used drugs in cancer treatment, often in combination with other anticancer drugs. Additionally, 5-FU is an antimetabolite that targets replicating cells by overwhelming DNA repair mechanisms, eventually leading to cell death [166]. After 24 h of cell insertion, incubation, and growth, 5-FU was added to the complete cell culture growth medium. Figure 2.7B shows that, after 48 h, for the highest 5-FU concentration (1000 μM), it was possible to observe the initial signs of cell damage in the biochip from the AK signal collected. At the end of the assay, the RIPA buffer was allowed to flow into the biochip to verify the amount of AK that was released. In the chip with the highest concentration of 5-FU, a smaller amount of target AK was observed when cell lysis was performed using the RIPA buffer at the end of the experiment, as expected (Figures 2.7B and 2.8). In this way, it was possible to conclude that the lower the 5-FU concentration flowed on the chip, the greater the amount of the target AK released at the end of the experiment following lysis. This is due to the greater number of viable cells on the chip, without a compromised cell membrane at lower 5-FU concentrations.

Figure 2.7. Detection of AK resulting from cell damage in cell chips. Two different procedures were performed: **(A)** cell growth for 61 h with complete cell culture growth medium perfusion, followed by lysis inside or outside the microfluidic channel, performed with RIPA buffer. Intermediate measurements of AK before lysis were taken during this period ($n = 1$); **(B)** cell growth for 24 h with complete cell culture growth media perfusion, followed by the continuous 5-FU injection at different concentrations during 72 h. Intermediate measurements of AK were taken during this period. At the end of this period, lysis was performed by flowing RIPA buffer inside the microfluidic channel ($n = 2$). In both cases, the control and RIPA buffer refer to the non-specific background fluorescence value when only the complete cell culture growth medium or RIPA buffer flowed through the channel (in the absence of cells) ($n = 3$). The excitation wavelength was 450–490 nm (blue).

Figure 2.8. Micrograph of a subsection over time of injection of a specific drug concentration, 0 μM and 1000 μM.

The standard assays for AK measurement rely on two chemical reactions. Firstly, the AK released by damaged cells converts ADP into ATP. Then, in a bioluminescence method, luciferase catalyses light formation from ATP and luciferin. This signal can be measured using a luminometer and is proportional to AK concentration. Available in commercial kits, these assays are easy to use. However, high volumes of both the reagent buffer and cell culture medium are required for the bioluminescence reaction (25 μL for 384-well plates or 100 μL for 96-well plates). Additionally, the luminescence signal generated cannot be related to the number of cells seeded and always has to be relative to a control condition. Lastly, these approaches are usually endpoint evaluations and do not allow for the continuous monitoring of cell damage.

The methodology presented in this chapter allows the monitoring of AK release over time through cell media collection at the outlet at specific time points without compromising cell incubation. In addition, the reaction volumes used can be as low as 2 μL . Moreover, by using an anti-AK antibody, the signal measured is directly proportional to the amount of AK present in the samples.

2.4. Conclusions

A microfluidic biosensing platform capable of detecting a cell damage biomarker—AK—was proposed and demonstrated. Using a direct immunoassay, in which AK was captured on the surface of microbeads trapped in the microfluidic device and detected using a labelled anti-AK antibody, it was possible to detect AK in the supernatant of human colorectal adenocarcinoma HCT116 cells corresponding to about 10–100 lysed cells. This procedure was also implemented at the outlet of a cell chip. In this case, it was possible to detect the AK resulting from the lysis of the cells cultivated in the chip, and to monitor the effect of the exposure of the cell culture in the chip to 5-FU over time, albeit still with limited sensitivity. The integration of this microfluidic biosensor—and additional biosensors with other capabilities—with the cell chip platform can potentially dramatically improve the speed and quality of drug discovery and disease treatment procedures.

This work not only demonstrates the potential for real-time biomarker analysis in miniaturized systems but also provides valuable insights for optimizing microbead-based assays and integrating microfluidic modules into portable devices for health-related applications. Importantly, the knowledge and technical expertise gained during this phase—particularly in assay development, microfluidic handling, and sensor integration—served as a foundation for extending the platform's use beyond human cell analysis. In the following chapters, this versatility is explored in the context of plant biology, where the system is adapted to detect biomarkers

associated with biotic and abiotic stress. This transition highlights the interdisciplinary potential of microfluidic technologies and their applicability across fields such as precision agriculture and environmental monitoring.

Chapter 3

Competitive Immunoassay in a Microfluidic Biochip for In-Field Detection of Abscisic Acid in Grapes

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Highlights

Viticulture and associated products are an important part of the economy in many countries. However, biotic and abiotic stresses negatively impact the production of grapes and wine. Climate change is in many aspects increasing both these stresses. Routine sample retrievals and analysis tend to be time-consuming and require expensive equipment and skilled personnel to operate. These challenges could be overcome through the development of a miniaturized analytical device for the early detection of grapevine stresses in the field. ABA is involved in several plant processes, including the onset of fruit ripening and tolerance mechanisms against drought stress. This hormone can be detected through a competitive immunoassay and is found in plants in concentrations up to 10^{-1} mg/mL. A microfluidic platform is developed in this work, capable of detecting ABA in buffer at concentrations as low as 10^{-3} to 10^{-6} mg/mL. Grape samples were tested using the microfluidic system alongside benchmark techniques such as HPLC. The microfluidic system could detect an increase to 10^{-5} mg/mL of ABA present in real berry samples at the *veraison* stage of ripening.

Publication

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Personal contributions

Designed, and microfabricated the microfluidic structures. Development of the competitive immunoassay, and the sample treatment protocol, as well as, the validation with a real sample. Co-performed the HPLC measurements. Analysed all the data acquired. Main writer of the publication.

3.1. Introduction

Our planet is facing a climate change crisis, due to factors such as burning fossil fuels, cutting down forests, and farming livestock, leading to an increase in the planet's temperature [1]. This increase in temperature, in addition to the rise of seawater levels resulting from the melting of the polar ice caps, affects biodiversity and causes an increase in the spread of pests and pathogens. In this way, climate change critically threatens the natural ecosystem, causing floods, droughts, and heat stress for plants, where vines are no exception [2]. As stated in the 2019 statistical report from the International Organization of Vine and Wine (OVI), in 2018 there was a world production of 77.8 million tons of grapes, with 57% of these destined for winemaking, 36% for table grapes and 7% for raisins [5]. Vines are susceptible to climate change, as they need a specific set of conditions to be able to fully develop. Thus, it is necessary to prevent biotic stresses (pathogenic infections) and abiotic stresses (e.g., drought, heat, cold, salinity) [168][169][170]. Several phytohormone concentrations are altered under these stresses, such as JA, AzA, and SA for infections, and ABA and IAA for drought stress [43][16][17][171].

In particular, ABA (molar mass: 264.32 g/mol [172]) is a small molecule that regulates several biological processes in plants, such as water use efficiency, tolerance to osmotic stress, and seed germination. ABA is mostly synthesized in the roots in response to drought stress and transported to the leaves, although the leaves are also capable of producing ABA. During a drought period, the ABA produced in the roots is transported to the leaves, where the osmotic potential of the stomatal cells is rapidly altered, causing the stomata to close, reducing transpiration, and preventing water loss from the leaves [33][34]. Thus, when under stress, this phytohormone tends to rise. In addition to this, ABA is also important in the process of development and onset of ripening of grape berries [8]. Its concentration increases during the *veraison* stage when the berries change colour due to anthocyanin accumulation [8]. The concentration of ABA varies depending on the grape variety, so a certain concentration of ABA in one type of grape may be considered normal, while in another it can be considered as a sign of stress [23]. Therefore, it is important to monitor the ABA concentration over time to establish a baseline to use its concentration to monitor the condition of the plant.

That said, with the method developed in this work, it is possible to detect drought stress before starting to see physiological and morphological changes in the grape, such as changes in leaves (withering), or even leaf curling, or lifting of the stem [173][174]. It can also be used for monitoring the dynamics of pre-harvest and post-harvest fruit ripening in association with other markers [8].

In order to have continuously updated information on the state of the plant, it is essential to develop a fast, inexpensive, and easy-to-use device to diagnose biotic and abiotic stresses in the field (point-of-impact) to avoid delayed or unnecessary countermeasures, such as application of irrigation or fungicides. Typically, the biomarkers referred to above are found in concentrations ranging between 10^{-5} to 10^{-1} mg/mL, and the most commonly used detection method is HPLC [25]. HPLC is an analytical technique used to first separate and then detect the components present in a solution. However, this technique is not suitable for field testing due to its bulk and the need for skilled personnel to operate the equipment, relatively long analysis time, and high costs [30][137].

Microfluidics technology may address these limitations through the development of devices that can provide a portable, easy-to-use, and high-throughput solution to in-field testing. Compared to standard immunoassays (e.g., ELISA), assays made with microfluidic devices use smaller quantities of reagents and have faster reaction times due to smaller diffusion lengths [55][56]. These advantages of microfluidic devices meet all the important criteria of an immunoassay used for environmental analyses, clinical diagnoses, and biochemical studies [175]. Early application of microfluidics for hormone detection in grapes was developed by Brás *et al.*, with an enzymatic assay to quantify AzA based on the inhibitory effect of AzA on the activity of the tyrosinase enzyme [134]. However, in this method, the detection of the biomarker is performed indirectly. Due to the complexity of the grape matrix, enzyme activity may be inhibited by a compound other than AzA, resulting in an erroneous result. Antibodies, compared to enzyme-based assays, are more suitable for biomarker detection, given that the target is captured directly and does not depend on any additional reaction that could result in a loss of selectivity. In this work, a novel competitive immunoassay capable of detecting ABA in the buffer in a microfluidic device was developed. This assay was also capable of detecting ABA in real berry samples, making use of a sample pre-treatment protocol also developed in this work. This platform was validated with measurements of ABA in real berry samples at the *veraison* stage that were also performed by HPLC.

3.2. Materials and Methods

3.2.1. Fabrication of the Microfluidic Devices

The microfluidic devices for ABA detection and sample treatment were fabricated with two different heights: (1) a channel with a height of 100 μm was used for bead packing, and (2) a channel with a height of 20 μm for the sample and reactant injection. The shallower channels allow for trapping microbeads with diameters greater than 20 μm . The fabrication of the

microfluidic devices containing immobilized microbeads is described elsewhere and briefly summarized below [139]. These devices were fabricated using a two-mask microfabrication process, each for a different height. A schematic drawing of the microfluidic devices is shown in Figures 3.1A and 3.2A.

The photomasks were designed using CAD software (AutoCAD, Autodesk Inc., Mill Valley, CA/USA) and were fabricated in-house using direct-write photolithography (Heidelberg DWLII, Heidelberg Instruments Mikrotechnik, Germany) after sputtering a 200 nm aluminium layer on a glass substrate using a Nordiko 7000 DC magnetron sputtering system (Nordiko Technical Services LTD, Hampshire, UK). Two different patterned Al masks were fabricated on glass substrates, one for each height of the final channel, to fabricate a two-level mould patterning using SU-8 2015 (Microchem, Newton, MA/USA) for the 20 μm layer and SU-8 50 (Microchem, Newton, MA/USA) for the 100 μm layer. The SU-8 photoresists were exposed to UV light through the respective photomask, followed by a post-exposure bake and development step in PGMEA 99.5% (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO/USA). After patterning the SU-8 features and a final hard bake step at 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, for 15 min, the finished SU-8 mould was used to fabricate the standard process of replication of PDMS structures, using Sylgard 184 silicon elastomer kit (Dow Corning, Midland, MI/USA). The PDMS was mixed at a ratio of 10 parts to 1 part curing agent and poured on top of the mould. The PDMS was subsequently baked for 90 min at 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and then peeled from the mould. Holes were punched with an 18-gauge syringe (Instech Solomon, Plymouth Meeting, PA, USA) through the inlets and outlets of the structure. The devices containing the microfluidic structures were sealed against a 500 μm PDMS membrane, exposing both surfaces to an oxygen plasma (Harrick Plasma, Ithaca, NY/USA). To stabilize their hydrophobicity, the PDMS structures are stored for at least 24 hours before being used [176]. Supplementary information Figure S3.1 shows the sequence of steps involved in the fabrication of the microfluidic devices used for trapping beads

Figure 3.1. Competitive Immunoassay for ABA detection: (A) schematic of the microfluidic structures, packed with protein A microbeads for the detection of ABA; (B) schematic of the competitive fluorescence immunoassay: bead functionalization (the anti-ABA antibody is bound to the bead through the constant zone of the anti-ABA antibody, leaving the binding site available for binding to the target); control, non ABA-spiked assay (only the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate is present in the system, so only this labelled ABA-BSA conjugate will bind to the anti-ABA antibody, resulting in the maximum signal in the absence of competition for the anti-ABA antibody sites); and ABA-spiked assay (both the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate and the free analyte are present in the system, so both will compete for the anti-ABA antibody binding sites: the higher the ABA concentration, the lower the fluorescence); (C) fluorescence response curve for different target ABA concentrations, ranging from 10^{-11} mg/mL to 10^{-1} mg/mL ($n = 4$). The excitation wavelength was 450–490 nm (blue). The error bars represent \pm the standard deviation.

Figure 3.2. Sample treatment protocol and calibration curves for red and white treated table grapes: (A) overview of the steps carried out in the sample treatment: maceration of the sample; centrifugation (2000 rpm, 10 min); filtration (pore diameter: 0.2 μm); and bead cleaning step in a microfluidic channel (the columns used were 1 cm long, with a width of 0.1 cm, and a height of 100 μm, and, additionally, they had a smaller channel with 200 μm of width and a height of 20 μm designed to trap beads with diameters superior to 20 μm); (B) ABA detection competitive immunoassay performed in ABA-spiked and treated table grape samples, with ABA concentrations ranging from 10⁻⁶ at 10⁻² mg/mL (n=2). The excitation wavelength was 450–490 nm (blue). The error bars represent ± the standard deviation.

3.2.2. Competitive Immunoassay for ABA Detection

3.2.2.1. Reagents

Protein A microbeads were obtained from Cytiva (Uppsala, Sweden). PBS 10×, casein (1% w/v), and Alexa Fluor® (A430) NHS ester (succinimidyl ester) were obtained from Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA). Anti-ABA antibody (14.3 mg/mL) was obtained from Agrisera (Vännäs, Sweden). ABA-BSA conjugate (4 mg/mL) was obtained from Creative Diagnostics (Shirley, NY, USA). ABA (50 mg/mL), sodium bicarbonate buffer, DMSO, and methanol (MeOH) anhydrous 99.8% were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA).

3.2.2.2. Functionalization of the Microbeads

The protein-A microbeads (diameter ~ 90 μm) were first incubated with the anti-ABA antibody solution. The incubation was performed by adding 3 μL of bead stock to 19 μL of anti-ABA antibody at 0.2 mg/mL. After 60 min of incubation, 110 μL of PBS was added to homogenise the bead suspension. These 3 μL of the bead stock always have approximately the same number of beads. If there is a different number of beads in different incubations, the anti-ABA antibody concentration on the beads will vary, and therefore, a different number of binding sites will be available, which will be a source of irreproducibility for the assay.

3.2.2.3. Packing the Biomarker Detection Chamber

To insert the beads into the microfluidic structure, a negative pressure was applied at both the outlet and inlet₁ with a syringe pump (NE-4000, New Era Pumps, Farmingdale, NY, USA). The channel was first filled with PBS 1 \times buffer and a pipette tip containing 20 μL of bead solution was inserted in the bead chamber inlet₂ as shown in Figure 3.1A. The negative pressure produced a flow rate of approximately 6 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ in the channel, resulting in the packing of the beads inside the detection chamber. Subsequently, the microfluidic structure was washed at a flow rate of 16 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ with PBS 1 \times , and the bead chamber inlet₂ was sealed using a 20-gauge metal plug. The bead-packed structure was stored in a container filled with deionised water (DI) and refrigerated overnight to remove any air bubbles formed during the microbeads insertion process.

3.2.2.4. ABA-BSA Conjugate Labelling

To prepare fluorescently labelled ABA-BSA conjugate, 20 μL of ABA-BSA conjugate was diluted in 480 μL of 0.1 M sodium bicarbonate buffer and then conjugated with 2 μL of the amine-reactive dye Alexa Fluor[®] (A430) NHS ester (succinimidyl ester) previously dissolved in DMSO at 10 mg/mL. This mixture between ABA-BSA conjugate and Alexa₄₃₀ was incubated in the dark for 60 min at room temperature. To remove the excess non-conjugated dye, a series of washing steps were performed, using a 10 kDa Amicon Ultra-0.5 centrifugal filter unit (Merck, Alameda Fernão Lopes, Algés, Portugal). The incubated solution was added to the Amicon tube, and centrifuged at 14,000 times gravity ($\times g$) for 10 min. After centrifugation was complete, the permeate at the bottom of the tube was discarded, 500 μL of PBS 1 \times was added to initiate the washing process, and the solution was again centrifuged at 14,000 $\times g$ for 10 min. This latter step was performed by repeated cycles until the permeate became transparent. Then, the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate solution was collected by reverse centrifugation at 2000 $\times g$ for 2 min and the remaining volume was measured and made up to the initial volume with PBS 1 \times , to set the concentration.

3.2.2.5. ABA Detection Immunoassay

The microcolumn was packed with functionalized microbeads, as described in Section 3.2.2.2. To minimize non-specific interactions with both the microchannel PDMS surface and the agarose beads, a solution of 0.1% casein (*w/v*) was pumped at a flow rate of 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 10 min. Then, the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate (0.03 mg/mL) together with a given concentration of the analyte in the calibration assays or the prepared sample was pumped through the channel at a flow rate of 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ flow rate for 5 min (while keeping a constant percentage of MeOH of 1%), followed by a washing step with PBS 1 \times with a flow rate of 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 10 min, to remove any unbound labelled ABA-BSA conjugate and analyte. For the control assay, which was not spiked with ABA, only the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate was introduced into the microchannel. In the case of an ABA-spiked assay or an assay with prepared grapes or leaf samples (see Section 3.2.3), the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate flowed together with the sample to be measured.

3.2.2.6. Image Acquisition and Processing

The acquisition signal from the experimental assay was performed using a fluorescence microscope (Leica DMLM) equipped with a digital camera (DFC300FX) and a Cool LED lamp (pE-300lite) as an excitation light source, coupled to an I3 filter cube with a band-pass for excitation of 450–490 nm (blue) and a long pass for emission at 515 nm (green). The images acquired were analysed using ImageJ software from the National Institutes of Health, USA [162], where only the green channel was appraised. The value obtained through this green channel results from the subtraction between an inner area of the channel (signal), and an equal-sized area outside the channel (background). All fluorescence micrographs used for ABA quantification were acquired using an exposure time of 2 s, and 1 \times gain.

3.2.3. Sample Collection and Treatment for ABA Detection

To establish the sensitivity of the ABA detection assay, samples of real table grapes, white (Beauty Sweet Gold) and red (Red Globe), were bought at the supermarket and kept at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until use. These grapes have a low ABA content compared to grapes that are in the *veraison* stage. To validate the ABA detection method, berries from the Touriga Nacional cultivar were collected from a local vineyard at the *veraison* stage, frozen in liquid nitrogen, transported to the laboratory in dry ice, and kept at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until use. The protocol developed for sample treatment consisted of first macerating the sample in a mortar with a 5% MeOH solution diluted in PBS 1 \times , at a ratio of 1 g of sample to 1 mL of solution, for 8 min. This first step had the purpose of dissolving and extracting the biomarkers present in the plant tissues. Afterwards, the samples were centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 10 min, and the supernatants were collected and then filtered using a Nylon

syringe filter with a 0.2 μm pore diameter. In the next step, to remove any remaining contaminants that did not come out during filtration, such as debris, these supernatants were cleaned using Q-Sepharose beads packed in microfluidic channels. The supernatant was pumped through the channel with Q-Sepharose beads at a flow rate of 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 10 min. A final dilution was performed to reach a constant composition of 1.1% MeOH in all samples, given that during preliminary microfluidic experiments, it was verified that high percentages of MeOH caused interference with the molecular recognition assay.

3.2.3.1. Packing of the Sample Treatment Chamber

To insert the Q-Sepharose microbeads (diameter $\sim 90\ \mu\text{m}$) from Cytiva (Uppsala, Sweden) into the microfluidic structure, a negative pressure was applied at the outlet using a syringe pump. The channel was first filled with PBS 1 \times buffer, and a pipette tip containing 30 μL of bead solution (prepared at a ratio of 1:10 with its bead stock in 20% ethanol) was inserted into the chamber inlet₂ (Figure 3.2A). The negative pressure produced a flow rate of approximately 12 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ into the channel, resulting in the packing of the beads inside the sample treatment chamber. Subsequently, the microfluidic structures were washed at 22 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ with PBS 1 \times , and the bead chamber inlet₂ (Figure 3.2A) was sealed using a 20-gauge metal plug.

3.2.4. Reverse-Phase HPLC Detection of ABA

The concentration of ABA in the grape samples was confirmed using a Hitachi LaChrom HPLC system. The HPLC system consists of two pumps (L-7100), a UV-detector (L-7400), a programmable autosampler (L-7250), and an interface (Hitachi D 7000) to connect the system to a computer. The column used was a core-shell organo-silica LC column from Kinetex (5 μm EVO C18 100 \AA , 250 \times 4.6 mm) with UV detection at 206 nm. The analysis was performed in isocratic mode with sodium phosphate buffer (50 mM, pH 3.55, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) and acetonitrile (VWR, Carnaxide, Portugal) as the mobile phase (75:25 v/v), an injection volume of 25 μL , and a flowrate of 1.2 mL/min, following the method described in Brás *et al* [134].

3.3. Results and Discussion

The main objective of this work was the development of a method capable of detecting ABA in grapes using a microfluidic platform. In this work, ABA was used as a biomarker for the onset of grape ripening (berry colour transition), i.e., the *veraison* stage. A competitive immunoassay was designed, consisting of the immobilization of the anti-ABA antibody on Protein A

microbeads, which are mechanically trapped in the microfluidic channel (Figure 3.1A), followed by the optical detection of ABA in a competition between the ABA in the sample and a labelled ABA-BSA conjugate. This strategy is schematically summarized in Figure 3.1B. In this assay, in the absence of ABA, the fluorescence signal reaches its maximum, because there is no free analyte present to compete with the anti-ABA antibody capture sites. However, in the presence of ABA, the free analyte will compete with the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate in solution for the binding sites of the anti-ABA antibody, and, as a consequence, the higher the concentration of the free analyte, the lower the fluorescence signal.

The use of microbeads in the microfluidic structure increases the surface area for probe immobilization, leading to an increase in the sensitivity of detection. Additionally, it decreases the diffusion length required for capture, and therefore the duration of the assay. Given that the incubation of the anti-ABA antibody and the microbeads is performed off-chip, and then the functionalized beads are packed in the microfluidic channels, it is necessary to ensure that the number of microbeads is approximately the same in each assay. This is necessary to maintain approximately constant the number of antibodies available so that the conditions for the competition between the analyte and the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate for the binding sites are kept constant.

3.3.1. ABA-Spiked in PBS 1× Buffer

The first step in developing the assay was to determine the concentrations of labelled ABA-BSA conjugate and anti-ABA antibody to be used to obtain a competitive immunoassay. Figure S3.2 in the Supplementary Materials shows a summary of the optimization steps. The anti-ABA antibody concentration cannot be too high because if there are too many binding sites, there will be no competition between the free analyte and the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate, and both will bind to the anti-ABA antibody. The chosen labelled ABA-BSA conjugate concentration considers the anti-ABA antibody concentration used to functionalize the beads. It must always be lower than the antibody concentration, because otherwise, the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate would prevail over the analyte, resulting in no competition. After optimization, the chosen concentrations of anti-ABA antibody and labelled ABA-BSA conjugate were 0.2 mg/mL and 0.03 mg/mL, respectively.

After determining the concentration of labelled ABA-BSA conjugate and anti-ABA antibody, the dependence of the fluorescence signal with ABA concentration in PBS 1× buffer was measured and is shown in Figure 3.1C. To perform this experiment, successive dilutions of a solution with 50 mg/mL of ABA were measured to determine the lowest detectable ABA concentration using the microfluidic ABA detection immunoassay.

Figure 3.1C shows that the fluorescence dependence of ABA concentration yields a V-shaped graph. Between 10^{-11} and 10^{-5} mg/mL, the assay behaves as a typical competitive immunoassay, with the fluorescence decreasing as the concentration of ABA increases. However, for higher concentrations of analyte, between 10^{-4} and 10^{-1} mg/mL, the behaviour changes, and the fluorescence signal increases with increasing concentration of analyte, suggesting that there is an aggregate formation between the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate and the free analyte in solution. Figure S3.3 in the Supplementary Materials shows a more detailed schematic diagram of the proposed formation of aggregates. This shape will have an impact on the measurement of real samples, as discussed in Section 3.3.3.

The selectivity of this detection method was confirmed using a different analyte, SA, which, for concentrations around 10^{-5} – 10^{-4} mg/mL, showed no decrease in fluorescence concerning the control, which was the non-ABA spiked assay.

3.3.2. ABA-Spiked in Treated Table Grape Samples

Having established the sensitivity of the ABA detection assay in model conditions (i.e., using ABA in PBS 1×), the next step was to establish the sensitivity of the ABA detection assay in real table grape samples. For this purpose, a sample treatment protocol was developed as shown schematically in Figure 3.2A (and described in detail in Section 2.3).

The role of the step of bead cleaning step is to remove any larger particles that escaped the step of filtration step and that interfered with the analysis.

Using the protocol developed on table grapes, we obtained the curves shown in Figure 3.2B for the dependence of the fluorescence on the ABA concentration spiked in the grape samples. Table grapes were used in this study as they are easier to acquire. Both the curve obtained for the treated white grapes and for the treated red grapes match the curve obtained using PBS 1× buffer, confirming that the sample treatment protocol is efficient in removing the majority of the interferences from the grape samples. The decrease in fluorescence observed in assays with the real sample compared to the buffer is attributed to residual interferences.

Having developed a method capable of detecting ABA in PBS 1× buffer, as well as a sample treatment protocol capable of removing possible interferences in grapes, the next step is detecting ABA in wine grapes, under conditions in which a natural increase in ABA is expected.

3.3.3. ABA in Real Wine Grape Samples

The grape samples chosen to validate the ABA detection method are those undergoing the *veraison* stage, which corresponds to the phase in which the berries are in a colour transition.

During this phase, it is known that there is an increase in the concentration of ABA in the grape [23]. During the *veraison* stage, in the same cluster of grapes, some berries present a green colour, some dark, and others in between, revealing high heterogeneity in ripening. Samples were picked belonging to the three different stages, green, intermediate, and dark, as shown in the photos in Figure 3.3. The samples for “dark” and “green” grapes correspond to those that clearly show red and green colour, respectively. The “intermediate” grapes refer to samples that are exactly in the colour transition, where the berries have both colours. These samples were of the Touriga Nacional grape variety.

Before analysing the sample, the grapes were treated using the sample cleaning protocol mentioned in Section 3.2.3.

Using HPLC, it is possible to verify in Figure 3.3A that the ABA concentration is higher when the berry is exactly at the colour transition, as expected. Figure S3.4 in the Supplementary Materials shows how the ABA concentration was estimated using HPLC. Thus, intermediate and dark grape samples present 5×10^{-4} mg/mL and 4×10^{-5} mg/mL of ABA concentration, respectively. The ABA concentration in the green grapes could not be detected by HPLC and is estimated to be around 10^{-11} mg/mL.

The results of the microfluidic assay for ABA detection, shown in Figure 3.3B, agree with the results obtained by HPLC. It should be noted that, as the detection method is competitive, the absence of ABA in the sample results in an increase in fluorescence signal (as can be seen in the green sample). The intermediate and dark grape samples, which have ABA concentrations from HPLC in the 10^{-4} mg/mL and 10^{-5} mg/mL range, respectively, follow the curve shown in Figure 3.2B, where the fluorescence signal in a sample with 10^{-4} mg/mL ABA is higher than the fluorescence signal in of a sample with 10^{-5} mg/mL ABA. Nevertheless, this conclusion is possible since the ABA concentrations were known from the HPLC measurements. To clarify the ambiguity in ABA concentration due to the V-shape of the curve in Figure 3.2B, the same processed grape samples used to validate the assay were diluted 10× and remeasured using the microfluidic system. These results are shown in Figure 3.3C. Figure 3.3C shows that the intermediate and dark grape samples, when diluted 10×, have ABA concentrations in the 10^{-5} mg/mL and 10^{-6} mg/mL range, respectively, and in this way, the intermediate sample now has a lower fluorescence signal than the dark sample. Furthermore, the signal in the green grape sample remains at approximately the same value after dilution, as expected, presenting a value close to that of non-ABA spiked table grapes (Figure 3.2B), having an ABA concentration in the 10^{-11} mg/mL range. In this way, successive dilutions can be performed if there is an ambiguity in the concentration of ABA present in the sample.

Figure 3.3. ABA detection method validation in real grape samples. The three tested samples, dark, intermediate, and green grapes, were selected from a grape bunch undergoing veraison stage: (A) ABA concentration obtained from HPLC, where the peak area is directly proportional to the ABA concentration for each the tested samples; (B) ABA concentration obtained using microfluidic competitive immunoassay for ABA detection after the sample processing step; (C) microfluidic ABA detection competitive immunoassay performed in 10× diluted validation samples. The fluorescence intensity value of non-ABA spiked assay (table grape sample) was taken from Figure 3.2(B), by averaging the fluorescence intensity of the non-ABA spiked of the treated red grapes with the fluorescence intensity of the non-ABA spiked of the treated white grapes. The error bars represent \pm the standard deviation.

Finally, it is important to mention that the concentrations of ABA present in the different *veraison* stage samples are effectively 5× higher than those shown in Figure 3.3 and mentioned in the discussion above because the final step of the sample treatment protocol is a 5× dilution. This way, the estimated ABA concentrations for the intermediate, dark, and green grape samples during the *veraison* stage are 2.5×10^{-3} mg/mL, 2×10^{-4} mg/mL, and 10^{-11} mg/mL, respectively.

The determination of the ABA concentration described above has the limitation that the calibration curve used (Figure 3.1) was not obtained with the same matrix as the real grape samples used (Figure 3.3). Although Figure 3.2 suggests that the effect of the matrix, after sample treatment, does not qualitatively alter the calibration, it would be more accurate, in critical practical applications, to perform a calibration of the ABA concentration in a matrix as close as possible to that of the sample under study.

3.4. Conclusions

A microfluidic biosensing platform capable of detecting the onset of ripening biomarker—ABA—was proposed, demonstrated, and validated. ABA, in addition to being representative of the onset of fruit ripening, is also a biomarker of drought stress; thus, the platform developed in this work can be used to monitor ABA concentration over time in a continuous manner, and thus control the water level in the plant, and experiments are underway to demonstrate this capability. A competitive immunoassay was developed, in which the anti-ABA antibody is functionalized on the surface of microbeads trapped in the microfluidic device, allowing for the detection of ABA using a labelled ABA-BSA conjugate. It was possible to detect ABA not only in buffer but also in real grape samples (both spiked and intrinsic), in concentrations ranging from 10^{-6} to 10^{-3} mg/mL, making this method more sensitive than any other ABA detection method reported in the literature [134][177]. Using HPLC, only ABA concentrations above 10^{-5} mg/mL could be detected.

The integration of this microfluidic biosensor, and additional biosensors for other relevant plant hormones can potentially allow point-of-use, real-time control of grape biotic and abiotic stresses and onset of ripening, and improve timings of pesticide application and irrigation. It is noteworthy that ABA also regulates the same processes in other plants, such as strawberries and tomatoes, so this platform has the potential to be used in other plants than vines, both during growth and also during processing, transportation, and storage.

This work laid the foundations for ABA detection in a point-of-impact setting. Building on this microfluidic immunoassay is possible to integrate it with optical sensors, creating a platform that can be taken to the field.

Chapter 4

A Versatile Platform for Point-of-Care Detection of Molecular Biomarkers

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Highlights

This article presents a PoCT molecular biomarker detection platform based on microfluidics technology. The core of the platform is composed of a miniaturized microfluidic component designed to perform immunoassays for molecular recognition and a fluorescence biosensor system, where the optical transducer is a hydrogenated amorphous silicon (a-Si: H) p-i-n photodiode, which converts the molecular recognition event into an electrical signal proportional to the quantity of emission from the fluorescence label tagged to the target molecule. The fluorescence biosensor system achieved a LOD of 0.36 nM when measuring free Alexa₄₃₀ fluorophore in an open microfluidic channel. The microfluidic device was able to successfully replicate the results of a laboratory benchtop immunoassay. As proof of concept, the platform was used to detect ABA, a biomarker of grape maturation. The results showed a significantly different output for a green grape (low ABA levels) compared with a matured grape (high ABA levels).

Publication

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Personal contributions

Designed, and microfabricated the microfluidic structures. Development of the competitive immunoassay, and the sample treatment protocol, as well as, the validation with a real sample. Co-performed the experiments in the developed platform. Analysed all the data acquired from the ABA assay. Partial contribution to the writing of the publication.

4.1. Introduction

Molecular biomarkers can provide valuable information about the health of humans, animals, and plants, making them important for clinical diagnosis and pathogen detection. Their detection could help prevent the spread of infectious diseases both in humans and livestock [179], [180], allow early disease detection [181], and reduce the waste of resources by monitoring the health of agricultural cultures [182]. Unfortunately, in many parts of the world, access to these diagnostic tests is difficult due to insufficient medical facilities, lack of specialized staff, and the need for expensive, bulky laboratory equipment, making it crucial to develop a low-cost, fully integrated, and automated solution to perform molecular recognition testing [183].

Microfluidic PoCT devices have the potential to provide low-cost and rapid detection of molecular biomarkers [184]. This technology could provide an alternative diagnosis or screening tool, particularly in remote or low-resource places, thus helping to improve the overall quality of life in these areas. Microfluidics can be defined as “the science and technology of systems that process or manipulate small (10^{-18} to 10^{-9} L) amounts of fluids, using channels with dimensions of tens to hundreds of micrometers” [185]. Scaling down results in a high surface-area-to-volume ratio, which results in faster reaction times and improved assay kinetics. This translates into advantages such as faster assay times and lower sample and reagent volumes, reducing the overall costs. A microfluidic chip allows fluid operation and detection to be performed in the same device, making it more integrated and easier to make portable [98]. Many of the mentioned molecular diagnosis techniques are compatible with these platforms [184].

Integrating biosensor technology with microfluidics holds promising possibilities for advancing PoC diagnostics [98], [186]. A biosensor measures biological or chemical reactions by producing signals that correlate to the concentration of an analyte in the reaction [187], [188]. The choice of an integrated transduction strategy should consider not only the sensitivity of the transducer but also the possibility of multiplexing. Optical detection through fluorescence, chemiluminescence (CL), and colorimetric immunoassays are some of the more common biosensors' transduction methods used in multiplexed microfluidic [186]. One of the first applications of optical biosensors in microfluidics for PoCT devices was the lateral-flow strips for pregnancy tests using colorimetry. While the result of a colorimetric assay can be seen with the naked eye, a fluorescence-based assay needs an excitation light source and a filtered photosensor to transduce the resulting fluorescence emission into an electrical signal. Current systems with transduction-integrated ON-chip include optical-fiber-based designs, integrated photodiode designs, CMOS-based microfluidic technologies, and organic electronics-based designs [189]. Novo *et al.* [190] integrated a microfabricated (a-Si: H) p-i-n photodiode in a microfluidic structure and, using a 405 nm laser, achieved a LOD of 5.6×10^{10} antibodies per

square centimeter using antibodies labelled with fluorophores. Thin-film a-Si:H photodiodes show high quantum efficiencies, and low dark currents, and can be microfabricated on glass or plastic substrates. Excitation light sources in fluorescence systems are usually lamps, lasers, or light-emitting diodes (LEDs). Among these, lasers have been very popular since they have a narrow wavelength bandwidth and overall lower detection limits, but despite this, LEDs have become increasingly more used since they are inexpensive, compact, easy to integrate, and have long lifetimes [191]. Novak *et al.* [192], created an integrated fluorescence detection system for LoC using a 490 nm LED and reported an LOD of 1.96 nM when measuring fluorescein, and Wang *et al.* [193] developed a fluorescence detector with a 466 nm LED achieving an LOD of 0.077 nM for fluorescein sodium.

A truly portable device requires not only the integration of the biosensor with microfluidics but also the implementation of all the peripheral components needed to adapt the device to a PoCT setting. One of the main challenges is to integrate and automate the various essential components, such as sensors, valves, pumps, heaters, and temperature control, if applicable. This challenge must be overcome to take microfluidic devices out of the laboratory and turn them into a standard diagnosis technology [183]. One crucial component in most microfluidic biosensor-based systems is a programmable fluid handling system to perform the assays. Most commercially available automated fluidic handling systems are very bulky and are not adequate for a miniaturized PoC device. Wang *et al.* [194] developed a fully automated handheld general microfluidic liquid handling platform based on a “clamshell-style” cartridge socket, a miniature electro-pneumatic controller, and injection-mouldable plastic cartridges.

This article presents a platform consisting of a microfluidic fluorescence biosensor detection system integrated with a miniaturized and automated microfluidic fluid handling system using disposable PDMS chips, resulting in a fully integrated PoCT device able to detect relevant biomarkers. As a proof of concept, an immunoassay for detecting ABA, a biomarker of maturation and abiotic (water-level) stress in grapes, was optimized and performed using the microfluidic system developed in this work and benchmarked against the same immunoassay performed with standard benchtop equipment.

4.2. Materials and Methods

4.2.1. System Overview

Figure 4.1(a) shows the schematic of the complete system-level components that make up the device. The device developed in this work contains two main subsystems: fluorescence detection and microfluidic fluid handling systems. The complete system comprises four printed

circuit boards (PCBs) that house the excitation light source, the sensing component, the amplification circuit, the microcontroller unit (MCU), and power supplies. The device is controlled by a Teensy 3.6 and is powered by two 3.7 V LiPo batteries connected to a charger module. The Teensy was integrated into a PCB that also contains two linear dropouts (LDO) voltage regulators, one of 3 V (ADP7104ARDZ-3.0-R7) and another of 5 V (ADP7118AUJZ-5.0-R7), to supply the various components, including the Teensy.

Figure 4.1. Microfluidic device for biomarker detection. (a) Schematic of the complete system-level components that compose the device, which contains two main subsystems: the fluorescence detector (green) and the microfluidic fluid handling system (blue). (b) Photograph of the device with arrows indicating the location of different components.

A polylactic acid (PLA) enclosure box was designed using Fusion 360 and 3D-printed (UltiMaker S3). The box is 15×25×12 cm and was printed with an 80% infill to block as much ambient light as possible. The design includes a hinge, screw holes to fixate the several components into place, and openings to fit the touchscreen, turn ON button, and USB-C connectors. The final device photograph is shown in Figure 4.1(b).

A capacitive touchscreen (Adafruit 2.8" Colour TFT Touchscreen Breakout v2) was used for the user interface, which was designed to be as user-friendly as possible. The menu screen has three buttons: one to start the fluorescence measurement, one to perform an immunoassay with the fluidic handling system described in the next chapter, and the last one to control the washing of the valves. To perform an assay, the user places the microfluidic chip in the designated pocket in the photodiode's PCB that guarantees the alignment between the channel and the photodiode, presses the button to perform the immunoassay, and follows the instructions on the screen. Once the immunoassay is completed, the device is closed, and the button for acquiring the fluorescence

data is pressed. The device acquires and displays the data on the screen and is also saved to an SD card inserted in the Teensy SD card socket.

All the system components are reusable except for the PDMS chip. The platform is compatible with any 4.5 cm by 4.5 cm PDMS chip as long as the detection microfluidic channels are aligned with the photodiodes.

4.2.2. Fluorescence Detection System

The fluorescence detection system within the PoCT device uses an LED as a fluorescence excitation source to illuminate the microfluidic channel. The emitted fluorescence resulting from a fluorescence assay performed inside the microfluidic channel is captured by a photodiode with an integrated fluorescence filter positioned beneath the channel and converted into an electrical signal. This signal is subsequently amplified by a trans-impedance amplifier (TIA) and digitized by a 16-bit analog-to-digital converter (ADC) module (ADS1115, Joy-It).

We chose a 405 nm high-power UV monochromatic LED (LTPL-C034UVH405, Lite-On) as our excitation light source. This wavelength was chosen since at 405 nm the integrated optical filter blocks the excitation light and allows the transmission of the emission of a large Stokes shift fluorophore, such as Alexa430, which has an emission peak at 550 nm. Due to the LED's lack of collimation, a total internal reflection (TIR) lens (G2-ROSE-UV-SS, Ledil) was added on top. The LED and lens were mounted onto a PCB to ensure their alignment with each other. A constant current LED driver module was used to drive the LED with 52 mA.

At the light levels of fluorescence measurements, the photodiode is expected to produce photocurrents between 10^{-14} and 10^{-9} A. It is thus necessary to use a low-noise TIA with a large gain to amplify the signal. The overall performance of the circuits depends on the operational amplifier (OpAmp) chosen. We selected the ADA4530-1 op-amp from Analog Devices, a single, electrometer-grade operational amplifier characterized by an ultralow offset voltage and a femtoampere-level input bias current. A feedback resistor (RF) of 10 G Ω (HVC1206Z1008KET, Ohmite) was chosen, and a 3 pF ceramic capacitor (08055A3R0KAT2A, KYOCERA AVX) was added in parallel to guarantee the stability of the circuit and improve the filtering efficiency. The value chosen for the capacitor results in a bandwidth of 5 Hz, and, since the fluorescence signals are dc, the low bandwidth will not affect the signal and provide filtering of higher frequency noise sources. The TIA circuits have a dual power supply of ± 5 V: the ADP5074, a dc-to-dc inverting regulator, provides the negative power supply, and two LDO regulators, a positive +5 V fixed-voltage ADP7118 and a negative -5 V fixed-voltage ADP7182, provide a low-noise power supply to the ADA4530-1. The schematic of the electronic circuit for optical detection is shown in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2. Schematic of the electronic circuit for optical detection. The photocurrent generated from the fluorescence light of the *a*-Si:H photodiode is converted into a voltage by the ADA4530. The photodiode is unbiased.

Both the TIA and the respective power supplies were implemented on a four-layer PCB. Guarding techniques were implemented in the PCB design to minimize leakage currents. The techniques used include a guard ring, guard plane, fencing, coaxial connectors, and electrostatic shielding with RF shields on top and beneath the trans-impedance amplifier circuit. The center pin of the PCB's input SMB connector (the photodiode's cathode) is connected to the inverting pin of the ADA4530-1 OpAmp. The rest of the V_{in} pins are connected to the ground. This configuration makes the photodiode non-biased. The output of the TIA is connected to the output screw terminal.

The noise analysis of the TIA circuit was simulated using LTspice1 from 1 Hz to 2 MHz. The test circuit and the respective noise analysis are presented in Figures 4.3(a) and 4.3(b), respectively. The test circuit uses a simplified model of the photodiode used in this platform with an estimated 208.3 GΩ shunt resistance and an 8.35 pF junction capacitance. According to the simulation, the TIA has a noise contribution of 71.417 μ VRMS across the entire frequency spectrum.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4.3. Noise analysis of the TIA circuit. (a) Test circuit used for noise analysis. (b) Simulated noise with a frequency sweep from 1 Hz to 2 MHz.

Besides the TIA noise contribution, the noise introduced by the ADS1115 ADC needs to be considered. To acquire the data, the data rate of the ADC was set to an 8 samples per second (SPS) rate, which corresponds to the data rate with the highest oversampling ratio (OSR), meaning a lower output noise. According to the datasheet, the ADC noise will depend on the gain used. Considering that during signal acquisition the ADC is operated in automatic gain, and the maximum signal limit is 5 V, it is possible to infer that the highest noise possible is 187.5 μ VRMS at an 8-SPS data rate.

Considering the TIA's and the ADC's noise contributions and (1), the maximum total noise of the electronic circuit across the frequency spectrum is 200 μ VRMS. Considering the signals to be measured with this system, the level of noise simulated allows a good signal-to-noise ratio.

$$Total\ Noise = \sqrt{Vnoise_{TIA}^2 + Vnoise_{ADC}^2} \quad (Equation\ 4)$$

4.2.3. Fluid Handling System

In a typical laboratory bench-top fluid handling system for performing microfluidic immunoassays, a syringe pump is used to drive the flow, and each reagent is pipetted into the inlet of the microfluidic chip [139]. However, for a portable platform, this pump is too bulky, and the manual pipetting of the reagents is not user-friendly. For a true PoC device, it is necessary to design a new system.

The microfluidic device's full fluid handling system comprises a miniature peristaltic pump (RP-QIIIBP5S P06ADC3VS, Takasago and Aquatech Co) for flow control and four two-way normally closed (NC) valves (MVL-22-NC-08 14PPEEK-SIL, Memetis) mounted on a four-valve array with four inlets and a common outlet (AD-MVL22-PEEK-4v-T1032, Memetis) so the pump can pull the correct fluid at the right time from the different fluid reservoirs. OFF-chip components were chosen over ON-chip integration to simplify the microfluidic chip design. The pump was actuated with a stepper motor driver module (DRV8834, Polulu), which supplies the motor with 3 V, and each valve is connected to a constant current supply module that applies 500 mA to open the respective valve. The inlets of the four-valve array are connected through IDEX fittings (10⁻³² Flat-bottom PEEKFittings plus Ferrules, IDEX) to PTFE tubing with an internal diameter of 0.8 mm (BL-PTFE-1608-20, Darwin Microfluidics), and these tubes are submerged in Eppendorfs containing the reagents. A tube with an open metal plug at the tip is connected to the array's outlet.

When using this system for an immunoassay, there are three main steps: 1) pulling of the reagents from the reservoirs; 2) pulling of the correct volumes of each reagent necessary for the assay; and 3) pumping of the reagents inside the microfluidic channel. To perform the first two steps, the tubing of the peristaltic pump is connected to the outlet of the four-valve array, and the other tube of the peristaltic pump is connected to a waste recipient. In the first step, the reagents are pulled from the reservoirs. The first three reservoirs can be filled with the reagents, while the last reservoir always contains PBS needed for the washing steps of the immunoassay. First, the pump is turned ON, applying negative pressure to the valve array. Then, each valve, one at a time, is opened until the reagent has crossed the valve and reached the main channel of the adapter, and once that happens, the valve is closed. Once all the reagents have been pulled from the respective reservoirs, the valve connected to the PBS reservoir is kept open until the tubing connected to the adapter's outlet is filled with PBS. This step is important to guarantee that there will be no air gaps between the reagents, in the next step, and is also to wash the adapter and tubing of the first two reagents' waste, avoiding any chance of contamination. The second step corresponds to pulling the reagent volumes needed for the assay. Knowing the flow rate, each valve is kept open for the amount of time needed for the correct volume to flow out. The valve connected to the PBS

reservoir is kept open until the first reagent is at the end of the tubing connected to the adapter's outlet. For the final step, the tube connected to the outlet of the valve array is disconnected from the pump. The pump tubing is connected to the tubing from the third inlet immersed in the PBS. The pump is turned ON to purge the fluids so the fluids are on the tip of the metal plug, thus preventing any bubbles from entering the channel. After the purging, the tube connected to the valve array outlet is inserted into the microfluidic channel's inlet. The assay is performed by keeping the valve open and setting the pump to the desired flow rate, allowing the reagents to be pumped inside the channel. The steps mentioned are summarized in the schematic from Figure 4.4 [195].

The current setup allows any assay that requires one to up to four reagents and flow rates between 0.06 and 60 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ to be adapted to be performed within this platform.

Figure 4.4. Schematic of performing an immunoassay using the developed fluid handling system. (1) Pulling of the first reagent from the respective reservoir. (2) Pulling of the second reagent from the respective reservoir. (3) Pulling of PBS reagent from the respective reservoir and washing of the adapter and tubing to avoid contamination. (4) Pulling the correct volumes of each reagent necessary for the assay. (5) Pumping of the reagents inside the microfluidic channel. The image of the four-valve array is courtesy of Memetis [195].

4.2.4. Photodiode with integrated filter

The $200 \times 200 \mu\text{m}$ (a-Si: H) p-i-n photodiodes were used to detect the fluorescence emission from inside the microfluidic channel. The photodiodes were fabricated using as described elsewhere [196], [197]. The a-Si:H photodiodes are microfabricated on Corning Eagle glass

substrates. A bottom electrode of AlSiCu (2000 Å thick) and a top indium tin oxide (ITO) electrode (500 Å thick, resistivity 500 μΩ.cm) are used to provide electrical contact to the photodiode. ITO is a transparent conductive material, and so light enters through this electrode of the photodiode. The a-Si:H p-i-n layers were deposited using plasma-enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PlasmaPro, Oxford Instruments) with the respective thicknesses of 500, 5000, and 200 Å. The cross-section schematic of the a-Si:H is shown in Figure 4.5. These photodiodes have a 515 nm wavelength optical high-pass filter incorporated on top, fabricated using the techniques detailed in [198]. This filter works as the excitation filter, cutting the excitation light source wavelength (405 nm) while allowing the transmission of the fluorescence emission from Alexa® (A430) fluorophores (530 nm). This interference filter was designed as a distributed Bragg reflector (DBR) and was fabricated by depositing alternating layers of SiN_x and SiO₂ through radio frequency plasma-enhanced chemical vapour deposition (rf-PECVD).

The performance of the photodiodes was characterized [IV, photoresponse, and external quantum efficiency (EQE)] by applying a bias and simultaneously measuring their photocurrent using a picoammeter (Keithley 237). To measure the photoresponse and EQE, the current is measured while illuminating the photodiode with monochromatic light from a monochromator with a ruled grating (Newport model 77 298). As a light source, a tungsten-halogen lamp (HLX 64 655 250 W Xenophot, OSRAM) is used, and a power source supplies it (6032 0-60 V/0-50 A 1000 W, HP).

Figure 4.5. Schematic cross-section (not to scale) of the p-i-n photodiode with a photosensitive area of 200 μm by 200 μm [197].

4.2.5. Microfluidic Chip fabrication

The microfluidic structures used in this work for performing the assays were designed as described in [139]. The schematic of the microchannel and the respective cross-section are shown in Figure 4.6.

Figure 4.6. Schematic of the fabricated microfluidic channel, packed with protein-A microbeads for ABA detection. Adapted from [167].

The structure is composed of an inlet, used for the introduction of fluids, two channels with widths of 200 μm and height of 20 μm , a central channel with 1 mm width and 100 μm height that is connected to an inlet used to pack microbeads (diameter \sim 90 μm), that are used in the immunoassay, and an outlet. The trapping of the beads and packing along the larger channel is achieved by the height difference between the two channels.

The hard masks and master mould for the chip were fabricated as reported in detail in [156]. The PDMS elastomer was prepared by mixing PDMS with a curing agent (Sylgard 184 silicon elastomer kit, Dow-Corning) in a proportion of 1:10. The PDMS elastomer was then poured on top of the fabricated master mould and cured at 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 90 minutes. The cured PDMS was then peeled from the mould, and the inlets and outlets were opened by punching them with a 20-gauge needle. The structures were sealed against a 500 μm PDMS membrane that was prepared by spin-coating PDMS on top of a Si wafer and cured using the same conditions reported. The sealing process is achieved with a plasma cleaner (Harrick Plasma, Ithaca) by exposing the membrane and the PDMS structure with microchannels facing upward to oxygen plasma for 60 seconds. After oxygen plasma treatment, the PDMS structure is placed on top of the sealing side of the membrane. To guarantee that the PDMS regains its hydrophobicity and ensures good sealing, the structures can only be used after 24 hours of sealing.

4.2.6. Performing ABA immunoassay on the platform

To detect ABA, a competitive immunoassay was developed using a microfluidic chip with fluid handling by external syringe pumps and signal acquisition using a fluorescence microscope, as reported in detail in [167] and is schematically illustrated in Figure 4.7. Protein A microbeads with anti-ABA antibodies immobilized on their surface are loaded into the microfluidic chip. Antibodies bind to Protein A via the heavy chain part of the molecule, leaving the binding site

available for the target. To perform antibody immobilization incubation, 3 μL of bead stock was added to 19 μL of anti-ABA antibody at a 0.2 mg/mL concentration. After 60 minutes of incubation, 110 μL of PBS was added to homogenize the bead suspension. The incubation is made outside of the microfluidic channel. After incubation, the beads are inserted into the microfluidic structure [139]. Using beads in microfluidic immunoassays is useful since they enhance the surface-to-volume ratio inside the microchannel by a factor of 50 [74]. The sample under analysis is mixed with a labelled ABA-BSA conjugate. In this assay, in the absence of ABA, the fluorescence signal is at its maximum because there is no free analyte present to compete with the conjugate for the anti-ABA antibody capture sites. However, in the presence of ABA, the free analyte will compete with the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate in solution for the binding sites of the anti-ABA antibody. Consequently, the higher the concentration of free analyte, the lower the fluorescence signal.

Figure 4.7. Schematic of the ABA assay performed in the platform, and the fluorescence measurements (I) Microchannel is packed with functionalized beads outside the platform after the chip is placed on the slot. (II) Injection of casein 1% as blocking agent. (III) Injection of the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate (a: non-spiked assay) or labelled ABA-BSA conjugate plus a certain concentration of ABA (b: spiked assay). (IV) Wash with PBS 1 \times and detect with the fluorescence detector within the platform.

For this assay, only three out of the four valves are used. The first Eppendorf connected to the first valve contained 100 μL of the casein solution, the second one 20 μL of the conjugate plus a certain concentration of free ABA, and the last Eppendorf contained 1.5 mL of PBS. The

immunoassay works by first flowing in the channel 10 μL of 0.1% casein at a flow rate of 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ and then 5 μL of labelled ABA-BSA conjugate at a concentration of 0.03 mg/mL plus a certain concentration of free ABA, at the same flow rate. A final washing step is performed by flowing PBS at a flow rate of 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 10 minutes. The fluorescence signal is acquired twice: before the reagents are injected inside the channel, meaning before the assay is performed (background signal), and after the washing step.

4.3. Results and Discussion

4.3.1. Photodiode Characterization

The dark I–V curve of the photodiodes, plotted in Figure 4.8(a), shows that the lowest dark current is measured when the photodiode is unbiased. By having the lowest dark current possible, we are maximizing the detection of low levels of light.

Figure 4.8. *a-Si:H photodiode characterization. (a) Dark current-voltage (I–V) in logarithmic scale. (b) EQE as a function of wavelength with a bias of 0 V. (c) Photoresponse at 550 nm with a 0-V bias in logarithmic scale.*

Figure 4.8(b) presents the EQE plotted as a function of the incident light wavelength with a 0-V bias applied to the photodiode. The maximum EQE achieved in the photodiode with the integrated filter was 6.68% at a wavelength of 580 nm. The EQE for wavelengths smaller than 515 nm is reduced to 0.03%, confirming the good rejection achieved by the 515 nm high-pass filter.

The photoresponse is shown in Figure 4.8(c) as the photocurrent of the a-Si:H photodiode is plotted as a function of the photon flux of incident light at 550 nm, with the photodiode biased with 0 V. This wavelength was chosen since it is near the emission wavelength of Alexa₄₃₀, the fluorophore that will be used in the immunoassay. The photocurrent increases approximately

linearly with the light intensity. The photodiode response covers at least six orders of magnitude of light intensity down to a photon flux of the order of $10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$.

4.3.2. Fluorescence Calibration Curve

A calibration of the sensitivity of the fluorescence detector system developed for fluorescence emission was performed to validate it and assess the system's LOD, as shown in Figure 4.9(a). Successive dilutions of Alexa Fluor® (A430) NHS ester (succinimidyl ester) in PBS were made to produce concentrations of fluorophores ranging from 0.36 nM to 3.56×10^{-4} M, which were then measured with the integrated system. Each solution is pumped inside the same microfluidic channel, starting from the least concentrated solution and going to the most concentrated one. Washes with PBS were performed between each solution. Each point of the calibration curve corresponds to the photodiode signal with the channel filled with the fluorophore solution after subtracting the signal from the photodiode during the PBS washing step before the introduction of the fluorophore solution (corresponding to the background signal of the photodiode). The points correspond to an average of ten points taken consecutively at an 8-SPS data rate.

The calibration curve shows a clear correlation between Alexa₄₃₀ concentration and the system's output signal, with a LOD of 0.36 nM for free Alexa₄₃₀, highlighting the system's high sensitivity.

Figure 4.9. (a) Fluorescence detection system sensitivity curve in logarithmic scale using a dilution series of Alexa₄₃₀ fluorophore in PBS, conducted at room temperature. The solid red line corresponds to linear regression. (b) Fluorescence levels were measured with a microscope for the ABA immunoassays performed with the developed miniaturized fluid handling system, and the benchtop fluid handling system was measured with the fluorescence microscope. For both the fluidic systems, two experiments were performed: one without ABA (non-spiked) and another with ABA (spiked) with a 10^{-5} mg/mL concentration of free ABA.

4.3.3. ABA Immunoassays for Validation of the Device

This platform was validated with immunoassays of ABA in PBS, as well as in real berry samples from the Touriga Nacional cultivar at the *veraison* stage, which corresponds to the stage in which the berries are undergoing a colour transition. During this phase, it is known that there is an increase in the concentration of ABA in the grape, due to anthocyanin accumulation [8].

Two experiments were performed in PBS, one without ABA (non-spiked) and another with ABA (spiked). In the spiked immunoassay, a 10^{-5} mg/mL concentration of free ABA was used. To validate the immunoassay in the microfluidic device, the fluorescence levels were measured with a fluorescence microscope and compared with previous fluorescence levels obtained in the bench-top assay. The results are plotted in Figure 4.9(b). The levels of fluorescence obtained with the miniaturized fluid handling system are slightly higher than the ones obtained previously with the benchtop fluid handling system, but a similar difference in fluorescence between the non-spiked and spiked assays was achieved (1740 a.u for the benchtop system and 1700 a.u. for the miniaturized system).

After that, two other experiments were performed on real berry samples. During the *veraison* stage, in the same cluster of grapes, some berries present a green colour, some dark, and others in between, revealing high heterogeneity in ripening. For these experiments, only two different stages were considered, green and intermediate, as shown in Figure 4.10. The sample for “green” grapes corresponds to those that clearly show green colour. The “intermediate” grapes refer to samples that are exactly in the colour transition, where the berries have both colours. In these assays, the device was used to perform the immunoassays for ABA detection and to measure the fluorescence. It is important to note that grape juice has undergone a sample preparation protocol that includes maceration, MeOH extraction, centrifugation, and filtering and is fully described in [167]. The results are plotted in Figure 4.10(a), where each bar corresponds to the signal measured after the immunoassay, subtracting the background signal measured before the immunoassay. From the results obtained, it is possible to verify that the ABA concentration is higher when the berry is exactly at the colour transition, as expected. Figure 4.10(b) showcases fluorescence levels measured using a fluorescence microscope when performing the ABA immunoassay with green grape samples for both the fluid handling systems: the bench-top and the platform’s miniaturized system. The resulting fluorescence levels measured from both systems are very similar.

Figure 4.10. (a) Device output when measuring the fluorescence resulting from immunoassays for ABA detection on two real berries samples: “green” grapes that refer to those that clearly show green colour, and “intermediate” grapes that refer to grapes in colour transition. The error bars represent \pm the standard deviation from ten data points taken consecutively. (b) Fluorescence levels were measured with a microscope for the ABA immunoassays using the green grape samples performed with the developed miniaturized fluid handling system and the benchtop fluid handling system.

This indicates that the portable system developed in this work has comparable performance to the benchtop assay but requires less human intervention and offers increased portability.

4.4. Conclusion

The results presented in this article indicate that the miniaturized fluorescence biosensor system developed in this work, conjugated with the automated microfluidic fluid handling system, has the potential to perform biomarker diagnostic tests with a portable tool and minimal user intervention. Both the portable system and the consumables (microfluidic chips and reagents) are potentially low-cost in a mass fabrication scenario for applications in health, agrifood, and the environment, in particular, if thermoplastic-based chips are used instead of PDMS chips. The fluid handling system proposed is modular, portable, can be extended to handle more complex assays, and is fully programmable. In addition, it allows the use of microfluidic biochips that do not require the integration of valves or pumps. This system is also scalable to allow multiplexed testing of several biomarkers simultaneously. This can be done using a multi-wavelength array of LEDs and use, a photodiode array with a monolithic integrated multispectral optical interference filter array, as was described previously [199]. The LED wavelength and the interference array would be selected depending on the fluorophores being used. This configuration would allow the detection of fluorescence from a variety of fluorophores. For the fluidic handling system, a more simplified means of connecting the tubes to the pump and the microfluidic chip would need to be developed. In the case of the microfluidic chip, O-ring interconnects could be integrated [200]. Finally, a temperature regulation system could be added to the portable platform if the field assays were to be performed outside 20 °C–30 °C of ambient temperature range.

The integration of the microfluidic immunoassay with optical sensors takes the platform one step closer to being field-ready. However, it is necessary to remove the use of external pumps for fluid flow, as well as, having a simplified sample treatment protocol that does not require the use of laboratory equipment.

Chapter 5

A Reusable Capillary Flow-driven Microfluidic System for Abscisic Acid Detection Using a Competitive Immunoassay

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Highlights

PoC devices offer a promising solution for fast, portable, and easy-to-use diagnostics. These characteristics are particularly relevant in agrifood fields like viticulture, where the early detection of plant stresses is crucial to crop yield. Microfluidics, with its low reagent volume requirements, is well-suited for such applications. Self-driven microfluidic devices, which rely on capillary forces for fluid motion, offer an attractive alternative by eliminating the need for external pumps and complex fluid control systems. However, traditional microfluidic prototyping materials like PDMS present challenges due to their hydrophobic nature. This chapter presents the development of a reusable, portable, capillary-driven microfluidic platform based on a PDMS-PEG copolymer designed for the rapid, low-cost detection of ABA, a key biomarker for the onset of ripening of non-climacteric fruits and drought stress in vines. By employing passive fluid transport mechanisms, such as capillary-driven sequential flow, this platform enables precise biological and chemical screenings while maintaining portability and ease of use. A simplified field-ready sample processing method is used to prepare the grapes for analysis.

Publication

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Personal contributions

Designed, and microfabricated the externally pumped device, and co-fabricated the capillary structures. Development of the competitive immunoassay, and the sample treatment protocol, as well as, the validation with a real sample. Co-performed the experiments in the capillary platform. Analysed all the data acquired from the ABA assay. Main writer of the publication.

5.1. Introduction

Molecular biomarkers are crucial for monitoring the health of plants, animals, and humans, aiding in disease diagnosis and early intervention. To prevent the spread of infections, early detection is the key. This was shown in the COVID-19 pandemic, where rapid tests were essential [179][180][181]. This is also the case in agriculture, where early detection can prevent the spread of infections, optimize crop health, and enhance resource management [182][202]. However, access to traditional diagnostic tools is often limited by high costs, bulky laboratory equipment, and the need for specialized personnel. Besides this, the turnaround time for receiving the results of the analysis is often long, delaying the start of the intervention. This highlights the importance of developing rapid, portable, affordable, integrated, and easy-to-use PoC systems for molecular detection that are accessible even in resource-limited settings that could enable rapid, in-field diagnostics where timely decisions are essential for crop health and yield optimization [178][183][184][185][203].

This is particularly important for the early detection of plant stresses, which helps prevent disease spread, reduce resource waste, and improve overall crop management for sustainable agriculture. ABA (Molar Mass: 264.32 g/mol) is a plant hormone that is involved in the plant's response to physical environment changes and stresses, such as temperature changes, dehydration, and seed germination. Its levels rise under stress and during the ripening of non-climacteric fruits, like grapes, particularly in the *veraison* stage when the levels of anthocyanins increase and cause the berries to change colour [8]. ABA concentrations vary by grapevine cultivar, so what is normal for one genotype may indicate stress in another. Monitoring ABA over time helps establish a baseline for assessing plant health. Typically, ABA concentrations range from 10^{-5} to 10^{-1} mg/mL in grape berries [8][178][167]. HPLC is widely employed for detecting ABA, as it effectively separates and identifies components within a solution [204]. Despite its accuracy and reliability, HPLC is impractical for field applications due to its large, cumbersome equipment, the need for trained operators, lengthy analysis times, and significant operational costs [25][167].

Lateral Flow Assays (LFAs) are a widely recognized PoC technology, known for their simplicity and use in applications such as the detection of COVID-19 infections or pregnancy rapid tests. In these devices, the solution flows along a porous material (typically nitrocellulose) strip with immobilized reagents, where the reagents move laterally, producing visible results when detecting a target substance. Although LFAs are easy to use, affordable, and deliver quick results, they offer limited control over fluid flow, lack integration with advanced sensors, and are typically single-use. In contrast, channel-based capillary microfluidic devices provide more advanced capabilities by utilizing capillary forces to control fluid flow through patterned

channels, allowing for complex assays with sequential flows and sensor integration. These systems offer greater precision and reusability, with no cross-contamination between uses, and are ideal for applications requiring higher sensitivity, such as biomarker monitoring or advanced diagnostics in agriculture and personalized medicine [133]. Despite the potential advantages of PoC methods for detecting ABA in grapevines, the availability of such technologies remains limited, and most current detection methods still rely on traditional laboratory-based approaches. For instance, optical aptamer-based sensors with microfluidic interfaces have been reported for detecting plant hormones like ABA, offering sensitive and rapid detection through optical signals. However, they do not present an explicit sample treatment capable of being used in the field [25].

Microfluidic devices, particularly self-driven systems using capillary forces, process small volumes of samples and reagents with high precision, enabling the fast and sensitive detection of plant biomarkers and environmental factors, overcoming the challenge of needing external equipment for fluid control [98][184][205][206][207]. Microfluidic systems designed for sequential reagent flow are highly efficient tools for conducting complex biochemical assays, including immunoassays. These systems use precisely engineered channels and capillary forces to control the movement of various reagents in a set order, allowing for multiple steps in the assay to occur automatically. One key feature of these microfluidic platforms is their ability to handle intermediate and final washing steps, which are critical for removing unbound reagents and ensuring the accuracy and sensitivity of the assay. The system can introduce wash solutions between different reagent flows without user intervention, enhancing consistency and minimizing the risk of contamination [133]. PDMS, commonly used in microfluidics, is limited by its hydrophobic nature (contact angle $\sim 110^\circ$), making it unsuitable for capillary-driven flow [208][176]. To improve its wettability, methods like surface modifications, including oxygen plasma treatments and hydrophilic coatings, have been developed to make PDMS more effective for capillary microfluidic applications [133][209][210][211][212].

However, the effectiveness of these surface modification techniques should be assessed based on factors such as processing time, procedural complexity, required equipment, and their compatibility with downstream application processes. A balance must be achieved between enhancing PDMS's hydrophilicity and ensuring that the modifications are feasible, scalable, and compatible with the practical needs of agricultural PoC diagnostics. By addressing these challenges, microfluidic devices can offer a scalable, portable solution for monitoring plant stress, disease, and other factors affecting crop health and productivity [213][214]. PDMS-PEG is a hybrid material that combines the flexibility and hydrophobicity of PDMS with the hydrophilicity and biocompatibility of polyethylene glycol, making it ideal for antifouling, biomedical, and microfluidic applications [133].

With the goal of detecting stresses in grapevines in the field with minimal user intervention, in this study, a competitive immunoassay for the detection of ABA using a capillary-driven microfluidic device was developed based on the acquisition of a fluorescence signal. Key steps included developing a bead packing method, and adjusting the volumes and flow rates of the assay, as well as introducing intermediate washing steps, for a successful operation of the capillary chip. A simplified sampling cleaning protocol so that the whole analysis process can be performed in the field with no need for bulky laboratory equipment was also developed. Additionally, in this work, the device was fully characterised in terms of its reusability, and the method used to restore it to its original state after multiple uses.

5.2. Materials and Methods

5.2.1. Fabrication of the hard masks and the SU-8 moulds for the microfluidic devices – externally pumped and capillary

The microfluidic designs were created using CAD software (AutoCAD 2024 (version 24.3), Autodesk, CA, USA). An aluminium hard mask on Corning® Eagle glass is microfabricated using direct-write laser lithography (Heidelberg DWLII, Heidelberg Instruments, HD, DE) and subsequent aluminium wet etching (Gravure Aluminium Etchant, Microchemicals, MA, USA). Two aluminium masks were fabricated to allow the patterning of two-channel areas with different heights. These were used in conjunction with a negative photoresist, SU-8 2015 (Microchem, Newton, MA, USA) for 20 µm or 50 µm layers and SU-8 50 (Microchem, Newton, MA, USA) for 100 µm layers to create a two-level mould pattern. The SU-8 photoresists were subjected to UV light (UV KUB-2, KLOÉ, Saint-Mathieu-de-Trévières, FR) exposure through the corresponding aluminium hard mask, followed by a post-exposure baking process. The development was then carried out using PGMEA 99.5% (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) to remove the unexposed photoresist. The SU-8 mould was then rinsed with isopropanol and dried with compressed air, followed by a hard bake at 150 °C for 15 minutes [167].

5.2.2. PMDS device fabrication

5.2.2.1. Standard PDMS

To prepare standard PDMS, a curing agent and elastomer base were mixed in a 1:10 (w/w) ratio and then degassed for 45 minutes. Subsequently, the PDMS mixture was poured over the SU-8 mould. To ensure uniformity in the size of all replica moulds, a flat poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA, Trinseo S.A., Berwyn, USA) plate was positioned on top to close the

device. The assembly was then cured at 70 °C for 90 minutes. The microfluidic devices were sealed with a 500 μm thick PDMS membrane (fabricated on a silicon wafer under identical curing conditions) by exposing both surfaces to oxygen plasma (Harrick Plasma, Ithaca, NY, USA). To ensure a stable contact angle, the PDMS structures were stored for a minimum of 24 hours before use (Figure 5.1) [167].

Figure 5.1. Externally pumped microfluidic device: a 100 μm high channel utilized for bead packing, while a 20 μm high channel is designated for sample and reagent injection. The lower-height inlet and outlet channels effectively trap microbeads with diameters exceeding 20 μm .

5.2.2.2. Modified PDMS

For the modified PDMS, the standard mixture was combined with 1% (w/w) of dimethylsiloxane-(60-70% ethylene oxide) block copolymer. To fabricate the device's feature layer, which includes the channels, the detection chamber, and the capillary micropump, 1% copolymer-modified PDMS was poured onto the SU-8 mould. The PDMS mixture was then degassed in a heated desiccator at 40 °C. Once all air bubbles were eliminated, a flat PMMA plate was placed on top to close the device and ensure uniform size across all replicas. The assembled stack was cured for 90 minutes at 70 °C (Figure 5.2A). The capillary structures are sealed manually, offering the benefit of easy opening, cleaning, and reuse of the device. To close the channels, a 500 μm membrane is fabricated under identical curing conditions. This membrane was cast from a 6.42 \times 3.85 cm, 5 mm thick PMMA frame, with reservoirs engraved and drilled using CNC micromachining. (Figure 5.2B) The reservoirs were constructed with distinct geometries: the upper three were conical in shape, while the fourth featured a rounded-bottom cylindrical configuration. Each reservoir incorporated a 600 μm diameter circular aperture, designed to accommodate metallic adapters for sealing the serpentine channel. The conical geometry was optimized to enhance the efficient transfer of small reagent volumes to the entry points. Additionally, both the membrane and capillary structures were fabricated within frames

equipped with alignment markers to ensure accurate positioning of the features relative to the membrane's entry points (Figure 5.2C) [133].

Following the fabrication of both modified PDMS layers, the device was assembled using four components: the modified PDMS structure, a matching membrane, and top and bottom PMMA frames embedded with Teflon-coated magnets for sealing. The top frame had openings for the membrane's reservoirs and a vent at the capillary pump, while the bottom frame ensured proper alignment with a 2 mm depression to securely hold the device [133].

Figure 5.2. Device Assembly, Features and Operating Principles: (A) Modified PDMS feature layer. (B) Modified PDMS membrane layer incorporating reservoirs. (C) Key components of the capillary microfluidic device features: serpentine channel, four reagent entry points (reservoirs), capillary pump, air vent and microbead chamber. The device incorporates dual height levels within the microbead chamber to enable efficient trapping of microbeads. The total fluid volume capacity of the device is approximately 24 μL , with an average flow rate of 1.8 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$.

5.2.3. Ultraviolet ozone (UVO) treatment

UVO treatment was carried out using a UVO cleaner (1444AX-220, Jelight Company Inc., Irvine, CA, USA). After a significant change in the flow rates, to recover hydrophilicity in the device, the modified PDMS structures were submitted to the treatment, in which both interior surfaces of the device were exposed to a cycle of 5 minutes of cleaning and 5 minutes of exhaust time.

5.2.4. Solutions and chemicals

PDMS (Sylgard 184) was acquired from Dow Corning Corporation (Midland, MI, USA). Dimethylsiloxane-(60-70% ethylene oxide) block copolymer was acquired from Gelest (Morrisville, PA, USA). 10 kDa Amicon tubes were obtained from Merck (Alameda Fernão Lopes, Algés, Portugal). Protein A and Q-Sepharose microbeads were purchased from Cytiva (Uppsala, Sweden). PBS 10×, casein (1% w/v), Alexa Fluor® (A430) NHS ester (succinimidyl ester) from Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA), anti-ABA polyclonal antibody - AS09 422 (14.3 mg/mL) from Agrisera (Vännäs, Sweden), and ABA [BSA] (4 mg/mL) from Creative Diagnostics (Shirley, New York, USA). ABA (50 mg/mL), DMSO (10 mg/mL), and MeOH anhydrous 99.8% were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA).

5.2.5. ABA-BSA labelling

To prepare the fluorescently labelled ABA-BSA conjugate, 20 µL of ABA-BSA was diluted in 480 µL of 0.1 M sodium bicarbonate buffer and then conjugated with 2 µL of Alexa Fluor® (A430) NHS ester, an amine-reactive dye, which had been dissolved in DMSO at a concentration of 10 mg/mL and incubated at room temperature for 60 minutes in the dark. After incubation, the excess dye was removed by washing the mixture in a 10 kDa Amicon tube (Merck, Alameda Fernão Lopes, Algés, Portugal). This was done by adding 500 µL of PBS at a time, followed by centrifugation at $14,000 \times g$ for 10 minutes until the permeate became clear [167].

5.2.6. Protein-A microbeads functionalization

The protein-A microbeads (~90 µm) were incubated with an anti-ABA antibody solution by mixing 3 µL of bead stock with 19 µL of anti-ABA antibody at a concentration of 0.2 mg/mL. The incubation lasted 60 minutes. It is important to ensure that the 3 µL of microbead stock contains a consistent number of microbeads, as any variation in bead quantity across incubations could affect the antibody concentration on the microbeads, thereby influencing the number of available binding sites [167].

5.2.6.1. Microbead insertion in the externally pumped and capillary device

To introduce microbeads into the externally pumped microfluidic system, negative pressure was applied at both the outlet and inlet₁ using a syringe pump (NE-4000, New Era Pumps, Farmingdale, NY, USA). The channel was first pre-filled with PBS 1× buffer, and a pipette tip containing 20 µL of bead solution was positioned at the bead chamber inlet₂, as illustrated in

Figure 5.1. The applied negative pressure induced a flow rate of approximately 6 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, facilitating the packing of microbeads within the detection chamber. Subsequently, the microfluidic system was flushed with PBS 1 \times at a flow rate of 16 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, and the bead chamber inlet₂ was sealed using a 20-gauge metal plug. The bead-packed structure was then immersed in a container filled with DI water and refrigerated overnight to remove any air bubbles introduced during the bead-loading process [167].

For the capillary microfluidic device (Figure 5.2), 3 μL of functionalized microbeads were introduced into the bead chamber before performing the assay. Following the evaporation of the carrier solution, the device was manually sealed and made ready for operation.

5.2.7. ABA detection immunoassay

5.2.7.1. Externally pumped device

The bead chamber of the externally pumped device was packed with functionalized microbeads as described in Section 5.2.6.1. To minimize non-specific interactions with the PDMS surface of the microchannel and the agarose beads, a 0.1% (*w/v*) casein solution was introduced into the system at a flow rate of 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 10 minutes. Subsequently, the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate (0.03 mg/mL), along with a specified analyte concentration or prepared sample, was delivered into the channel at the same flow rate for 5 minutes, maintaining a consistent 1% MeOH concentration. This process was followed by a PBS 1 \times washing step at a flow rate of 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 10 minutes to eliminate unbound labelled ABA-BSA conjugate and analyte [167].

5.2.7.2. Capillary device

Following bead insertion into the capillary device, as outlined in Section 5.2.6.1, the device was manually closed (Figure 5.2C), reagents were loaded, and the immunoassay was conducted. In this assay, Reservoir 4 was filled with 12 μL of PBS 1 \times , which was used to prime the device and perform washing steps. Since the assay required only three reagents, Reservoir 3 was loaded with 5 μL of PBS 1 \times , Reservoir 2 with 4 μL of labelled ABA-BSA conjugate (0.03 mg/mL) mixed with a specified analyte concentration or prepared sample (maintaining a constant MeOH concentration of 1%), and Reservoir 1 with 3 μL of blocking agent (0.1% (*w/v*) casein).

5.2.8. Grape collection and treatment for ABA detection

To assess the sensitivity of the ABA detection assay, fresh Red Globe table grapes were purchased from a supermarket and stored at -80°C until use. These mature grapes exhibit naturally low ABA levels in comparison to those harvested at the *veraison* stage [8][167].

To further validate the ABA detection method, a first sample treatment was developed (Figure 5.3A) [167]. Berries from the Touriga Nacional cultivar were harvested at the *veraison* stage from a local vineyard and categorized based on anthocyanin accumulation into green, intermediate, and dark colour groups. The berries were flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen, transported to the laboratory on dry ice, and stored at -80°C for subsequent analysis. Sample preparation involved macerating the grape tissue in a mortar using a 5% MeOH solution diluted in PBS 1 \times , at a ratio of 1 g of tissue to 1 mL of solution, for 8 minutes to facilitate biomarker dissolution and extraction. The resulting mixture was centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 10 minutes, and the supernatant was collected and filtered through a 0.2 μm Nylon syringe filter. To further eliminate residual contaminants, including debris that passed the initial filtration, the supernatant was purified using externally pumped microfluidic channels packed with Q-Sepharose beads. The sample was passed through the channels at a flow rate of 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 10 minutes. Finally, all samples were diluted to achieve a consistent 1.1% MeOH composition, as preliminary microfluidic experiments showed that higher MeOH concentrations interfered with the molecular recognition assay.

To load the Q-Sepharose microbeads (~ 90 μm diameter) into the sample cleaning microfluidic structure (Figure 5.3), negative pressure was applied at the outlet using a syringe pump. The channel was first filled with PBS 1 \times buffer, and a pipette tip containing 30 μL of bead solution (prepared by diluting the bead stock 1:10 in 20% ethanol) was positioned at the chamber inlet₂. The applied negative pressure induced a flow rate of approximately 12 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, facilitating the packing of beads into the sample treatment chamber. Following this, the microfluidic structure was rinsed with PBS 1 \times at a flow rate of 22 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, and the bead chamber inlet₂ was sealed using a 20-gauge metal plug.

A centrifuge is not practical for field testing. Therefore, the sample treatment was simplified by eliminating the centrifugation and filtration steps from the original protocol, as shown in Figure 5.3B. This modified process is fully suitable for field use and does not require specialized personnel to operate the equipment.

Figure 5.3. Overview of Grape Sample Treatment Steps: (A) Comprehensive protocol: The process includes maceration of the sample; centrifugation (2000 rpm, 10 minutes), filtration through a 0.2 μm pore-sized filter, and a bead-based cleaning step within a microfluidic channel. The microfluidic columns used for cleaning were 1 cm in length, 0.1 cm in width, and 100 μm in height. Additionally, the system featured a smaller channel (200 μm in width and 20 μm in height) specifically designed to trap beads with diameters exceeding 20 μm . (B) Simplified protocol: The procedure consists of sample maceration followed directly by a bead-based cleaning step within a microfluidic channel.

5.2.9. Fluorescence image acquisition and data analysis using ImageJ

Fluorescence images for the experimental assays were captured using a fluorescence microscope (Leica DMLM, Wetzlar, Germany) equipped with a digital camera (DFC300FX) and a CoolLED lamp (pE-300lite) as the excitation light source. A filter cube with an excitation band-pass of 450-490 nm (blue) and an emission long-pass filter at 515 nm (green) was used. The acquisition parameters were fixed, with an exposure time of 2 seconds, a gain of 1 \times , and a saturation of 1, all acquired using a 10 \times objective. The images were then analysed with ImageJ software 1.49 (National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MD, USA) [162]. The analysis involved splitting the images into RGB channels, with only the green channel being further analysed. A region of interest (ROI) was defined around the beads to extract the fluorescence signal. The resulting green channel signal was determined by subtracting the background fluorescence (measured from an equal-sized area outside the bead chamber) from the fluorescence signal inside the ROI. These consistent acquisition settings and analytical methods ensured reliable quantification of the ABA in the micrographs [167].

5.3. Results and Discussion

The goal of this chapter is to detect ABA in a capillary-driven microfluidic device. By leveraging the natural capillary forces of the microfluidic system, the platform enables a simple and efficient detection method. ABA, a key biomarker for grape ripening during the *veraison* stage, is detected using a competitive immunoassay. ABA detection will be performed on real grape samples, utilizing a sample treatment method that was previously developed in our group [167]. This sample treatment will be compared to a newly developed field-ready sample treatment introduced in this study.

The user-friendly platform consists of the modified PDMS structure, the membrane layer, and the top and bottom PMMA frames [133]. A master mould was developed, with two distinct heights, to trap the microbeads inside a chamber, as can be seen in Figure 5.2, and used to carry out the competitive immunoassay. The SU-8 mould for the capillary device was fabricated using photolithography and soft-lithography techniques, as detailed in Section 5.2.1.

5.3.1. Test of capillary device operation with food colouring

The capillary microfluidic system was tested with food dyes, where each different colour can be associated with the reagents required for the immunoassay, to confirm the functionality of the optimized dual-height design in terms of sequential flow.

Device operation starts by sealing the reservoirs with metallic adapters and filling them with the solutions (Section 5.2.2.2). The volumes used in the proof-of-concept assay were 12, 4, 4, and 4 μL of orange, blue, green, and purple food colouring, respectively. Figure 5.4 represents the sequential flow of solutions from the moment the reservoirs are filled until the end of the assay. The liquid starts to flow when the bottom metallic plug is pulled from the structure, allowing for the priming of the microchannels. As the priming solution (orange) flows through the remaining three reservoirs, their plugs are sequentially removed, starting from the top to the bottom, allowing for the solutions to enter the device in a controlled manner. The reservoir containing the priming/washing solution facilitates the replication of the intercalated flow of reagents and washes typically utilized in standard immunoassays. The end of the assay is indicated by the filling of the capillary pump.

A correlation can be established between the various colours employed and the reagents in a competitive immunoassay: orange represents the washing buffer, blue represents the blocking agent, green represents the sample (which can be spiked or not spiked with ABA) together with the conjugate, and purple represents the washing buffer. In this assay architecture, the probe

antibody to which the target/conjugate will bind must already be present in the device, and, in this case, it is functionalized onto the protein-A microbeads off-chip, as detailed in Section 5.2.6.

Figure 5.4. Representation of the device's operation using food colouring: (A) Schematic illustration showing the key steps — reservoir filling (I); device priming – orange (II); and sequential introduction of solutions (blue, green, purple) from the remaining reservoirs (III and IV). (B) Photographs demonstrating the proof-of-concept with food colouring. Note that the images are captured from a top-down perspective, which does not reveal the height difference between the channel and the bead chamber.

5.3.2. Flow rate measurements

The use of liquids with different food colourings to test the performance of the capillary microfluidic device allows for the determination of the position of each reagent at a specific time after flow initiation. In addition to following the sequential flow, the images obtained can be used to calibrate the flow rates between specific points.

To determine the average flow rate of the capillary device, one can use the total assay time and the volume of the microfluidic structure, which is approximately 24 μL . The assay completion time was measured from the beginning of the priming step until the liquid reached the end of the capillary pump. The flow rate in the device stabilizes after the third use with a completion time of approximately 13 minutes, resulting in a flow rate of approximately 1.8 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$.

Additionally, the flow rate between specific parts of the device was assessed to determine how the reagents of the immunoassay were flowing through the structure. Several images were acquired throughout the assay, and the area occupied by the liquid was measured, converted to a volume, and divided by the time intervals between the images. Figure 5.5A shows these results, separated into three parts: the serpentine channel, the bead chamber, and the capillary pump. The obtained flow rate is higher when compared to the one in the ABA detection immunoassay using an externally pumped device, in which reagents flow at 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. However, it is lower than the rate used for the final PBS wash of 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$.

To determine the feasibility of device reuse and possible treatments to recover the hydrophilicity of the membranes, device ageing experiments were performed. To assess the ability to reuse the device, PBS was flowed through the channels, and the flow rate was measured each time. The results are expressed as the average flow rate, calculated from the total volume of the structure and the completion time of the assay. The flow rate variations can be seen in Figure 5.5B. After approximately three initial applications of the device, the modified PMDS can be reused at least four times, with minimal change in flow rates if used once a day, having a slight decrease at day eighteen. However, if used several times a day, with the first to last represented from darker to lighter colours, respectively, there is a significant decrease in average flow rates. This may occur if the hydrophobic methyl groups in PDMS migrate to the surface, returning to a more stable configuration. Furthermore, the fluid flow accelerates this re-arrangement process, especially under repeated flow conditions, which is seen when comparing daily use to multiple uses in a short time.

Figure 5.5. (A) Flow rate measurements were obtained through image acquisition and calculation at specific time intervals, when the liquid was flowing in the serpentine channel, bead chamber (highlighted in blue) and capillary pump. (B) Average flow rate measurements by repeated flow of PBS through the microchannels, to assess the ability to reuse the device and hydrophilicity recovery after UVO treatment. Each measurement refers to one experiment per day, except for 19 and 24, where several experiments were done, first to last represented from darker to lighter colour respectively. The error bars represent the standard deviation between two independent devices. (C) Fluorescence intensity measurements taken across multiple uses of the same capillary device, with respective acquired fluorescence images. The excitation wavelength was 450–490 nm (blue excitation light).

To recover hydrophilicity in the device, the membranes were exposed to the UV Ozone cleaner for 10 minutes, as described in Section 5.2.3. As a result, the surface becomes more hydrophilic, because hydroxyl and carbonyl groups are introduced. Figure 5.5B shows the hydrophilicity recovery of the device since the flow rate returns approximately to its initial state after the UVO treatments. Just like the first times the device is used, a similar stabilization in the flow rates is seen between days twenty and twenty-three, following UV Ozone treatment. Similar

flow rates were also registered after treatment, on days twenty and twenty-five, and on the first use, at day one.

An additional study investigated potential fluorescence residues left on the chip after each use of the capillary device. The fluorescence intensity shown in Figure 5.5C was measured after using and washing the capillary chip. Figure 5.5C confirms the absence of fluorescence contamination between uses, indicating that the device can be reused successfully, at least five times, with no contamination observed. The cleaning protocol between each experiment involves unsealing the device, washing both components, modified PDMS feature layer (Figure 5.2A) and modified PDMS membrane layer with reservoirs (Figure 5.2B), with isopropyl alcohol (IPA) and DI water, and drying them thoroughly with an air gun.

5.3.3. Application of the platform to a competitive immunoassay

A competitive immunoassay was used as a proof-of-concept application in the capillary platform. This assay was developed previously by our work group through immobilizing anti-ABA antibodies on Protein A microbeads using an externally pumped microfluidic channel for optical detection of ABA (Section 5.2.7.1) [167]. This strategy is schematically summarized in Figure 5.6. In this setup, the fluorescence signal is maximal in the absence of ABA. However, as ABA concentrations increase, the free analyte competes with the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate for binding to antibody sites, resulting in a reduction of the fluorescence signal. The use of microbeads enhances sensitivity by increasing the surface area for antibody binding and reducing assay time by decreasing diffusion distances. Consistent bead quantities were used to ensure uniform antibody availability and consistent competition conditions across assays. The optimal concentrations of the antibody and conjugate were previously determined to be 0.2 mg/mL for the anti-ABA antibody and 0.03 mg/mL for the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate [167].

In the control assay, where no ABA is present, only the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate is introduced into the microchannel. In contrast, for assays involving spiked ABA or treated grape samples, the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate is co-introduced with the sample under analysis.

The relationship between fluorescence signal intensity and ABA concentration in treated table grapes was evaluated, with the results presented in Figure 5.7. For these experiments, successive dilutions of ABA were spiked into the treated samples to determine the minimum detectable ABA concentration using both the externally pumped device and the capillary device. The sample treatment protocol, detailed schematically in Figure 5.3A of Section 5.2.8, including a centrifugation step, was strictly followed.

Figure 5.6. A schematic of the competitive fluorescence immunoassay is presented, comprising three key stages: bead functionalization, in which the anti-ABA antibody is covalently attached to the bead via its constant region, leaving the binding site available for target interaction; a control assay without ABA, where only the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate is present, binding to the anti-ABA antibody and generating the maximum fluorescence signal due to the absence of competition; and an ABA-spiked assay, where both the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate and free ABA analyte compete for antibody binding sites. As the concentration of free ABA increases, the fluorescence signal diminishes due to decreased binding of the labelled conjugate.

A competitive immunoassay using an externally pumped device was previously developed [167] and then adapted for the capillary device (Section 5.2.7.2). Both the flow rate and reagent volumes were adjusted. The standardized flow rate for this capillary device was set to 1.8 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. Figure 5.7 shows that similar results were obtained with both the externally pumped and capillary devices, with a LOD from 10^{-6} to 10^{-3} mg/mL and 10^{-6} to 10^{-4} mg/mL, respectively, confirming the applicability of the capillary device for ABA detection. Regarding the assessment of grape ripeness based on fluorescence intensity in on-site applications, it is important to note that grape ripening is accompanied by visible colour changes and an increase in ABA concentration, as documented in the literature [8]. These measurements help identify the relevant segment of the curve, enabling accurate quantification of the ABA concentration. For a continuous study of grape ripening, monitoring the same grape bunch over successive seasons would provide valuable insights. This approach would allow for the observation of ABA concentration dynamics over time, offering a clearer picture of the relationship between ABA levels and grape maturation.

Figure 5.7. A competitive immunoassay for ABA detection was performed on ABA-spiked treated table grape samples, with ABA concentrations ranging from 10^{-2} to 0 mg/mL ($n=2$), using optimized concentrations of anti-ABA antibody (0.2 mg/mL) and labelled ABA-BSA conjugate (0.03 mg/mL). Fluorescence intensity was measured on two platforms: an externally pumped device and a capillary-driven device. The excitation wavelength was 450-490 nm (blue excitation light). Error bars represent \pm the standard deviation.

The fluorescence response as a function of ABA concentration follows a V-shaped curve. Below 10^{-5} mg/mL, the assay behaves as a typical competitive immunoassay, with fluorescence decreasing as ABA concentration increases. However, at higher concentrations, above 10^{-5} mg/mL, the fluorescence signal increases with rising analyte concentration, suggesting the potential formation of aggregates between the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate and the free analyte in the solution. Therefore, as a part of our method to accurately assess the ABA concentration in the sample, a 10 \times dilution may be used to identify the corresponding segment of the curve and accurately determine the ABA concentration.

5.3.4. Sample treatment in wine grape samples

The grape samples selected to validate the ABA detection method, through the capillary device, were at the *veraison* stage, the phase where berries undergo colour change. During this stage, ABA levels are known to rise in grapes. In the same grape cluster, berries exhibit varying degrees of ripening, with some remaining green, others turning dark, and a few in between, showing significant ripening heterogeneity. Samples were categorized into three stages—green, intermediate, and dark—based on their visual appearance, as seen in Figure 5.8. "Green" grapes were fully green, "dark" grapes had a clear red colour, while "intermediate" grapes showed both colours, marking the transition. All samples were of the Touriga Nacional cultivar.

Figure 5.8. The ABA detection method was validated in real grape samples using the capillary microfluidic device. Three grape samples—dark, intermediate, and green—were selected from a grape cluster at the *veraison* stage. ABA concentrations were measured using the microfluidic competitive immunoassay for ABA detection under three conditions: without sample processing, with sample treatment involving centrifugation, and with simplified treatment that excludes centrifugation and filtration. The final set of bars represents the microfluidic ABA detection competitive immunoassay performed on 10× diluted validation samples subjected to the simplified sample treatment. The excitation wavelength was 450–490 nm (blue excitation light). Error bars represent \pm the standard deviation ($n=2$).

The samples used in this study were previously analysed using HPLC [167]. The ABA concentrations in the intermediate, dark, and green grape samples, measured with HPLC, were approximately 5×10^{-4} mg/mL, 4×10^{-5} mg/mL, and 0 mg/mL, respectively.

To be able to detect stress biomarkers in grapevines directly in the field—without requiring skilled operators, lengthy analysis times, or high costs—a simplified sample treatment method was developed. This method eliminates the need for equipment typically unavailable in field settings, such as centrifuges (Figure 5.3B in Section 5.2.8).

Figure 5.8 highlights the importance of proper sample pre-treatment. In the first set of results, it is evident that without treatment, it is difficult to distinguish the fluorescence intensity between the green and intermediate samples. In the next set of results, the sample treatment developed in reference [167] was applied, with the microfluidic assay for ABA detection yielding results consistent with those obtained from HPLC analysis. As anticipated in a competitive assay, the absence of ABA in the sample results in a higher fluorescence signal, as observed in the green grape sample. The intermediate and dark grape samples, with ABA concentrations of approximately 10^{-4} mg/mL and 10^{-5} mg/mL, respectively, exhibit fluorescence trends consistent with those presented in Figure 5.7. In these cases, the fluorescence signal for the 10^{-4} mg/mL ABA sample is greater than that of the 10^{-5} mg/mL sample. However, this pre-treatment requires centrifugation, which is not convenient for use in the field. To address this limitation, a simplified pre-treatment was developed involving only maceration and a bead-cleaning step in a microfluidic channel. The results in Figure 5.8 show that the fluorescence intensity levels from this simplified treatment were similar to those obtained using the previous method, which includes centrifugation [167]. This demonstrates that sample preparation can be effectively streamlined to just maceration and bead cleaning in a microfluidic channel for use in the field.

In order to address the uncertainty in ABA concentration caused by the V-shaped curve in Figure 5.7, the processed grape samples previously used for assay validation were diluted by a factor of 10 and reanalysed with the capillary microfluidic system, and the simplified sample treatment. The results of these measurements, shown in Figure 5.8, indicate that after a $10\times$ dilution, the ABA concentrations in the intermediate and dark grape samples are within the ranges of 10^{-5} mg/mL and 10^{-6} mg/mL, respectively. Consequently, the intermediate sample displays a lower fluorescence signal compared to the dark sample. Additionally, the fluorescence signal of the green grape sample remains relatively unchanged after dilution, consistent with expectations, as it closely resembles the signal from the non-ABA-spiked grapes. Therefore, if there is uncertainty regarding the ABA concentration in a sample, further dilutions can help clarify the measurement. However, when performing these measurements, one must take into account that the labelling process (Section 5.2.5) inherently varies slightly between consecutive runs. These variations result in differences in fluorescence intensity. The key focus should be on observing the overall trend. However, our goal is to determine the concentration of ABA, not just to look at the trend. Observing the trend is simply one step in our method to accurately quantify the ABA concentration. The most accurate approach would be to generate a new calibration curve each

time a new labelling is performed. Additionally, it is important to calibrate the ABA concentration using a matrix that closely resembles the sample under study; for example, in the experiments in Figure 5.7, one should use a wine grape matrix.

5.4. Conclusions

A capillary microfluidic biosensing platform for detecting the fruit ripening biomarker ABA was successfully developed, demonstrated, and validated. Beyond indicating the onset of fruit ripening, ABA also serves as a biomarker for drought stress, making this platform suitable for the continuous monitoring of ABA levels to assist in managing plant water status. The platform's functionality was enhanced by incorporating a dimethylsiloxane-(60–70% ethylene oxide) block copolymer into PDMS, rendering it hydrophilic and compatible with capillary-driven applications. The design incorporates a two-height structure to improve microbead trapping within the chamber, while it was demonstrated that the device has the potential to be reused at least four times, enhancing both its environmental sustainability and its user-friendliness.

A sequential introduction of solutions was initially demonstrated using food dyes, followed by a competitive immunoassay for ABA detection. This immunoassay employed fluorescence as the signal transduction method, with anti-ABA antibodies functionalized on the surface of the microbeads trapped within the capillary microfluidic device [167]. Additionally, this study introduced and validated a simplified sample treatment that eliminates the need for centrifugation, thereby enabling the platform's use for in-field ABA detection.

A key advantage of the proposed device is its magnetic-assisted mechanical sealing, which enables easy opening, cleaning, and reuse. The platform is user-friendly, with three simple steps: reagent loading, device priming, and reservoir opening. With the developed assay, we were able to detect ABA in concentrations ranging from 10^{-6} to 10^{-4} mg/mL using our capillary device, which is within the range of interest [25]. The most used technique, HPLC, has a LOD of around 10^{-4} mg/mL [215]. An alternative microfluidic technique using aptamers as molecular recognition probes was able to obtain a LOD of 10^{-5} mg/mL [25]. This makes our assay as sensitive as the previously reported ones, with the additional advantage that it can be used directly in the field from a raw sample, providing results in just 13 minutes.

For full automation and portability, future integration of an optical sensor or colorimetric measurements with smartphone readout will be necessary to further enhance the platform's portability.

This capillary platform for ABA detection allows for monitoring drought stress directly in the field. However, monitoring other stress biomarkers is also vital for optimal crop management. One key biomarker is SA, which is linked to biotic stresses in grapevines, such as pathogen infections. With this goal, we aimed to develop a microfluidic platform for SA detection in the field. Since these stresses impact crops beyond grapevines, the platform was validated using strawberry samples, as contaminated grape samples were unavailable.

Chapter 6

Aptamer-Based Microfluidic Assay for In- Field Detection of Salicylic Acid in *Botrytis cinerea*- Infected Strawberries

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Highlights

Rapid detection of plant infections is crucial for minimising crop loss and optimising management strategies, particularly in the context of climate change. While traditional diagnostic methods provide precise measurements of phytohormones such as salicylic acid (SA), a key regulator of plant defence responses, their reliance on bulky equipment and lengthy analysis times limits field applicability. This study presents a microfluidic-based aptamer assay for SA detection, enabling rapid and sensitive fluorescence-based readout from plant samples. A tailored sample pre-treatment protocol was developed and validated with real strawberry samples using HPLC measurements. The assay demonstrated a detection limit ranging from 10^{-9} to 10^{-6} mg/mL, within the relevant range for early infection diagnosis. The integration of the microfluidic platform with the optimised pre-treatment protocol offers a portable, cost-effective solution for on-site phytohormone analysis, providing a valuable tool for early infection detection and improved crop management.

Publications

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Personal contributions

Development of the aptamer-based assay, and the sample treatment protocol, as well as, the validation with a real sample. Co-performed the HPLC measurements. Analysed all the data acquired. Main writer of the publication.

6.1. Introduction

The increasing global population, projected to surpass 9.7 billion by 2050, requires a substantial rise in agricultural production, estimated at 60–110% according to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) [53]. However, this goal is challenged by climate change, soil degradation, and pollution, which threaten crop yields and food security. Among these challenges, plant diseases pose a significant risk, with their rapid spread impacting both economic stability and environmental sustainability [167]. As climate conditions become more unpredictable, early detection of plant infections is crucial for timely intervention, preventing disease outbreaks, and minimizing losses [216][217][218].

The traditional approach for pathogen detection is by directly detecting the pathogen's genetic material through DNA amplification techniques, most commonly the polymerase chain reaction (PCR). PCR provides great sensitivity and specificity, and remains the gold standard, however, it involves complex sample preparation procedures, lengthy analysis times, and diverse laboratory equipment that cannot be taken to the field [219][220].

One promising approach for early pathogen detection is monitoring changes in phytohormone levels before visible infection symptoms appear. In particular, salicylic acid (SA) plays a key role in plant defence, as its concentration increases in response to biotic stress, such as fungal infections [7]. However, conventional detection methods, including High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), while highly accurate, are impractical for field use due to bulky equipment, skilled operator requirements, and lengthy analysis times [25][53]. These limitations delay intervention, reducing the effectiveness of disease management, especially during rapidly spreading infections. Thus, there is an urgent need for portable, cost-effective PoC diagnostic tools that enable real-time, in-field SA detection, particularly in resource-limited settings [63][64][98].

Despite the advantages of PoC methods for plant hormone analysis, their availability remains limited. Most existing detection techniques rely on laboratory-based approaches, which lack the portability required for field applications. Optical aptamer-based sensors integrated with microfluidic platforms have shown promise for detecting plant hormones such as ABA, offering rapid and sensitive detection [25]. However, the absence of suitable sample pre-treatment protocols for complex plant matrices limits their practical implementation. Addressing this gap requires the development of streamlined, field-compatible diagnostic tools capable of integrating robust sample processing with highly sensitive detection mechanisms.

This study presents a novel microfluidic-based aptamer assay for SA detection in strawberry samples. SA (molar mass: 138.12 g/mol) plays a key role in plant defence, particularly in the SAR pathway [41]. During infection, SA accumulates at the infection site, triggering protective mechanisms and limiting pathogen spread. SA levels vary among strawberry cultivars, and monitoring these fluctuations helps establish a baseline for plant health [7][8][17]. In strawberries, SA concentrations typically range from 10^{-5} to 10^{-1} mg/mL [25].

Strawberries are highly susceptible to fungal infections such as *Botrytis cinerea*, the causal agent of grey mould, which thrives in humid conditions and can cause substantial yield loss, reduced fruit quality, and shorter post-harvest shelf life [221]. Even at undetectable infection levels, grey mould can accelerate spoilage during transport and storage [222][223]. Previous studies have shown that SA levels increase in grapes infected with *Botrytis cinerea*, suggesting a broader role for SA in plant immune responses. Monitoring SA fluctuations in strawberry plants could provide valuable insights into infection progression and improve disease management strategies.

Aptamer-based sensors offer a highly specific and sensitive alternative to conventional antibody-based assays. Aptamers, single-stranded DNA or RNA molecules selected through the Systematic Evolution of Ligands by Exponential enrichment (SELEX), exhibit strong binding affinities (picomolar to nanomolar range) and superior stability under various environmental conditions [101][224]. Unlike antibodies, aptamers can be synthesised against targets with low immunogenicity, ensuring high reproducibility and minimal batch-to-batch variability [102][103][104]. Their ability to undergo reversible denaturation allows for potential sensor reusability, making them well-suited for field applications [225].

Microfluidic technologies provide an ideal platform for phytohormone detection due to their precise fluid handling, controlled reaction environments, and enhanced assay kinetics [53][57][167][180]. By integrating an aptamer-based fluorescence assay within a microfluidic system, we enable rapid, sensitive, and field-deployable SA detection. In this study, we developed a tailored sample pre-treatment protocol for real strawberry samples and validated the assay using HPLC measurements. Our results demonstrate the potential of this microfluidic platform for real-time SA monitoring, offering a practical tool for early infection detection and improved agricultural disease management.

6.2. Materials and Methods

6.2.1. Fabrication of the microfluidic devices

The process of fabricating microfluidic devices with immobilized microbeads has been documented elsewhere [167]. The microfluidic designs were developed using AutoCAD 2024 software (version 24.3) (Autodesk, San Francisco, CA, USA). To create the aluminium hard masks, the design pattern was transferred to a Corning Eagle glass substrate with a layer of aluminium using direct-write laser lithography (Heidelberg DWLII, Heidelberg Instruments, Heidelberg, Germany), followed by etching with Gravure Aluminium Etchant (Microchemicals, Ulm, Germany). Since the microfluidic channels are made up of two different heights, two aluminium hard masks were fabricated. Using these hard masks, an SU-8 master mould was then manufactured using two different SU-8 photoresists, one for each height (SU-8 2015 for 20 μm , SU-8 50 for 100 μm layers, both from Microchem, Newton, MA, USA). The photoresist was spin-coated on top of a silicon wafer, followed by exposure to UV light through the aluminium hard mask (UV KUB-2, KLOÉ, Saint-Mathieu-de-Trévières, France) and then baked. Following the baking, the unexposed photoresist was removed with propylene glycol methyl ether acetate (PGMEA, Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA). To fabricate the PDMS structures (polydimethylsiloxane), the curing agent and base were mixed in a ratio of 1:10 (w/w) and degassed. The mixture was then poured onto the SU-8 mould and covered with a flat poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) frame and placed in the oven to cure at 70 °C for 90 min. Following this, the inlets and outlets of the structure were punctured, and the structure was sealed against a 500 μm -thick PDMS slab (fabricated under the same conditions) using oxygen plasma (Harrick Plasma, Ithaca, NY, USA).

6.2.2. Aptamer-based assay for SA detection

6.2.2.1. Reagents

Streptavidin microbeads (45–90 μm diameter) were sourced from Merck (Alameda Fernão Lopes, Algés, Portugal), while Phosphate Buffered Solution (PBS) 10 \times , and TE buffer were obtained from Fisher Scientific (Waltham, MA, USA). The biotinylated SA aptamer (the sequence was obtained from Chen *et al.* [103], who performed the SELEX for this aptamer, represented in Figure 1) and fluorescently labelled DNA (fdNA) were provided by Integrated DNA Technologies (Coralville, IA, USA), and both were resuspended in TE buffer to a 100 μM concentration—Table 6.1. Sodium chloride (NaCl), magnesium chloride (MgCl_2), Tris(hydroxymethyl) aminomethane, and methanol (MeOH), anhydrous 99.8%, were purchased

from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Lastly, Q-Sepharose microbeads (90 μm diameter) were obtained from Cytiva (Björkgatan, Uppsala, Sweden).

Table 6.1. Sequence of SA aptamer and fDNA molecules.

	Sequence (5' - 3')	Modification 5' end	Modification 3' end
SA Aptamer	CTTTCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCTTCCGTTACCCCTTATCTCATGC CTGCACTTGATCATGGTCTGTAGGCACCATCAATAGATCG	Biotin	none
fDNA	CGG GAA AGA TCG GAA GAG	Alexa ₄₃₀	none

6.2.2.2. Packing the biomarker detection chamber

The streptavidin microbeads were introduced into the microfluidic structure using a pipette tip, and a controlled negative pressure was applied at both the inlet₁ and outlet with a syringe pump (NE-4000, New Era Pumps, Farmingdale, NY, USA). The channel was first filled with PBS 1 \times by placing a pipette tip at inlet₂, followed by a 20 μL solution of bead suspension at a flow rate of 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, allowing the beads to accumulate inside the chamber. Once the beads were packed, inlet₂ was closed with a 20-gauge metal plug, and the chamber was washed with PBS 1 \times at 15 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. The structure was then submerged in DI and refrigerated overnight to remove any air bubbles that were introduced into the system during the packing process.

6.2.2.3. Fluorescence-based aptamer for SA detection

The aptamer-based assay was conducted using a microfluidic system containing a microcolumn packed with streptavidin microbeads, as described in Section 2.2.2, following a series of preparation, incubation, and detection steps. First, the aptamer solution was heated to 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 min to denature and unfold its structure, followed by rapid cooling in ice for 1 min to promote proper refolding into its active conformation. The analyte was then mixed with the aptamer and incubated outside the microfluidic channel for 30 min to allow sufficient binding before being introduced into the microfluidic system. The analyte–aptamer solution was then flowed through the microcolumn at 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 20 min, ensuring effective interaction with the microbeads. Following this, a fDNA probe was introduced at 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 5 min to enable signal detection. The fDNA sequence was designed to bind to a specific region of the aptamer, in such a way that it binds partially to the target binding section of the aptamer, and partially outside of this region, as seen in Figure 6.1 [226]. The target binding region, highlighted in red in Figure 1, was estimated from the results obtained by Chen *et al.* [225] through the SELEX process, where this region is changed throughout the cycles until an aptamer specific to the target is obtained. This interaction allows for the detection of SA, given that the binding of SA to the aptamer

influences the ability of the fDNA to bind to the aptamer as well. Lastly, to remove any unbound molecules and minimise background noise, the system was washed with SA buffer at 2.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 2 min.

Figure 6.1. Schematic representation of the aptamer biotinylated at the 5' end, folding structure under buffer conditions. In blue is highlighted the fDNA binding section, and in red the analyte binding section, with the overlapping portion in purple. Schematic generated in mFold, considering the salt concentrations and pH conditions used in the test [226].

6.2.3. Sample Collection and Preparation for SA Detection in Strawberries

To evaluate the sensitivity of the SA detection assay, strawberries were purchased from a local supermarket and stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until further analysis. These strawberries were selected because they were not expected to contain high levels of SA (Figure 2A), in contrast to infected strawberries, which typically have higher levels of SA. The strawberries were analysed using HPLC, which confirmed the absence of SA in the samples. Figure S6.1 in the Supplementary Materials displays the chromatograms obtained from HPLC.

Figure 6.2. Photographs of supermarket-purchased strawberries and *Botrytis cinerea*-infected strawberries ((A) and (B), respectively), alongside a schematic representation of the sample treatment process (C). The process includes maceration of the strawberries with 5% of MeOH, followed by centrifugation (2000 rpm, 20 minutes), filtration through a 0.2 μm pore filter, and a bead cleaning step within the microfluidic channel. The columns used for bead trapping were 1 cm long, 0.1 cm wide, and 100 μm high. Additionally, a smaller channel (200 μm wide, 20 μm high) was incorporated to capture *Q*-Sepharose microbeads larger than 20 μm in diameter.

To validate the developed method, strawberries infected with *Botrytis cinerea* (Figure 2B) were collected from a local farm. These were quickly frozen in liquid nitrogen, transported in dry ice to the laboratory, and kept at -80°C until processing. The infected strawberry samples were analysed using HPLC, which confirmed the presence of SA at a concentration of 8×10^{-3} mg/mL. Figure S6.2 in the Supplementary Materials displays the calibration curve used to quantify the amount of SA in the infected strawberry sample.

The sample preparation, as shown in Figure 6.2C, began by macerating the strawberries in a 5% MeOH solution in PBS 1×, mixed at a 1:1 ratio (*w/v*) for 8 minutes. The mixture was then centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 20 min, and the pellet of cell debris at the bottom was discarded. To further purify the sample and remove large debris, the supernatant was filtered through a 0.2 μm

nylon syringe filter. To remove any remaining contaminants not captured by the filter, the solution was flowed through Q-Sepharose beads packed in a microfluidic channel at 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 10 min. Lastly, the solution was diluted to achieve a 1% MeOH concentration in the sample, due to preliminary tests showing that a higher MeOH percentage hinders molecular recognition [167].

6.2.3.1. Packing of the Sample Treatment Chamber

The Q-Sepharose microbeads were similarly inserted into the microchannel as described in Section 6.2.2.2. The microchannel was first filled with PBS 1 \times by placing a pipette tip at inlet₁ and applying negative pressure with a syringe pump. Following this, a pipette with 30 μL bead suspension solution was placed at inlet₂ (Figure 6.2), and a 12 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ flow rate was applied until the microchannel was fully packed. This was followed by washing with PBS 1 \times at 22 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ and sealing inlet₂ with a 20-gauge metal plug.

6.2.4. Fluorescence Imaging and Data Analysis

The fluorescence signals for the experimental assay were collected using a Leica DMLM microscope, coupled with a DFC300FX digital camera and a CoolLED pE-300lite lamp for excitation. The imaging system was fitted with an I3 filter cube, which enabled excitation in the 450–490 nm range (blue) and captured fluorescence emission above 515 nm (green). Image analysis was conducted with ImageJ software 1.49 (NIH, USA), focusing solely on the green fluorescence channel [162]. To quantify fluorescence intensity, the background signal was subtracted from a reference region outside the experimental area. All images used for SA quantification were acquired with a fixed exposure time of 1 s and a gain setting of 1 \times to maintain measurement consistency.

6.2.5. Quantification of SA Using Reverse-Phase HPLC

The concentration of SA in strawberry samples was measured using a Hitachi LaChrom HPLC system, which consisted of two pumps (L-7100), a UV detector (L-7400), a programmable autosampler (L-7250), and a data interface (Hitachi D-7000) for computer connectivity. A core-shell organo-silica LC column (5 μm EVO C18 100 \AA , 250 \times 4.6 mm) from Kinetex was employed for the analysis, with UV detection set at 206 nm. Chromatographic separation was performed in isocratic mode, using a mobile phase composed of sodium phosphate buffer (50 mM, pH 3.55, Sigma-Aldrich) and acetonitrile (VWR) in a 75:25 (v/v) ratio. The injection volume was 25 μL , with a flow rate of 1.2 mL/min, following the procedure described in reference [167]. Under these conditions, the retention time of SA was approximately 3.12 minutes.

6.3. Results and Discussion

This study developed a microfluidic-based method for detecting SA in strawberries, leveraging SA as a biomarker for plant stress and pathogen response. SA plays a crucial role in plant defence, particularly against biotic stress, such as pathogen infections. The detection strategy utilises a biotinylated SA aptamer immobilised on streptavidin-coated microbeads, which are mechanically trapped within the microfluidic channel. The incorporation of microbeads enhances assay sensitivity and efficiency by increasing the surface area for aptamer immobilisation and minimising diffusion distances, thereby reducing assay time. In this approach, a fDNA is designed to hybridise with a specific region of the aptamer. Upon SA binding, the aptamer undergoes a conformational change, increasing the accessibility of the fDNA binding site and leading to an enhanced fluorescence signal, enabling sensitive and specific SA detection.

6.3.1. SA Spiked in Binding Buffer

The first step in developing the assay was to determine the optimal concentrations of the SA aptamer and fDNA to ensure a functional and sensitive detection method. Figure S6.3 in the Supplementary Materials shows a summary of the optimisation steps. These concentrations were carefully optimised to generate a measurable fluorescence signal while maintaining responsiveness to varying SA levels. The fDNA concentration was set slightly higher than that of the aptamer to facilitate competitive binding. Excessive fDNA concentration would lead to no competition with SA for aptamer binding, reducing assay sensitivity, whereas too little fDNA would lead to indiscriminate binding, making it difficult to distinguish SA concentrations. After optimisation, the SA aptamer and fDNA concentrations were fixed at 0.3 μM and 0.4 μM , respectively.

After establishing the optimal concentrations of SA aptamer and fDNA, we evaluated the relationship between fluorescence intensity and varying SA concentrations in the binding buffer (20 mM Tris, pH 7.5, 5 mM MgCl_2 , 137 mM NaCl) [25][225]. A series of SA solutions, diluted from an initial stock concentration of 5 mg/mL, were prepared to determine the minimum detectable SA concentration using the microfluidic system and aptamer-based assay, as shown in Figure 6.3. The fluorescence signal varied with SA concentration, reflecting the dynamic interactions between SA, fDNA, and the immobilised aptamer. Within the concentration range of 10^{-9} to 10^{-6} mg/mL, the fluorescence intensity increased with higher SA concentrations, indicating that SA binding induces a conformational change in the aptamer, enhancing its affinity for fDNA. However, at higher SA concentrations (10^{-5} to 10^{-3} mg/mL), the fluorescence signal plateaued, similar to the non-spiked assay. This behaviour suggests that at higher SA concentrations, the analyte may form aggregates, rendering the aptamer binding site inaccessible,

which prevents efficient capture and results in a reduced fluorescence signal, returning to baseline levels.

Figure 6.3. Aptamer- based assay for SA detection: **(A)** The microfluidic device for biomarker detection was designed with distinct channel heights to facilitate different functions within the system. A 100 μm -high channel was allocated specifically for bead packing, allowing efficient retention and arrangement of the streptavidin-coated microbeads (approximately 90 μm in diameter). Meanwhile, a 20 μm -high channel was used for the controlled injection of samples and reagents. The variation in channel heights played a crucial role in bead confinement, as the lower-height inlet and outlet channels acted as physical barriers, effectively preventing the passage of microbeads larger than 20 μm while allowing fluid flow; **(B)** The detection strategy involved immobilising SA aptamers onto streptavidin-coated microbeads, which were mechanically confined within the microfluidic channel. In this approach, the fDNA is designed to complement a specific region of the aptamer. When the analyte is present, the aptamer undergoes a conformational change that enhances the binding affinity of the fDNA; **(C)** The fluorescence response curve was generated for varying SA target concentrations, ranging from 10⁹ mg/mL to 10³ mg/mL. The excitation wavelength was set between 450 and 490 nm (blue). Error bars indicate the standard deviation (\pm) of four replicas.

The selectivity of this detection method was confirmed using different analytes, ABA, and JA, for the highest detectable concentration, 10^{-6} mg/mL, showed no change from the non-spiked assay. These supporting data are in Figure S6.4 in the Supplementary Information.

6.3.2. SA Spiked in Supermarket Treated Strawberries Samples

After validating the assay's sensitivity under optimal conditions using SA in the binding buffer, we tested the method on strawberries purchased from a local supermarket, which were free from detectable SA (as detailed in Figure S6.1 of the Supplementary Materials). A specific sample preparation protocol was developed, as outlined in Figure 6.2 and described in Section 6.2.3. A critical step in this protocol was bead cleaning, which removed large particles that might have bypassed initial filtration and interfered with detection. Applying this procedure to strawberry samples, we conducted the microfluidic assay and collected fluorescence data (Figure 6.4), establishing a correlation between SA concentration and fluorescence intensity. The results indicated that the fluorescence response from the strawberry samples closely matched that of the binding buffer, confirming the effectiveness of the sample preparation in eliminating most interfering compounds. The slight reduction in fluorescence observed with strawberry samples, compared to buffer-only assays, is likely due to residual contaminants. With a validated method for detecting SA in the binding buffer and an effective preparation process for strawberry samples, we next analysed SA levels in infected strawberries, anticipating a natural increase in SA concentration during infection.

Figure 6.4. Fluorescence curve response in strawberries. The aptamer-based assay for detecting SA was conducted using strawberry samples spiked with SA, with concentrations varying from 10^{-9} to 10^{-3} mg/mL. Fluorescence was measured with an excitation wavelength between 450 and 490 nm (blue). Error bars indicate the standard deviation (\pm) of two replicas.

6.3.3. SA in Naturally Infected Strawberry Samples

To validate the SA detection method, we selected strawberry samples based on their expected SA levels, given SA's key role in plant defence mechanisms. Infected strawberries naturally accumulate higher SA concentrations in response to pathogen attacks, while healthy strawberries typically have minimal SA levels. Before analysis, all samples underwent a standardised preparation process (outlined in Section 6.2.3) to ensure consistency and eliminate potential interferents. High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) analysis confirmed significantly higher SA concentrations in infected strawberries. Quantification, detailed in Figure S6.2 of the Supplementary Materials, determined the SA concentration in these samples to be 8×10^{-3} mg/mL.

The microfluidic assay results for SA detection (Figure 6.5) aligned with HPLC findings, confirming the assay's reliability. Given that the microfluidic assay is optimised for SA concentrations in the 10^{-9} to 10^{-6} mg/mL range, and the infected strawberry sample contained approximately 10^{-3} mg/mL of SA (as determined by HPLC), dilution was necessary for accurately reaching a concentration within the range of detection of the developed assay analysis. Following the sample treatment protocol (Section 6.2.3), the infected sample underwent serial dilutions until reaching a concentration within the assay's sensitivity range. A 1000-fold dilution yielded a fluorescence signal corresponding to an SA concentration of 10^{-6} mg/mL on the response curve,

corresponding to a concentration of 10^{-3} mg/mL before dilution, matching the results obtained via HPLC and validating the assay's capacity to detect SA at this concentration.

An alternative sample treatment protocol was evaluated to simplify the process for potential field use, replacing the original method that required centrifugation. This simplified approach involved only maceration followed by a bead cleaning step. However, as shown in Figure 6.5, while both methods yielded similar results, the simplified protocol was less effective in thoroughly cleaning the sample compared to the centrifugation-based method [201]. This suggests that, although the simplified treatment is more convenient, centrifugation remains essential for optimal sample preparation and analysis.

It's important to note that the SA concentrations reported in the previous sections are five times lower than their actual values. This discrepancy arises from the final step of the sample treatment protocol, which involves a $5\times$ dilution of the samples. Consequently, the estimated SA concentration in the infected samples before dilution is approximately 4×10^{-2} mg/mL.

Figure 6.5. Validation of SA detection method in real strawberry samples. SA concentrations were determined using the microfluidic aptamer-based detection method following sample processing, with additional $10\times$, $100\times$, $1000\times$, and $10,000\times$ dilutions. The shades of red represent strawberry samples subjected to maceration, centrifugation, filtration, and bead cleaning step, while the shades of brown indicate samples that underwent maceration and bead cleaning step only, without centrifugation. Error bars represent \pm the standard deviation of two replicas.

6.4. Conclusions

In this study, we developed a microfluidic platform suitable for field applications, incorporating a simplified sample cleaning protocol for the detection of SA in plants. SA serves as a biomarker indicative of plant stress, especially biotic stresses such as fungal infections, accumulating at infection sites as part of the plant's defence mechanisms. Continuous monitoring of SA levels enables early detection of such infections.

The platform utilises an aptamer-based assay, employing streptavidin-coated microbeads to immobilise biotinylated aptamers within the microfluidic channel. Detection is achieved through a labelled DNA strand complementary to a segment of the aptamer. In the presence of the analyte, the aptamer undergoes a conformational change, leading to an increase in the fluorescence signal. Sensitivity evaluations under buffer conditions and validations with strawberry samples infected with *Botrytis cinerea* demonstrated the platform's capability to detect SA concentrations, with limits of detection ranging from 10^{-9} to 10^{-6} mg/mL.

The platform also features simplified sample treatment protocols, eliminating the need for complex analyte extraction and isolation procedures. An improved protocol, omitting the centrifugation step, is field-ready and does not require sophisticated laboratory equipment; however, it slightly reduces assay sensitivity. The detected concentration range aligns with reported values, and the method exhibits greater sensitivity compared to other SA detection techniques. The developed sample treatment protocol, together with the microfluidic assay, allows us to obtain results in under 2 hours, surpassing the traditional methods that require lengthy procedures, both at the analyte extraction and the detection stage [25][227]. Additionally, as quantitative information as to how SA values change with infection levels is limited, as baseline values are cultivar dependent, the developed device could be used to measure SA values throughout time and provide valuable information that farmers could use to optimise their crop management.

Utilising this platform in the field allows for rapid, sensitive, and continuous monitoring of SA concentrations in strawberries and other fruits, facilitating timely infection detection. This capability equips farmers with tools to implement preventive measures, effectively controlling the spread of pathogens that could lead to yield losses during harvest, transportation, and storage.

PART III

Chapter 7

Conclusions & Future work

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7.1. Conclusions

My Ph.D. research is centred on the development of an innovative, miniaturized analytical device for rapid, on-site detection of grapevine infections and hydric stress. The device is based on a user-friendly microfluidic biochip, designed for standalone, field-based applications. The initial phase of my thesis focused on exploring technologies to develop a device for real-time immunoassays, aiming to improve the efficiency and accuracy of bead-based assays for rapid diagnostics and field applications. The second phase focused on addressing the PoC potential of this technology to create a portable device that can perform immunoassays in diverse on-site environments.

The key goals achieved in the research are outlined by topic, highlighting the progress made in real-time diagnostics and PoC applications:

- ❖ The integration of a microfluidic platform for AK detection with a cell culture microfluidic device demonstrated the ability to monitor cell damage with high sensitivity. This system successfully detected AK in the supernatant of human colorectal adenocarcinoma HCT116 cells, corresponding to approximately 10–100 lysed cells. By utilizing NHS-Sepharose microbeads for AK capture and fluorescent antibodies for detection, the device enabled real-time, miniaturized analysis of cell damage. When paired with a cell culture platform, the system detected AK released from lysed cells cultured in the chip and monitored the impact of the chemotherapeutic agent 5-FU over time. The integration of this microfluidic biosensor, along with the potential to incorporate additional biosensors, holds promise for improving the efficiency and quality of drug discovery and disease treatment procedures.
- ❖ A microfluidic platform was developed for sensitive detection of ABA, a key plant hormone involved in fruit ripening and drought stress response. Using Protein-A microbeads functionalized with anti-ABA antibodies, the system detects ABA at concentrations as low as 10^{-3} to 10^{-6} mg/mL in buffer solutions. When tested with grape samples, it identified ABA levels up to 10^{-5} mg/mL during the *veraison* stage, demonstrating its potential for in-field agricultural monitoring.
- ❖ A versatile microfluidic system was developed for rapid and efficient biomarker detection, tailored for diagnostics in non-laboratory settings such as in-field or at-home use. The system combines antibody-functionalized microbeads and a competitive immunoassay with an optical transducer featuring a hydrogenated amorphous silicon (a-Si: H) p-i-n photodiode, which functions as a fluorescence signal transduction mechanism. This design enables precise fluorophore quantification at low concentrations, with a LOD of 0.36 nM. The integration of interference filters, while more complex,

expands the range of compatible fluorophores compared to traditional microscope filter cubes, eliminating the need for microscopy equipment. This innovation makes the device compact, portable, and ideal for PoC or remote applications, supporting fast, sensitive, and specific detection of disease-associated biomarkers for early diagnosis and health monitoring.

- ❖ Two sample treatment protocols were developed. The first involved sample maceration, centrifugation at 2000 rpm for 10 minutes, filtration using a 0.2 μm pore diameter filter, and a bead-based cleaning step within a microfluidic channel. Subsequently, a new optimization was implemented to simplify the protocol. The optimized procedure involves sample maceration followed directly by a bead-based cleaning step within a microfluidic channel. Designed for field use, this simplified method eliminates the need for skilled operators, lengthy analysis times, and high costs, as well as the reliance on equipment like centrifuges, which are typically unavailable in field settings;
- ❖ A reusable, capillary-driven microfluidic system with a two-height design to trap beads within the chamber platform, made from a PDMS-PEG copolymer, was developed for portable, cost-effective plant hormone analysis, eliminating the need for external pumps or power sources. By using a competitive immunoassay with anti-ABA antibody-functionalized microbeads, the system detects ABA with LOD ranging from 10^{-6} to 10^{-4} mg/mL, enabling precise monitoring of plant stress and development. The platform, which enables at least four reuses coupled with an external cleaning protocol, effectively detects ABA in real grapevine samples, especially during stress or ripening stages. This system supports precision agriculture by providing real-time hormone monitoring, enhancing crop management, and bridging the gap between laboratory and field diagnostics.
- ❖ A microfluidic platform was developed for the sensitive detection of SA, a key plant defence hormone. The system uses a biotinylated SA aptamer on streptavidin-coated microbeads, which changes conformation upon binding with the analyte, increasing accessibility to the fDNA and enhancing fluorescence. The platform detected SA with LOD ranging from 10^{-9} to 10^{-6} mg/mL, highlighting its potential for in-field monitoring. Given that these stresses affect various crops, the platform was validated with strawberry samples in the absence of contaminated grape samples.

While significant progress was made throughout the research, several challenges and setbacks were encountered along the way:

- ❖ During the optimization of the immunoassays, a consideration emerged regarding the ratio of antibodies to microbeads, which is critical for consistent assay performance. Since the functionalization of protein-A microbeads with the antibody is performed off-

chip, followed by packing the functionalized beads into the microfluidic channels, it is essential to ensure that the number of microbeads is consistent in each assay. The standard protocol involves mixing 3 μL of beads with 19 μL of antibody. However, pipetting 3 μL does not guarantee a uniform number of beads, even when using the same bead stock. Maintaining a consistent number of beads is necessary to ensure a constant amount of available antibodies, preserving the competition conditions between the analyte and the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate for the binding sites. Any variation in bead quantity affects this ratio, disrupting the competition and compromising assay performance;

- ❖ Another point regarding the optimization of the competitive assay is the concentration of antibody and conjugate. The concentration of anti-ABA antibody must be carefully controlled to avoid an excess of binding sites. If the antibody concentration is too high, both the free analyte and the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate could bind to the antibody, eliminating competition. The concentration of the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate is selected based on the antibody concentration used for bead functionalization. It must always be lower than the antibody concentration to ensure that the analyte can effectively compete for binding sites; otherwise, the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate would dominate, disrupting the competition;
- ❖ In addition to utilizing fluorescence-based detection, an attempt was made to implement chemiluminescence detection, which is more suitable for field applications as it does not require external light sources and allows for a constant substrate flow to sustain enzymatic reactions at maximum velocity. However, the results were consistently unpromising, possibly due to disruptions in the proportions necessary for effective competition between the analyte and the labelled ABA-BSA. As a result, this approach was ultimately abandoned;
- ❖ The selected targets are insoluble in water; therefore, MeOH was chosen as the reagent for this purpose. During buffer experiments, it was observed that the presence of MeOH affected the molecular recognition between the target and the antibody. As a result, varying MeOH concentrations under the same experimental conditions led to different fluorescence intensity values. To address this, the MeOH concentration was standardized at 1% across all experiments. This approach was also applied to experiments conducted with real sample matrices;
- ❖ Additional molecules, including JA, Aza, and IAA, were selected for stress detection. Detection methods were developed for each, based on a competitive assay. However, the antibodies or conjugates required for detection were discontinued from the market, making it impossible to proceed with the optimization process and subsequent validation;
- ❖ Building on the previously mentioned issue of product discontinuation, many commercially available products, such as the anti-SA antibody, were of insufficient

quality. This challenge prompted a shift towards detecting phytohormones using aptamers. However, synthesizing aptamers without prior SELEX is impractical. For SA, an aptamer sequence was already available, as a research group had previously conducted the SELEX process and published the sequence [225];

- ❖ Other molecules, such as PolyGalacturonase-Inhibiting Protein (PGIP), were considered as potential targets. PGIP plays a vital role in protecting plants from fungal pathogens by inhibiting the action of fungal endopolygalacturonases, which would otherwise degrade pectin and compromise the plant's cell wall integrity [228]. However, we were advised against this approach by Professor Ana Margarida Fortes, as fungi have developed countermeasures to overcome PGIP-mediated inhibition. Throughout the four years of my thesis, I received valuable support not only from Professor Fortes but also from Sogrape;

7.2. Future Work

Building on the findings and challenges of this research, future work will focus on refining the approach, optimizing detection methods, enhancing system sensitivity, and exploring further applications in disease monitoring and crop management.

- ❖ Another important aspect to consider is the early detection of infections to control their spread and ensure the vine can be treated promptly with a controlled amount of plant protection products, preventing pathogen resistance. Early detection refers to identifying infections before stress-induced damage becomes visible to the naked eye, which requires a highly sensitive method. In this context, it is preferable to choose a detection method based on pathogen DNA rather than detecting stress-related markers like SA and AzA, as these are only produced in high quantities when the infection is relatively advanced. By the time SA and AzA levels are elevated, it may be too late to save the vine. Therefore, with the goal of early detection, DNA amplification techniques, such as LAMP, were considered. LAMP is a powerful molecular technique for amplifying DNA with high specificity, efficiency, and speed under isothermal conditions. It utilizes a DNA polymerase with strong strand-displacement activity along with a specially designed set of primers. These primers bind to multiple regions of the target DNA, typically four to six primers targeting six to eight distinct sites on the gene of interest. The selected fungus for this study was *Botrytis cinerea*, which significantly affects grape and strawberry crops. Primers were designed for its detection, and preliminary results have shown promising outcomes, supporting further research in this direction;

Primer design for LAMP was performed using the PrimerExplorer V5 software [229]. The ITS gene (GenBank accession no. KP900730) was chosen as the target due to its common use in *Botrytis cinerea* detection and its slight variation between strains, which enhances specificity (Table 7.1).

Table 7.1. Sequence of the ITS gene.

IST sequence

TCATTACAGAGTTCATGCCCGAAAGGGTAGACCTCCCACCCTTGTGTATTATTAC
TTTGTTGCTTTGGCGAGCTGCCTTCGGGCCTTGTATGCTCGCCAGAGAATACCAA
AACTCTTTTTATTAATGTCGTCTGAGTACTATATAATAGTAAAACCTTCAACAAC
GGATCTCTTGGTTCTGGCATCGATGAAGAACGCAGCGAAATGCGATAAGTAATG
TGAATTGCAGAATTCAGTGAATCATC

The designed primers are listed in Table 7.2. Following primer design, macroscale experiments were conducted to optimize primer concentrations. Three different primer mixtures were tested (Figure 7.1A):

Mix 1: [Loop] = 2.5 μ M, [B3/F3] = 1.25 μ M, [FIP/BIP] = 5 μ M

Mix 2: [Loop] = 1.25 μ M, [B3/F3] = 0.625 μ M, [FIP/BIP] = 2.5 μ M

Mix 3: [Loop] = 5 μ M, [B3/F3] = 2.5 μ M, [FIP/BIP] = 10 μ M

The results indicated that Mix 3 provided the best performance (Figure 7.1A). The reaction conditions were adapted from previous microfluidic LAMP studies and included: [dNTPs] = 1 mM, [MgSO₄] = 8 mM, [Bst polymerase] = 0.32 U/ μ L, 1 \times buffer, and 100 \times dye, with an incubation temperature of 65 $^{\circ}$ C [230][231][232].

Another experiment was conducted to optimize the reaction conditions by varying the concentrations of key components, including dNTPs, MgSO₄, and Bst polymerase. The results, presented in Figure 7.1B, indicated that the optimal conditions were: [dNTPs] = 1 mM, [MgSO₄] = 8 mM, [Bst] = 1 U/ μ L, 1 \times buffer, and 100 \times dye.

The next steps involve generating a calibration curve and subsequently applying the assay to the microfluidic platform. The microfluidic structure, already fabricated, is shown in Figure 7.1C. It was designed with a capacity of 25 μ L, matching the reaction volume used in the experiments.

Table 7.2. Sequence of LAMP primers (F3, B3, FIP, BIP, and LB).

Primers	Sequence (5' - 3')
F3	AAAGGGTAGACCTCCCAC
B3	GATGATTCACCTGAATTCTGCA
FIP	TCTCTGGCGAGCATAACAAGGGTGTATTACTTTGTTGCTTTGG
BIP	AACTTTCAACAACGGATCTCTTGGTCACATTACTTATCGCATTTTCG
LB	TTCTGGCATCGATGAAGAACGCA

Figure 7.1. LAMP macroscale experiment results and microfluidic integration: (A) Primer concentration optimization—Mix 1: [Loop] = 2.5 μM , [B3/F3] = 1.25 μM , [FIP/BIP] = 5 μM ; Mix 2: [Loop] = 1.25 μM , [B3/F3] = 0.625 μM , [FIP/BIP] = 2.5 μM ; Mix 3: [Loop] = 5 μM , [B3/F3] = 2.5 μM , [FIP/BIP] = 10 μM . (B) Optimization of reaction conditions by varying dNTP, MgSO₄, and Bst polymerase concentrations. (C) Schematic representation of the fabricated microfluidic structure, designed with a 25 μL reaction chamber to accommodate the optimized LAMP assay. The structure measures 23 mm in length, 6 mm in width, and 100 μm in height, with 800 μm posts throughout. The channels connecting the chamber to the outside progressively increase in width, starting at 300 μm and expanding to 500 μm near the chamber.

- ❖ There is the potential to integrate all developed modules—sample treatment, optical sensor for signal measurement, and capillary action—into a fully autonomous platform that can be used in the field without the need for bulky equipment.
- ❖ Recent studies have highlighted the crucial role of ABA in regulating glucose metabolism in mammals. The research demonstrates that nanomolar concentrations of

ABA can stimulate glucose uptake in skeletal muscle and adipose tissue via an insulin-independent pathway. As a result, the platform developed in this thesis for ABA detection could be utilized not only for monitoring plant water stress but also for human health applications. This review underscores the potential of ABA as a therapeutic agent for managing metabolic disorders, including diabetes and metabolic syndrome, and calls for further clinical studies to evaluate its efficacy and safety in human health applications [233].

- ❖ Messenger RNAs (mRNAs) play a crucial role in detecting and responding to stresses and infections in grapevines by reflecting changes in gene expression. When grapevines face biotic stress (such as fungal, bacterial, or viral infections), genes like PR1, PR3, and VvSTS (stilbene synthase) are upregulated to activate defence mechanisms against pathogens like *Plasmopara viticola* (downy mildew) and *Botrytis cinerea* (gray mould) [234][235]. Similarly, during abiotic stress, such as drought, genes like VvNCED3 (involved in ABA biosynthesis) and VvRD22 (responsive to dehydration) are activated to help the plant conserve water and maintain cellular stability [236]. These changes at the mRNA level can be detected using techniques like RNA sequencing (RNA-seq), quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR), and LAMP, allowing researchers to identify early stress signals, understand resistance mechanisms, and develop strategies to improve grapevine resilience [237][238][239].

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Supplementary Information

Chapter 2

Figure S2.1. Detection of AK resulting from cell damage in cell chips. Two different procedures were performed: (A) Cell growth + RIPA lysis in the microfluidic cell culture chamber. (B) Cell growth + 5-FU + RIPA lysis in the microfluidic cell chamber.

Figure S2.2. Optimization performed related to blocking agent, using $[AK] = 0 \mu M$ (absence) and $[anti-AK antibody] = 1 \text{ mg/mL}$.

Chapter 3

Figure S3.1. Sequence of steps involved in the fabrication of the (A) aluminium hard masks; (B) SU-8 negative photoresist mould; and (C) PDMS structures used for trapping beads.

Figure S3.2. A selection of the results of optimization assays of the concentration of labelled ABA-BSA conjugate to be used in the competitive immunoassay.

Figure S3.3. Proposed mechanisms of ABA detection at different ABA concentrations: (A) schematic of the competitive fluorescence immunoassay, with the respective fluorescence micrograph, present at low ABA concentrations; (B) schematic of the aggregation between the labelled ABA-BSA conjugate and the analyte, with the respective fluorescence micrograph, highlighting the presence of aggregates, present at high ABA concentrations.

Figure S3.4. Calibration curve for different concentrations of ABA using HPLC.

Chapter 6

(A) Strawberries Purchased from a Local Supermarket

(B) Strawberries Purchased from a Local Supermarket + 0.025 mg/mL Spike of SA

Figure S6.1. Chromatograms obtained via HPLC for strawberries purchased from a local supermarket: (A) Chromatogram from the strawberry sample; (B) Chromatogram from the strawberry sample spiked with 0.025 mg/mL of SA. In graph (B), where 0.025 mg/mL of SA was spiked, a peak appears at a retention time of 3.12 minutes. However, in graph (A), no peak is observed at the same retention time. This indicates that the strawberries purchased from a local supermarket do not naturally contain SA, making it an ideal matrix for constructing the calibration curve.

Figure S6.2. A calibration curve was established using HPLC by analysing samples with known concentrations of SA. The resulting data was plotted, with the peak area on the y-axis and the corresponding SA concentrations on the x-axis. This calibration curve allowed for the determination of unknown SA concentrations in real samples. Specifically, the infected sample by *Botrytis cinerea* produced a peak area of 37,875 A.U. By substituting this value into the equation of the calibration line, the SA concentration in the contaminated sample was calculated to be 8×10^{-3} mg/mL. This approach utilizes the linear relationship between peak area and concentration, providing a precise means of quantifying SA in complex samples.

Figure S6.3. A selection of the results of optimization assays of the concentration of aptamer and labelled DNA to be used in the aptamer-based assay. The excitation wavelength was set between 450 and 490 nm (blue). Error bars indicate the standard deviation (\pm) of two replicas.

Figure S6.4. Evaluation of the assay specificity through measurements of buffer solutions spiked with SA, ABA, and JA. The excitation wavelength was set between 450 and 490 nm (blue). Error bars indicate the standard deviation (\pm) of two replicas.